

Applications of Fast Multipole Method to Boundary Integral Equation Method

Ken-ichi Yoshida

Dept. of Global Environment Eng.
Kyoto Univ., Japan

March 2001

Contents

1	Introduction	2
1.1	Background	2
1.2	Organization of thesis	2
2	Overview of Fast Multipole Method (FMM)	4
2.1	Brief history of FMM and other fast solution methods	4
2.2	Basic framework of FM-BIEM	6
2.2.1	Basic role of FMM in FM-BIEM	6
2.2.2	Formulation for FM-BIEM	7
2.2.3	Fast multipole algorithm and estimation of its computational cost	10
3	Applications of FMM to three-dimensional crack problems	17
3.1	Crack	17
3.1.1	Notation	17
3.1.2	Integral equation for crack problems in three-dimensional elastostatics	18
3.1.3	A note on integral equations	19
3.2	Crack problems for three-dimensional Laplace's equation	20
3.2.1	Integral Equation	20
3.2.2	FM-BIEM with hypersingular integral equation	21
3.2.3	FM-BIEM with regularised integral equation	22
3.2.4	Numerical procedure	23
3.2.5	Numerical examples	25
3.3	Crack problems for three-dimensional elastostatics with collocation method	32
3.3.1	Integral equation	32
3.3.2	FM-BIEM with hypersingular integral equation	33
3.3.3	FM-BIEM with regularised integral equation	34
3.3.4	Numerical procedures	36
3.3.5	Numerical examples	37
3.3.6	Comparison of formulations for the single- and double-layer potentials	45
3.4	Crack problems for three-dimensional elastostatics with Galerkin's method	47
3.4.1	Variational Boundary Integral Equation	47
3.4.2	FM-GBIEM	48
3.4.3	Algorithm	49
3.4.4	Algorithm for computing stress	51
3.4.5	Numerical examples	51
3.5	Three-dimensional scattering of scalar waves by cracks	61
3.5.1	Integral equation	61
3.5.2	FM-BIEM	62
3.5.3	Numerical procedures	63
3.5.4	Numerical examples	65
3.5.5	Relation between formulations in Laplace's equation and Helmholtz's equation	72
3.6	Three-dimensional scattering of elastic waves by a crack	73
3.6.1	Integral equation	73
3.6.2	FM-BIEM	74
3.6.3	Numerical procedure	75
3.6.4	Numerical examples	77
3.6.5	Comparison of formulations for the double-layer potential	82

3.7	Concluding remarks	82
4	Applications of the new FMM to three-dimensional problems	84
4.1	Crack problems for three-dimensional Laplace's equation	85
4.1.1	New FM-BIEM	85
4.1.2	Rotation of coefficients	87
4.1.3	Algorithm for the new FM-BIEM	89
4.1.4	Numerical examples	89
4.2	Crack problems for three-dimensional elastostatics	94
4.2.1	New FM-BIEM	94
4.2.2	Rotation of coefficients	95
4.2.3	Algorithm for the new FM-BIEM	98
4.2.4	Numerical examples	98
4.3	Concluding remarks	102
5	Final remarks	103
A	Series expansion of $\frac{1}{ x-y }$	104
B	Relations between solid harmonics $R_{n,m}$ and $S_{n,m}$	106
C	Recurrence formulae for $R_{n,m}$ and $S_{n,m}$	109
D	Derivatives of $R_{n,m}$ and $S_{n,m}$	110
E	M2M, M2L, L2L in three-dimensional Laplace's equation	112
E.1	M2M translation formula	112
E.2	M2L translation formula	112
E.3	L2L translation formula	113
F	Series expansion of $x - y$	114
G	Series expansion of the fundamental solution of three-dimensional elastostatics	116
H	M2M, M2L, L2L in three-dimensional elastostatics	119
H.1	M2M translation formula	119
H.2	M2L translation formula	120
H.3	L2L translation formula	121
I	M2M, M2L, L2L in three-dimensional Helmholtz's equation	122
I.1	M2M translation formula	122
I.2	M2L translation formula	122
I.3	L2L translation formula	123
J	M2X, X2X, X2L in three-dimensional Laplace's equation	124
J.1	M2X translation formula	124
J.2	X2X translation formula	125
J.3	X2L translation formula	126
K	M2X, X2X, X2L in three-dimensional elastostatics	127
K.1	M2X translation formula	127
K.2	X2X translation formula	127
K.3	X2L translation formula	128
L	Regularisation of integral equations	129
L.1	Regularisation of BIE in three-dimensional Laplace's equation	129
L.2	Regularisation of BIE in three-dimensional elastostatics	129
L.3	Regularisation of VBIE in three-dimensional elastostatics	130
L.4	Regularisation of BIE in three-dimensional Helmholtz's equation	131
L.5	Regularisation of BIE in three-dimensional elastodynamics	131

List of Figures

2.1	Conventional evaluation of contribution from distant particles: $O(N^2)$ algorithm	5
2.2	Multipole moment represents distant particles	5
2.3	Evaluation with the multipole moment and the local expansion: $O(N)$ algorithm	5
2.4	Particles and the corresponding binary tree	6
2.5	Configuration of points and regions	7
2.6	Construction of a tree structure and corresponding quad-tree	11
2.7	Boundary element is in a cell or not	12
2.8	M2M translation and L2L translation	12
2.9	Adjacent cells and well-separated cells	13
2.10	Discretisation (Step 1)	13
2.11	Construction of tree structure (Step 2)	14
2.12	Multipole moments and M2M translation (Step 3)	14
2.13	M2L and L2L translation (Step 4)	15
2.14	Evaluation of total contribution (Step 5)	15
3.1	Notations about a crack	17
3.2	Domain D and surfaces S_1 and S_2	18
3.3	Domain D and surfaces S_2 , S^+ and S^-	19
3.4	Line integration for analytical computation of $\widetilde{M}_{j,n,m}$	24
3.5	Crack mesh (DOF=9592)	26
3.6	Total CPU time (sec)	27
3.7	CPU time per iteration (sec)	27
3.8	Ratio of the time required with FM-BIEM (TimeFM-BIEM) to the time required with the conventional BIEM (TimeBIEM)	28
3.9	L_2 -norm Error	28
3.10	Crack opening displacement ϕ/u_0 obtained with NE1 and NE2	29
3.11	Crack opening displacement ϕ/u_0 obtained with NE1 and NE3	29
3.12	Crack opening displacement ϕ/u_0 obtained with NE1 and NE4	30
3.13	Crack opening displacement	30
3.14	Crack mesh (DOF=30,208)	31
3.15	Crack opening displacement (DOF=30,208)	31
3.16	Line integration for analytical computation of $\widetilde{M}_{kj,n,m}^1$ and $\widetilde{M}_{k,n,m}^2$	37
3.17	Total CPU time (sec)	39
3.18	CPU time per iteration (sec)	39
3.19	Ratio of the time required with FM-BIEM (TimeFM-BIEM) to the time required with the conventional BIEM (TimeBIEM)	40
3.20	L_2 -norm Error	40
3.21	Crack opening displacement NE1 and NE2	41
3.22	Crack opening displacement NE1 and NE3	41
3.23	Crack opening displacement NE1 and NE4	42
3.24	Crack opening displacement	42
3.25	Crack mesh (DOF=380,928)	43
3.26	Crack opening displacement (DOF=380,928)	44
3.27	Piecewise linear shape function N^J and global node x^J	50
3.28	Global boundary element belongs to a cell or not	50
3.29	Mesh and crack opening displacement	54
3.30	Crack opening displacement vs distance from the centre of the crack	55
3.31	Stress σ_{33} vs distance from the crack tip	55

3.32	CPU time (sec) vs number of unknowns	56
3.33	CPU time (sec) per iteration vs number of unknowns	56
3.34	Mesh for 512 cracks (DOF=241,152)	57
3.35	Crack opening displacements of 512 cracks (DOF=241,152)	58
3.36	Surface Π	59
3.37	J_2 on surface Π	59
3.38	Crack opening displacements of 512 cracks with random radii (DOF=241,152).	60
3.39	kR vs P	64
3.40	Scattering problem	65
3.41	Total CPU time (sec) ($ka_0 = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$)	67
3.42	CPU time per iteration (sec) ($ka_0 = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$)	67
3.43	Crack opening displacement $ \phi /u_0$ ($ka_0 = 1$)	68
3.44	Displacement $ u /u_0$ at both sides ($ka_0 = 1$)	68
3.45	Crack opening displacement $ \phi /u_0$ ($ka_0 = 2$)	69
3.46	Displacement $ u /u_0$ at both sides ($ka_0 = 2$)	69
3.47	Crack opening displacement $ \phi /u_0$ ($ka_0 = 3$)	70
3.48	Displacement $ u /u_0$ at both sides ($ka_0 = 3$)	70
3.49	Comparison of computational times for Laplace's equation and Helmholtz's equation ($ka_0=1$)	71
3.50	Real part of crack opening displacement (DOF=32,256, $ka_0 = 1$)	71
3.51	Imaginary part of crack opening displacement (DOF=32,256, $ka_0 = 1$)	72
3.52	Total CPU time (sec) ($k_T a_0 = 1.4$)	78
3.53	Crack opening displacement ($k_T a_0 = 1.4$)	78
3.54	Total CPU time (sec) ($k_T a_0 = 3.2$)	79
3.55	Crack opening displacement ($k_T a_0 = 3.2$)	79
3.56	Total CPU time (sec) ($k_T a_0 = 4.4$)	80
3.57	Crack opening displacement ($k_T a_0 = 4.4$)	80
3.58	Numerical result and analytical solution ($k_T a_0 = 3.2$)	81
3.59	Comparison of computational times for elastostatics and elastodynamics ($k_T a_0 = 1.4$)	81
4.1	Computational cost for M2L and M2X+X2X+X2L	84
4.2	Uplist of source cell	86
4.3	Crack mesh (DOF=1912)	90
4.4	Crack opening displacement	91
4.5	CPU time (sec)	91
4.6	Crack mesh (DOF=241,664)	92
4.7	Crack opening displacement (DOF=241,664)	93
4.8	Crack opening displacement	99
4.9	CPU time (sec)	100
4.10	CPU time (sec)	100
4.11	Crack opening displacement (DOF=1,285,632)	101
B.1	Exchange of indices	108
J.1	Exchange of indices	125

Acknowledgements

The author would like to express his gratitude to Prof. Naoshi Nishimura and Prof. Shoichi Kobayashi for their helpful advice and enthusiastic directions.

The author would like to thank Prof. Masaru Matsumoto and Prof. Takeshi Tamura for their reviews and criticisms.

The author also acknowledge doctoral students, Mr. Takahashi and Mr. Yoshikawa for useful discussions and suggestions, Mr. Miyakoshi and Mr. Iritani for their contributions in numerical work and other colleagues in Geosphere Engineering Laboratory for their support.

Finally, the author would like to express his gratitude to his parents for their unconditional support.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Background

In contrast with domain methods such as Finite Element Method (FEM) or Finite Difference Method (FDM), Boundary Integral Equation Method (BIEM), also called Boundary Element Method (BEM), discretises only the boundary of the domain. Because of this reduction of the dimensionality BIEM was expected to be advantageous in large-scale problems. However, the application of this method has so far been limited to relatively small problems. This was because coefficient matrices in BIEM are full, due to which both the operation count and the memory requirements for the matrix equation buildup are of the order of $O(N^2)$, where N is the number of unknowns. The operation count even increases to $O(N^3)$ as one attempts to solve the matrix equations with conventional direct solvers such as Crout's method and Gaussian elimination. In particular, the full matrix property leads to a serious exhaustion of the memory of a computer and is an obstacle for applications of BIEM to large-scale problems. On the other hand, coefficient matrices in domain methods are banded and both computational complexity for matrix buildup and memory requirements are $O(N)$. This is why applications of domain methods to large-scale problems are relatively easy. However, the appearance of Fast Multipole Method (FMM), also referred to as Fast Multipole Algorithm (FMA), drastically changed the circumstances around BIEM. The use of FMM in conjunction with iterative solvers such as Conjugate Gradient (CG) method and Generalised Minimal RESidual (GMRES) method has been shown to reduce the memory requirements to $O(N)$ and the operation count to $O(N(\log N)^\alpha)$, where α is a small non-negative number. Thus FMM enables us to apply BIEM to large-scale problems. Thanks to FMM, BIEM is no longer what it was.

FMM was initially introduced by Rokhlin [69] as a fast solution method for integral equations for two-dimensional Laplace's equation and then developed by Greengard [33, 35] as a fast evaluation method for the pairwise force calculation in multibody problems with Coulombic potential. FMM has been applied to problems in various fields such as BIEM and Molecular Dynamics (MD).

The author has been studying this topic in order to apply Fast Multipole Boundary Integral Equation Method (FM-BIEM) to practical problems in fracture mechanics and earthquake engineering. In this thesis the author discusses applications of FM-BIEM to various fundamental boundary value problems in three dimensions and show its efficiencies so as to make the first step toward practical applications.

1.2 Organization of thesis

The organization of this thesis goes as follows:

- Chapter 2

In chapter 2 we briefly describe the history of FMM and other fast solution methods such as tree method, panel clustering method and wavelet-based method. Also, we explain the framework of FM-BIEM and the algorithm and computational cost of FMM.

- Chapter 3

In chapter 3 we apply the original FM-BIEM to three-dimensional problems. In particular, we deal with hypersingular integral equations for crack problems. Crack has the singularity at the tip and this property sometimes leads to failures of structures. This is why crack is worthy to be considered in engineering. Furthermore, techniques for the hypersingular integral equation can

be easily extended to the single-layer and double-layer potentials. In this chapter we consider the following cases:

- Laplace’s equation: Laplace’s equation is a very important and basic PDE. Laplace’s equation can be interpreted as the stationary heat equation, the electrostatic equation, etc. We apply FM-BIEM to crack problems for Laplace’s equation. For example a crack may mean a thin insulation in the stationary heat equation or in the electrostatic equation.
- Elastostatics: Crack is an interesting object because its behaviours have much influence on the stress field. We apply FMM to BIE analyses of crack problems for three-dimensional elastostatics with collocation method and Galerkin’s method.
- Helmholtz’s equation (wave equation in the frequency domain): Because BIEM is particularly suitable for wave analyses, BIEM is often used for numerical analyses of elastodynamic problems in non-destructive evaluation, earthquake engineering or computational seismology. Bearing applications of FM-BIEM to elastodynamics in mind, we apply FM-BIEM to three-dimensional scattering of scalar waves by cracks since techniques developed for Helmholtz’s equation can be easily extended to elastodynamics.
- Elastodynamics in the frequency domain: Using techniques proposed for Helmholtz’s equation, we apply FM-BIEM to three-dimensional scattering of elastic waves by a crack.

- Chapter 4

In FMM the computational cost for the M2L translation (details of the M2L translation will be given later) dominates the performance especially in three-dimensional problems or problems dealing with Helmholtz’s equation. In order to reduce the computational cost for the M2L translation Greengard and Rokhlin [36] proposed some techniques based on an integral representation for a fundamental solution. In this thesis we call FMM and FM-BIEM connected with these techniques “new FMM” and “new FM-BIEM”, respectively. In chapter 4 we apply new FMM to BIE analyses of crack problems for three-dimensional Laplace’s equation and three-dimensional elastostatics and compare results obtained with new FM-BIEM with those obtained in chapter 3.

- Chapter 5

In chapter 5 we state conclusions.

- Appnedix

In appendix we give derivations of some formulae and equations in this thesis.

Chapter 2

Overview of Fast Multipole Method (FMM)

In this chapter we briefly describe the history, framework and algorithms of FMM.

2.1 Brief history of FMM and other fast solution methods

Fast Multipole Method

FMM was initially introduced by Rokhlin [69] as a fast solution method for integral equations for two-dimensional Laplace's equation. In Rokhlin's paper [69] the term "FMM" did not appear but the main framework of FMM was constructed. After Rokhlin's work, Greengard [33,35] refined the algorithm, applied FMM to two and three-dimensional N-body problems with Coulombic potential and showed the applicability of FMM to various fields.

Rokhlin uses FMM in conjunction with an iterative solver to reduce the computational complexity for the matrix-vector multiplication from $O(N^2)$ to $O(N)$. In FMM Rokhlin uses multipole moments to represent distant particle groups (particle means collocation point of a boundary element in BIEM) and introduces a local expansion to evaluate the contribution from distant particles in the form of a series. The multipole moment associated with a distant group can be translated into the coefficient of the local expansion associated with a local group. In addition to Rokhlin's work, Greengard introduces the hierarchical decomposition of a spatial domain with a quad-tree in two dimensions and an oct-tree in three dimensions to carry out efficient and systematic grouping of particles with tree structures. Greengard uses FMM to reduce the computational cost for the pairwise force calculation from $O(N^2)$ to $O(N)$ (See Fig.2.1–2.3). In the last decades FMM has been applied to various fields such as BIEM, molecular dynamics (MD) (e.g. [8,14,15,48,81]). The fact that FMM was nominated as one of the top 10 algorithms of the century along with Fast Fourier Transform (FFT), QR algorithm, etc. in [7] shows how much influence it had on numerical analyses.

Applications of FMM to BIEM are investigated by many authors: by Fukui and Hattori [23] and Miyakoshi et al. [60] to two-dimensional Laplace's equation, by Fukui and Mochida [28] and Helsing [42] to two-dimensional elastostatics, by Nishimura et al. [65] and Nishida and Hayami [62] to three-dimensional Laplace's equation, by Yoshida et al. [84,87], Takahashi et al. [78], Fukui and Kutsumi [27] and Fu et al. [18,19] to three-dimensional elastostatics, by Chew et al. [10], Fujiwara [21] and Iritani et al. [47] to two-dimensional elastodynamics, by Fujiwara [22] and Yoshida et al. [86] to three-dimensional elastodynamics, and by Gómez and Power [30,31], Mammoli and Ingber [57,58], Fu and Rodin [20] and Takahashi et al. [79] to fluid mechanics. BIEM are particularly suitable for wave analyses in the infinite domain. Because of this advantage, applications of FM-BIEM to large-scale wave problems, particularly to acoustical and electromagnetic scattering problems, are vigorously investigated by many researchers: by Rokhlin [70], Lu and Chew [54,55], Song and Chew [77], Fukui and Katsumoto [25] and Yoshida et al. [85].

Recently several techniques to enhance the efficiencies of FMM are proposed by several authors. Rokhlin [70–72] proposed such a technique called the "diagonal form". We shall call this technique "Rokhlin's diagonal form". Epton and Dembart [17] and Elliot and Board [16] also proposed similar techniques. However, Rokhlin's diagonal form is known to have numerical instabilities in dealing with static problems and low frequency problems. Hence, Greengard et al. [11,34,36] and Hrycak and Rokhlin [44] proposed techniques based on the integral representation of a fundamental solution. In this thesis

we call their techniques the “new FMM”. The new FMM resolves problems of Rokhlin’s diagonal form. Besides above techniques, several other techniques to improve the efficiency are proposed by White and Head-Gordon [82], Hu et al. [45], etc.

Applications of these techniques to FM-BIEM are found in several papers mentioned above, Koc and Chew [50], Hu et al. [46], Gyure and Stalzer [37], Dembart and Yip [13], Fukui and Katsumoto [26], Nishimura et al. [64] and Yoshida et al. [88, 89]

Figure 2.1: Conventional evaluation of contribution from distant particles: $O(N^2)$ algorithm

Figure 2.2: Multipole moment represents distant particles

Figure 2.3: Evaluation with the multipole moment and the local expansion: $O(N)$ algorithm

Tree Method

Although Rokhlin and Greengard have developed FMM, they were not the only researchers to make efforts to reduce the computational cost for BIEM and N-body problems. Tree method was investigated by Appel [3] and Barnes and Hut [4] in astrophysics. Appel represents Coulombic potentials due to

Figure 2.4: Particles and the corresponding binary tree

distant particles with monopoles (if one needs more accurate result one may use quadruples, octuples.... in addition to monopoles), by taking a mass centre of two particles as their representative point (pseudoparticle) and continuing these hierarchical representations of particles recursively to build up a binary tree structure (See Fig.2.4). A pseudoparticle represents contributions from all descendants. Barnes and Hut refined Appel’s work using a quad-tree in two dimensions and an oct-tree in three dimensions.

Tree method and FMM are the same in that both methods use multipole moments. FMM can reduce the computational cost for the pairwise force calculation from $O(N^2)$ to $O(N)$, whereas tree method to $O(N \log N)$ where N is the number of particles. This difference comes from the fact that FMM achieves further reduction by introducing the local expansion. Tree method can also be applied to BIEM. Indeed, Fukui and Katsumoto [25] applied FMM and Barnes and Hut algorithm to BIEM for two-dimensional Helmholtz’s equation. Though FMM is superior to tree method in the estimated computational cost as $N \rightarrow \infty$, tree method seems to be more popular in astrophysics because of its simple implementation. Indeed, overheads caused by introducing the local expansion are not negligible occasionally.

Panel clustering method

Panel clustering method proposed by Hackbusch and Nowak [38] gives an algorithm of the order of $O(N \log^{d+2} N)$ with the help of an expansion of a kernel function and decompositions of the spatial domain with “panels” where d is a dimension of a problem. As one views the algorithm of panel clustering method one will see that panel clustering method is similar to FMM or the tree method. The use of panel clustering method has been investigated by several authors: by Hayami and Sauter [39–41] and Sauter [73].

Wavelet-based method

Wavelet-based methods were introduced by Beylkin [5] for the compression of matrices. In wavelet-based method the magnitude of components of a matrix can be dramatically compressed with the use of wavelet basis for discretisation of boundary integral equations and the dense matrix property could be avoided by replacing small-valued components with zero to such degree that the necessary precision is kept. Applications of wavelet-based methods to BIEM are found in [1, 52, 67, 68, 90].

2.2 Basic framework of FM-BIEM

2.2.1 Basic role of FMM in FM-BIEM

In BIEM an integral equation is given by

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = \int_S K(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \varphi(\mathbf{y}) dS \quad \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \in S, \quad (2.1)$$

where φ is an unknown function on S , f is a given function on S and K is a given kernel function on $S \times S$. When one solves the integral equation numerically one discretises it into the form of a matrix-vector product. In FM-BIEM an iterative method is used as a solver for linear equations. Namely FMM is utilised to reduce the computational complexity for the multiplication of a matrix and a candidate vector in BIEM. Indeed, FMM can reduce this complexity from $O(N^2)$ to $O(N)$. In FM-BIEM the integral in (2.1) is evaluated with direct computation in the same manner as in the conventional BIEM only when \mathbf{x} is in the neighbourhood of \mathbf{y} because of a singularity at $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{y}$ of a kernel function. Otherwise, the integral is evaluated efficiently with FMM.

2.2.2 Formulation for FM-BIEM

In this section we describe procedures of FM-BIEM.

Expansion of a kernel function

In FM-BIEM the first step is to expand the kernel function into a series of products of functions of \mathbf{x} and those of \mathbf{y} as follows:

$$K(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \sum_i \phi_i(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})\psi_i(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}), \quad (2.2)$$

where ψ_i is regular near the origin O , ϕ_i is regular at infinity and O is a certain point such that the inequality $|\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}| < |\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}|$ is valid (See Fig.2.5).

Figure 2.5: Configuration of points and regions

Multipole moment

Let S_y , a subset of S , be a union of boundary elements $S_L (L = 1 \dots N)$ and \mathbf{x} be sufficiently far from S_y that the inequality $|\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}| > |\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}|$ ($\mathbf{y} \in S_y$) is valid (See Fig.2.5).

Using (2.2), one can evaluate the integral in (2.1) on S_y as follows:

$$\int_{S_y} K(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})\varphi(\mathbf{y})dS = \sum_i \phi_i(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})M_i(O), \quad (2.3)$$

where $M_i(O)$ is a multipole moment centred at O defined as

$$M_i(O) = \sum_{L=1}^N \int_{S_L} \psi_i(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) \varphi(\mathbf{y}) dS. \quad (2.4)$$

M2M translation

Suppose that one can expand the function ψ_i as follows:

$$\psi_j(\overrightarrow{O'\mathbf{x}}) = \sum_i \psi_i(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) \alpha_i^j(\overrightarrow{OO'}), \quad (2.5)$$

where α_i^j is the coefficient of the expansion.

The multipole moment centred at O' is given by

$$M_j(O') = \sum_{L=1}^N \int_{S_L} \psi_j(\overrightarrow{O'\mathbf{y}}) \varphi(\mathbf{y}) dS. \quad (2.6)$$

Substituting (2.5) into (2.6) one obtains the following formula:

$$M_j(O') = \sum_i M_i(O) \alpha_i^j(\overrightarrow{OO'}). \quad (2.7)$$

This formula (2.7) is used to translate the multipole moment as the centre of the multipole expansion is shifted from O to O' (See Fig.2.5) and this translation is called ‘‘M2M (Multipole moment to(2) Multipole moment) translation’’. Notice that one can evaluate the integral in (2.1) with the translated multipole moments as follows:

$$\int_{S_y} K(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \varphi(\mathbf{y}) dS = \sum_i \phi_i(\overrightarrow{O'\mathbf{x}}) M_i(O').$$

Local expansion

We can efficiently evaluate the integral in (2.1) using the multipole moments alone. However, in order to enhance this efficiency we use the local expansion in FMM.

Suppose that one can expand ϕ_i as follows:

$$\phi_i(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) = \sum_l \xi_l(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) \beta_l^i(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0}), \quad (2.8)$$

where ξ_l is a function, β_l^i is a certain coefficient of the expansion and \mathbf{x}_0 is a certain point such that the inequality $|\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}| < |\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0}|$ is valid (See Fig.2.5).

Substituting (2.8) into (2.3), one can evaluate the integral in (2.1) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{S_y} K(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \varphi(\mathbf{y}) dS &= \sum_i \phi_i(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) M_i(O) \\ &= \sum_i \sum_l \xi_l(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) \beta_l^i(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0}) M_i(O) \\ &= \sum_l \xi_l(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) \sum_i \beta_l^i(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0}) M_i(O) \\ &= \sum_l \xi_l(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) L_l(\mathbf{x}_0), \end{aligned} \quad (2.9)$$

where $L_l(\mathbf{x}_0)$ is the coefficient of the local expansion centred at \mathbf{x}_0 given by

$$L_l(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_i \beta_l^i(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0}) M_i(O). \quad (2.10)$$

This formula (2.10) is used to translate the multipole moments centred at O to the coefficients of the local expansion centred at \mathbf{x}_0 (See Fig.2.5) and this translation is called ‘‘M2L (Multipole moment to(2) Local expansion) translation’’.

L2L translation

Suppose that one can expand the function ξ_j as follows:

$$\xi_j(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) = \sum_i \xi_i(\overline{\mathbf{x}_1\mathbf{x}}) \chi_i^j(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}_1}), \quad (2.11)$$

where χ_i^j is a certain coefficient of the expansion.

Substituting (2.11) into (2.9), one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{S_y} K(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \varphi(\mathbf{y}) dS &= \sum_l \xi_l(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) L_l(\mathbf{x}_0) \\ &= \sum_l \sum_i \xi_i(\overline{\mathbf{x}_1\mathbf{x}}) \chi_i^l(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}_1}) L_l(\mathbf{x}_0) \\ &= \sum_i \xi_i(\overline{\mathbf{x}_1\mathbf{x}}) \sum_l \chi_i^l(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}_1}) L_l(\mathbf{x}_0) \\ &= \sum_i \xi_i(\overline{\mathbf{x}_1\mathbf{x}}) L_i(\mathbf{x}_1). \end{aligned}$$

Thus the following formula is obtained

$$L_i(\mathbf{x}_1) = \sum_l L_l(\mathbf{x}_0) \chi_i^l(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}_1}). \quad (2.12)$$

The formula (2.12) is used to translate the coefficients of the local expansion as the centre of the local expansion is shifted from \mathbf{x}_0 to \mathbf{x}_1 (See Fig.2.5) and this translation is called “L2L (Local expansion to(2) Local expansion) translation”.

2.2.3 Fast multipole algorithm and estimation of its computational cost

In this section we describe the fast multipole algorithm in two dimensions for simplicity. The algorithm in three dimensions is obtained by replacing a quad-tree with an oct-tree.

Fast multipole algorithm

Step 1. Discretisation:

Discretise S in the same manner as in the conventional BIEM using boundary elements.

Step 2. Construction of quad-tree structure:

Consider a square which circumscribes S and call this square the cell of level 0. Now take a cell (a parent cell) of level l ($l \geq 0$) and divide it into 4 equal sub squares whose edge length is half of that of the parent cell and call any of them a cell (a child cell) of level $l + 1$ if some boundary elements belong to this square (See Fig.2.6). In this statement a boundary element is said to belong to a cell C if the centroid of the element is in C (See Fig.2.7). Stop the cell subdivision if the number of boundary elements belonging to the cell is smaller than a given number. A childless cell is called a leaf.

Step 3. Computation of the multipole moments (Upward):

First we compute the multipole moments associated with leaves using (2.4). Here the multipole moments associated with a cell C stand for the integrals in (2.4) with O taken as the centroid of C . For a non-leaf cell C of level l , we compute the multipole moments associated with C by adding all the multipole moments of C 's children after shifting the origin from the centroids of C 's children to that of C via (2.7) (See Fig.2.8). This procedure is repeated for $l \geq 2$ tracing the tree structure of cells upward (decreasing l).

Step 4. Computation of the coefficients of the local expansion (Downward):

We have to prepare some definitions first. We say that two cells are “adjacent cells at level l ” if these cells are both of the level l and share at least one vertex. Two cells are said to be “well-separated at level l ” if they are not adjacent at level l but their parent cells are adjacent at level $l - 1$. The list of all the well-separated cells from a level l cell C is called the interaction list of C . The maximum number of well-separated cells is $6^2 - 3^2 = 27$ (See Fig.2.9).

Now we compute the local expansion associated with a cell C . The local expansion associated with C represents a sum of the contributions due to boundary elements in cells of the interaction list of C and the contributions due to all boundary elements in cells which are not adjacent to C 's parent. The former is computed as we substitute the multipole moments associated with cells in the interaction list of C into (2.10) and the latter by translating the local expansion associated with C 's parent via (2.12) as the centre of the local expansion is shifted from the centroid of C 's parent (\mathbf{x}_0) to the centroid of C (\mathbf{x}_1) (See Fig.2.8). The sum of these contributions gives the local expansion associated with C . We repeat these procedures starting from $l = 2$ and increasing l along the tree structure until we reach leaves. When $l = 2$, the coefficients of the local expansion are computed only by using (2.10). This is because cells of level 1 have no well-separated cells.

Step 5. Evaluation of the integral in (2.1):

We now compute the right-hand side of (2.1). Let C be a cell of the level l to which the collocation point \mathbf{x} belongs, and let C' be a cell of level l adjacent to C . We compute the contribution from boundary elements in C' to the integral in (2.1) at collocation points in C directly if either C or C' is a leaf. When C is a leaf, we also compute the right-hand side of (2.9) using the coefficients of the local expansion associated with C . The sum of all these terms as l increases from 2 gives the integral in (2.1) evaluated at the collocation points of all boundary elements.

Step. 6

Update the candidate vector and go back to **Step. 3**.

Figs. 2.10–2.14 present examples to give definite pictures of FMM. Figs. 2.10–2.14 show procedures for the evaluation of contributions from all boundary elements to a certain observation point. Figs. 2.10–2.14 correspond to Steps 1–5, respectively, in the algorithm described above.

Figure 2.6: Construction of a tree structure and corresponding quad-tree

Figure 2.7: Boundary element is in a cell or not

Figure 2.8: M2M translation and L2L translation

Figure 2.9: Adjacent cells and well-separated cells

Figure 2.10: Discretisation (Step 1)

Figure 2.11: Construction of tree structure (Step 2)

Figure 2.12: Multipole moments and M2M translation (Step 3)

Figure 2.13: M2L and L2L translation (Step 4)

Figure 2.14: Evaluation of total contribution (Step 5)

Estimation of the computational cost

We estimate the computational cost for Steps 3–6 since in FM-BIEM Steps 3–6 are iterated. Although we consider the two-dimensional case, we can similarly estimate the computational cost in three dimensions. The complexity for Step 6 is negligible because Steps 3–5 dominate the performance. For simplicity we carry out the estimation under the following conditions:

- Boundary elements are distributed uniformly.
- The number of unknowns is N .
- The number of boundary elements in a leaf is less than a fixed number M .
- The summation in the infinite series (2.3), (2.9), etc. is truncated at p terms.

From above conditions, the number of leaves is N/M , the depth of the quad-tree l_f is $\log_4(N/M)$ and the total number of cells is $1 + 4 + 4^2 + \dots + 4^{\log_4(N/M)} = (4/3)(N/M - 1) \approx 4N/(3M)$. Notice that all leaves are assumed to be cells at level l_f in this estimation.

- Cost of Step 3:

In step 3 we compute multipole moments at leaves and translate multipole moments.

- Computation of multipole moments

The number of leaves is N/M , the number of boundary elements is M in a leaf and the number of the multipole moments to be computed in a leaf is p . Therefore the cost for computation of multipole moments is $O(pN)$.

- Translation of multipole moments

The number of M2M translations via (2.7) at level ℓ is 4^ℓ and the cost per translation is $O(p^2)$. We iterate these translations from $\ell = l_f$ to $\ell = 3$. Therefore the cost for M2M translations is $O(\sum_{\ell=3}^{l_f} 4^\ell p^2) \approx O(4p^2 N/3M)$.

- Cost of Step 4:

In step 4 we compute coefficients of the local expansion and translate them.

- Computation of coefficients of the local expansion

The number of M2L translations via (2.10) at level ℓ is $27 \times 4^\ell$ and the cost per translation is $O(p^2)$. We iterate these translations from $\ell = 2$ to $\ell = l_f$. Therefore the cost for M2L translations is $O(\sum_{\ell=2}^{l_f} 27 \times 4^\ell p^2) \approx O(36p^2 N/M)$.

- Translation of coefficients of the local expansion

The number of L2L translations via (2.12) at level ℓ is 4^ℓ and the cost per translation is $O(p^2)$. We iterate these translations from $\ell = 3$ to $\ell = l_f$. Therefore the cost for L2L translations is $O(\sum_{\ell=3}^{l_f} 4^\ell p^2) \approx O(4p^2 N/3M)$.

- Cost of Step 5:

In step 5 we evaluate the contribution from adjacent cells at all the leaves with direct computation and the contribution from cells which are not adjacent with the local expansion at all the leaves.

- Evaluation with direct computation

The number of leaves is N/M and the cost for the direct computation per leaf is $O(9M^2)$. Therefore the cost is $O(9MN)$.

- Evaluation with the local expansion

The number of leaves is N/M and the number of boundary elements is M in a leaf. Also, we truncate the infinite series (2.9) taking p terms. Therefore the cost is $O(pN)$.

Hence the total computational complexity per iteration is

$$O(pN) + O(4p^2 N/3M) + O(36p^2 N/M) + O(4p^2 N/3M) + O(9MN) + O(pN) \approx O(N)$$

From above estimation one can see that the computational cost for M2L translation is expensive. Therefore, M2L translation is the bottleneck in FMM. To make matters worse, the cost for M2L translation is $O(216p^4 N/M)$ in three dimensions, making the cost for M2L translation a more serious problem than in two dimensions.

Chapter 3

Applications of FMM to three-dimensional crack problems

In this chapter we describe applications of FM-BIEM to various three-dimensional crack problems in sections 3.2–3.6 and state concluding remarks in section 3.7 after a brief derivation of the hypersingular integral equation for elastostatic crack problems and a summary of the notations in section 3.1.

3.1 Crack

It is well-known that cracks are important in engineering because they sometimes lead to failures of structures. Indeed, “fracture mechanics” is synonymous with the mechanics of cracks. To investigate phenomena related to fractures precisely three-dimensional analyses of crack problems are indispensable. However, three-dimensional analyses will inevitably become large-scale. Hence, we attempt to apply FM-BIEM to large-scale crack problems. In this section we formulate crack problems and derive the corresponding integral equations, taking the elastostatics case as an example.

3.1.1 Notation

Before we apply FM-BIEM to crack problems we summarise the notations about a crack. In this thesis we denote a crack by $S(\subset R^3)$ and assume that S is a union of smooth non-self-intersecting curved surfaces having edges ∂S and a unit normal vector \mathbf{n} (See Fig.3.1).

Figure 3.1: Notations about a crack

Also, we denote $S + \partial S$ by \bar{S} and the superscript $+$ ($-$) indicates the limit on S from the positive (negative) side of S where the positive side indicates the one into which the unit normal \mathbf{n} points. In this thesis we denote the discontinuity of u across S by $\phi(= u^+ - u^-)$ and call ϕ the crack opening displacement though ϕ may not necessarily be a physical displacement. In crack problems we impose the regularity condition $\phi = 0$ on ∂S . This condition guarantees the uniqueness of the solution. The above notations are used throughout this thesis unless stated otherwise.

3.1.2 Integral equation for crack problems in three-dimensional elastostatics

In this section we describe the derivation of the integral equation for elastostatic crack problems in the infinite domain.

We consider a domain D in the infinite space R^3 and assume that D is bounded by two surfaces S_1 and S_2 (See Fig.3.2). We first consider an elastic state (u_i, σ_{ij}) , where u_i is a displacement vector and σ_{ij} is a stress tensor associated with u_i . σ_{ij} satisfies the equilibrium equation given by

$$\sigma_{ij,i}(\mathbf{y}) = 0. \quad (3.1)$$

We also consider another elastic state $(\Gamma_{ki}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}), \Sigma_{kij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}))$, where $\Gamma_{ki}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})$ is a displacement vector at \mathbf{y} in the direction i when a unit concentrated load is applied at \mathbf{x} in the direction k and is called the fundamental solution of elastostatics. $\Sigma_{kij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})$ is the stress tensor associated with $\Gamma_{ki}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})$, which is given by

$$\Sigma_{kij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) = C_{ijnm} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_m} \Gamma_{kn}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})$$

and satisfies the equilibrium equation given by

$$\Sigma_{kij,i}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) = -\delta_{kj} \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}), \quad (3.2)$$

in D .

Now we introduce Betti's reciprocal identity

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{S_1+S_2} \sigma_{ij}(\mathbf{y}) n_i(\mathbf{y}) \Gamma_{kj}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) dS - \int_{S_1+S_2} \Sigma_{kij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) n_i(\mathbf{y}) u_j(\mathbf{y}) dS \quad (\mathbf{y} \in S_1 + S_2) \\ & = \int_D \{ \sigma_{ij,i}(\mathbf{y}) \Gamma_{kj}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) - \Sigma_{kij,i}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) u_j(\mathbf{y}) \} dV, \quad (\mathbf{y} \in D). \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

The first term and the second term in the left-hand side of (3.3) are called the single-layer potential and the double-layer potential, respectively. Also, Γ_{kj} and $\Sigma_{kij} n_i$ are called the single-layer kernel (or the fundamental solution) and the double-layer kernel, respectively.

Figure 3.2: Domain D and surfaces S_1 and S_2

Substituting (3.1) and (3.2) into (3.3), we obtain the Somigliana formula

$$\int_{S_1+S_2} \{ \sigma_{ij}(\mathbf{y}) n_i(\mathbf{y}) \Gamma_{kj}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) - \Sigma_{kij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) n_i(\mathbf{y}) u_j(\mathbf{y}) \} dS = \begin{cases} u_k(\mathbf{x}), & (\mathbf{x} \in D) \\ 0, & (\mathbf{x} \notin D) \end{cases}. \quad (3.4)$$

Now we consider the case where \mathbf{x} is in D and assume that the boundary S_1 is the surface of a crack with $S_1 = S^+ \cup S^-$ and $S^+ \cap S^- = \emptyset$ (See Fig.3.3). In numerical examples in this thesis we assume that a surface of a crack is free from traction and, hence, tractions on S^+ and S^- are set to be zero. Taking the above conditions into consideration, we rewrite (3.4) as

$$\begin{aligned} u_k(\mathbf{x}) &= \int_{S_2} \{ \sigma_{ij}(\mathbf{y}) n_i(\mathbf{y}) \Gamma_{kj}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) - \Sigma_{kij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) n_i(\mathbf{y}) u_j(\mathbf{y}) \} dS \\ & - \int_{S^+} \Sigma_{kij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) n_i^+(\mathbf{y}) u_j^+(\mathbf{y}) dS - \int_{S^-} \Sigma_{kij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) n_i^-(\mathbf{y}) u_j^-(\mathbf{y}) dS, \quad \mathbf{x} \in D, \end{aligned} \quad (3.5)$$

where $\mathbf{u}^+(\mathbf{u}^-)$ and $\mathbf{n}^+(\mathbf{n}^-)$ are the displacement vector and the unit normal vector on $S^+(S^-)$. We set $S^+ = S^- = S$ and $\mathbf{n}^- = -\mathbf{n}^+ = \mathbf{n}$ in (3.5), because the crack is considered to be a slit whose thickness is zero, to obtain the following integral representation for \mathbf{u} in the finite domain which contains a crack:

$$u_k(\mathbf{x}) = \int_{S_2} \{ \sigma_{ij}(\mathbf{y})n_i(\mathbf{y})\Gamma_{kj}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) - \Sigma_{kij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})n_i(\mathbf{y})u_j(\mathbf{y}) \} dS + \int_S \Sigma_{kij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})n_i(\mathbf{y})\phi_j(\mathbf{y})dS, \quad \mathbf{x} \in D, \quad (3.6)$$

where ϕ is the crack opening displacement vector defined by

$$\phi(\mathbf{y}) := \mathbf{u}^+(\mathbf{y}) - \mathbf{u}^-(\mathbf{y}).$$

Figure 3.3: Domain D and surfaces S_2 , S^+ and S^-

Next, letting S_2 tend to infinity in (3.6), we have the following integral representation

$$u_k(\mathbf{x}) = u_k^\infty(\mathbf{x}) + \int_S \Sigma_{kij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})n_i(\mathbf{y})\phi_j(\mathbf{y})dS, \quad \mathbf{x} \in D, \quad (3.7)$$

where \mathbf{u}^∞ is a solution of the equation of elastostatics in the whole space. Physically, we can interpret \mathbf{u}^∞ as the “no crack solution”. Applying the traction operator $T_{ik}(\mathbf{x})$ defined as

$$T_{ik}(\mathbf{x}) := C_{ijkl}n_j(\mathbf{x})\frac{\partial}{\partial x_l},$$

on both sides of (3.7), we obtain

$$t_i(\mathbf{x}) = t_i^\infty(\mathbf{x}) + \int_S T_{ik}(\mathbf{x})\Sigma_{klj}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})n_l(\mathbf{y})\phi_j(\mathbf{y})dS, \quad \mathbf{x} \in D, \quad (3.8)$$

where t_i and t_i^∞ are traction vectors associated with u_i and u_i^∞ , respectively. Finally, letting \mathbf{x} approach S in (3.8) and noting that S is free from traction, we have the following hypersingular integral equation

$$-t_i^\infty(\mathbf{x}) = \oint_S T_{ik}(\mathbf{x})\Sigma_{klj}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})n_l(\mathbf{y})\phi_j(\mathbf{y})dS, \quad \mathbf{x} \in S, \quad (3.9)$$

where \oint stands for the finite part of a divergent integral. Hypersingular integral equations of this type are the basic equations for crack problems considered in this thesis.

3.1.3 A note on integral equations

We restrict the discussion to the case of elastostatics. In elastostatics we mainly deal with (3.9) and efficiently compute ϕ in (3.9) with FMM. FMM gives us the method for efficient evaluation of integrals which contain products of kernel functions such as single- and double-layer kernels and density functions (e.g. displacement, traction). Now, we consider two integral representations (3.4) and (3.7) for example.

Letting \mathbf{x} approach S in (3.4), one can deal with ordinary boundary value problems. Also, one can compute displacement fields with (3.7) if ϕ is given. Moreover, applying the operator $P_{ijk}(\mathbf{x})$ defined as

$$P_{ijk}(\mathbf{x}) := C_{ijkl} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l},$$

on both sides of (3.7), one obtains the integral representation for σ given by

$$\sigma_{ij}(\mathbf{x}) = \sigma_{ij}^\infty(\mathbf{x}) + \int_S P_{ijk}(\mathbf{x}) \Sigma_{lj}^k(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) n_l(\mathbf{y}) \phi_j(\mathbf{y}) dS, \quad \mathbf{x} \in D, \quad (3.10)$$

Suppose that ϕ is given, one can compute stress fields with (3.10). One can see that the integrals in (3.4), (3.7) and (3.10) contain the product of the single-layer kernel (or the double-layer kernel) and the density function. Namely, if once one implements FM-BIEM for crack problems, one can simultaneously deal with ordinary boundary value problems, displacement fields and stress fields with FM-BIEM. In view of this the analysis of crack problems with FMM is considered to be more versatile than it appears, since techniques proposed in this thesis are not restricted to crack problems. Although we have restricted the discussion to elastostatics, the same is true in other governing equations. This is one of the reasons why we deal with crack problems in this thesis.

3.2 Crack problems for three-dimensional Laplace's equation

In this section we discuss an application of FM-BIEM to crack problems for three-dimensional Laplace's equation. Applications of FM-BIEM to ordinary problems in three-dimensional Laplace's equation are found in Nishida and Hayami [62] and Kaneko et al. [49]. In this section we present the FMM formulation with the hypersingular integral equation and the regularised integral equation. In order to discretise BIEs we use collocation method and piecewise constant shape functions.

The material in this section is from Nishimura et al. [65].

3.2.1 Integral Equation

Our problem is to find a solution u of Laplace's equation

$$\Delta u(\mathbf{x}) = 0 \quad \text{in } R^3 \setminus \overline{S}, \quad (3.11)$$

subject to the boundary condition

$$\frac{\partial u^\pm(\mathbf{x})}{\partial n} = 0 \quad \text{on } S, \quad (3.12)$$

regularity condition

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}) := u^+(\mathbf{x}) - u^-(\mathbf{x}) = 0 \quad \text{on } \partial S, \quad (3.13)$$

and an asymptotic condition

$$u(\mathbf{x}) \rightarrow u^\infty(\mathbf{x}) \quad \text{as } |\mathbf{x}| \rightarrow \infty,$$

where u^∞ and ϕ stand for a solution of Laplace's equation in the whole space and the crack opening displacement, respectively. Physically, the function u^∞ can be viewed as the "no crack solution" of the problem.

The solution u to this problem has an integral representation given by

$$u(\mathbf{x}) = u^\infty(\mathbf{x}) + \int_S \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial n_y} \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y, \quad \mathbf{x} \in R^3 \setminus \overline{S}, \quad (3.14)$$

where $G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})$ is the fundamental solution of Laplace's equation expressed as

$$G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) = \frac{1}{4\pi|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|}.$$

From the boundary condition (3.12) and (3.14), one obtains the following hypersingular integral equation given by

$$-\frac{\partial u^\infty(\mathbf{x})}{\partial n_x} = \int_S \frac{\partial^2 G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial n_x \partial n_y} \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y, \quad \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \in S, \quad (3.15)$$

where \oint stands for the finite part of a divergent integral. Also, using Stokes' theorem, one can regularise (3.15) as (See Appendix L.1)

$$-\frac{\partial u^\infty(\mathbf{x})}{\partial n_x} = -n_j(\mathbf{x})e_{jpl} \oint_S \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x}-\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_p} n_i(\mathbf{y})e_{iql} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y_q}(\mathbf{y})dS_y, \quad \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \in S. \quad (3.16)$$

where \int stands for the Cauchy principal value of a singular integral. We use (3.16) for a direct computation of (3.15) in the conventional BIEM as well as in FM-BIEM. In the following sections we describe two types of FM-BIEM; one is FM-BIEM with the hypersingular integral equation and the other is FM-BIEM with the regularised integral equation.

3.2.2 FM-BIEM with hypersingular integral equation

In this section we use the hypersingular integral equation (3.15) for the formulation. We first expand the fundamental solution $G(\mathbf{x}-\mathbf{y})$ into a series of products of functions of \mathbf{x} and those of \mathbf{y} . To this end we introduce the following well-known identity: (See Appendix A)

$$\frac{1}{|\mathbf{x}-\mathbf{y}|} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \overline{S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})} R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}), \quad |\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}| > |\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}|, \quad (3.17)$$

where $R_{n,m}$ and $S_{n,m}$ are the solid harmonics defined as

$$R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) = \frac{1}{(n+m)!} P_n^m(\cos \theta) e^{im\phi} r^n, \quad (3.18)$$

$$S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) = (n-m)! P_n^m(\cos \theta) e^{im\phi} \frac{1}{r^{n+1}}, \quad (3.19)$$

(r, θ, ϕ) are the polar coordinates of the point \mathbf{x} , P_n^m is the associated Legendre function and a superposed bar indicates the complex conjugate, respectively. The functions $R_{n,m}$ and $S_{n,m}$ satisfy the relations given by (See Appendix B)

$$S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{y\mathbf{x}}) = \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \overline{R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}})} S_{n+n',m+m'}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}), \quad |\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}| < |\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}|, \quad (3.20)$$

$$R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{y\mathbf{x}}) = \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{y\mathbf{O}}) R_{n-n',m-m'}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) \quad (3.21)$$

(This holds for arbitrary $\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}$ and $\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}$).

In FMM, Greengard uses the spherical harmonics making his formulation somewhat complicated. Therefore we use solid harmonics to make the formulae needed for FMM concise. The use of solid harmonics has been suggested by White and Head-Gordon [81] and Pérez-Jordá and Yang [66].

We now compute the integral on the right-hand side of (3.15) over a subset of S denoted by S_y for \mathbf{x} which is away from S_y . Using (3.17) we obtain

$$\int_{S_y} \frac{\partial^2 G(\mathbf{x}-\mathbf{y})}{\partial n_x \partial n_y} \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y = \frac{1}{4\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \frac{\partial \overline{S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})}}{\partial n_x} M_{n,m}(O), \quad (3.22)$$

where $M_{n,m}(O)$ is the multipole moment centred at O , defined by

$$M_{n,m}(O) = \int_{S_y} \frac{\partial R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}})}{\partial n_y} \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y. \quad (3.23)$$

In (3.22) we have assumed that the inequality $|\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}| > |\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}|$ ($\mathbf{y} \in S_y$) holds.

The multipole moment is transformed according to the following formula when the centre of the multipole moment is translated from O to O'

$$M_{n,m}(O') = \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{O'\mathbf{O}}) M_{n-n',m-m'}(O), \quad (3.24)$$

where we have used (3.21) and (3.23) (See Appendix E.1). The procedure given by (3.24) is called ‘‘M2M translation’’. Noting (A.5) and the fact that ϕ is real-valued, one finds that the multipole moment has the following property:

$$M_{n,-m}(O) = (-1)^m \overline{M_{n,m}(O)} \quad (m \geq 0). \quad (3.25)$$

The integral in (3.22) can be evaluated with the coefficient of the local expansion $L_{n,m}$ as follows:

$$\int_{S_y} \frac{\partial^2 G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial n_x \partial n_y} \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y = \frac{1}{4\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \frac{\partial R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}})}{\partial n_x} L_{n,m}(\mathbf{x}_0), \quad (3.26)$$

where $L_{n,m}(\mathbf{x}_0)$ is expressed in terms of $M_{n,m}(O)$ by

$$L_{n,m}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} (-1)^n \overline{S_{n+n',m+m'}(\overrightarrow{O \mathbf{x}_0})} M_{n',m'}(O). \quad (3.27)$$

In the derivation of this formula we have used (3.20) and have assumed that the inequality $|\overrightarrow{O \mathbf{x}_0}| > |\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}}|$ holds (See Appendix E.2). The procedure given by (3.27) is called ‘‘M2L translation’’. Also, the coefficient of the local expansion has the following property:

$$L_{n,-m}(\mathbf{x}_0) = (-1)^m \overline{L_{n,m}(\mathbf{x}_0)} \quad (m \geq 0). \quad (3.28)$$

The coefficient of the local expansion is translated according to the following formula when the centre of the local expansion is shifted from \mathbf{x}_0 to \mathbf{x}_1

$$L_{n,m}(\mathbf{x}_1) = \sum_{n'=n}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n'-n,m'-m}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}_1}) L_{n',m'}(\mathbf{x}_0), \quad (3.29)$$

where we have used (3.21) and (3.26) (See Appendix E.3). The procedure given by (3.29) is called ‘‘L2L translation’’.

3.2.3 FM-BIEM with regularised integral equation

In this section we use the regularised integral equation (3.16) for the formulation. We now compute the integral on the right-hand side of (3.16) over a subset of S denoted by S_y for \mathbf{x} which is away from S_y . Using (3.17) we obtain

$$-n_j(\mathbf{x}) e_{jpl} \int_{S_y} \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial y_p} n_i(\mathbf{y}) e_{iql} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y_q}(\mathbf{y}) dS_y = \frac{1}{4\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n n_j(\mathbf{x}) \overline{S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O \mathbf{x}})} \widetilde{M}_{j,n,m}(O), \quad (3.30)$$

where $\widetilde{M}_{j,n,m}(O)$ is the multipole moment centred at O , defined by

$$\widetilde{M}_{j,n,m}(O) = -e_{jpl} \int_{S_y} \frac{\partial R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O \mathbf{x}})}{\partial y_p} n_i(\mathbf{y}) e_{iql} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y_q}(\mathbf{y}) dS_y. \quad (3.31)$$

In (3.30) we have assumed that the inequality $|\overrightarrow{O \mathbf{x}}| > |\overrightarrow{O \mathbf{y}}|$ ($\mathbf{y} \in S_y$) holds. The multipole moment is transformed when the centre of the multipole moment is translated from O to O'

$$\widetilde{M}_{j,n,m}(O') = \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n'-n,m'-m}(\overrightarrow{O' O}) \widetilde{M}_{j,n-n',m-m'}(O), \quad (3.32)$$

where we have used (3.21) and (3.31). $\widetilde{M}_{j,n,m}(O)$ has the same property as that for $M_{n,m}(O)$ given in (3.25):

$$\widetilde{M}_{j,n,-m}(O) = (-1)^m \overline{\widetilde{M}_{j,n,m}(O)} \quad (m \geq 0). \quad (3.33)$$

The integral in (3.30) can be evaluated with the coefficient of the local expansion $\widetilde{L}_{j,n,m}(\mathbf{x}_0)$ as follows:

$$-n_j(\mathbf{x}) e_{jpl} \int_{S_y} \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial y_p} n_i(\mathbf{y}) e_{iql} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y_q}(\mathbf{y}) dS_y = \frac{1}{4\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n n_j(\mathbf{x}) R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}}) \widetilde{L}_{j,n,m}(\mathbf{x}_0), \quad (3.34)$$

where $\tilde{L}_{j,n,m}(\mathbf{x}_0)$ is expressed in terms of $\tilde{M}_{j,n,m}(O)$ by

$$\tilde{L}_{j,n,m}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} (-1)^n \overline{S_{n+n',m+m'}}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0}) \tilde{M}_{j,n',m'}(O). \quad (3.35)$$

In the derivation of this formula we have used (3.20) and have assumed that the inequality $|\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0}| > |\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}|$ holds. Also, $\tilde{L}_{j,n,m}(\mathbf{x}_0)$ has the same property as that for $L_{n,m}(\mathbf{x}_0)$ given in (3.28):

$$\tilde{L}_{j,n,-m}(\mathbf{x}_0) = (-1)^m \overline{\tilde{L}_{j,n,m}(\mathbf{x}_0)} \quad (m \geq 0). \quad (3.36)$$

The coefficient of the local expansion is translated according to the following formula when the centre of the local expansion is shifted from \mathbf{x}_0 to \mathbf{x}_1

$$\tilde{L}_{j,n,m}(\mathbf{x}_1) = \sum_{n'=n}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n'-n,m'-m}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}_1}) \tilde{L}_{j,n',m'}(\mathbf{x}_0), \quad (3.37)$$

where we have used (3.21) and (3.34).

Notice that in FM-BIEM with the regularised integral equation the multipole moments and the coefficients of the local expansion have three components for a given pair of n and m . This means that this formulation requires three times as much computational cost for M2M, M2L and L2L translation as FM-BIEM with the hypersingular integral equation obtained in the previous section and moreover the memory requirement of the regularised formulation is also triple that of the hypersingular one. However, because in the regularised formulation we can compute the multipole moments analytically (See the following section), FM-BIEM with regularisation can be expected to yield more accurate results than that without regularisation. Hence, we investigate the difference between numerical results obtained with two formulation through numerical experiments.

We have thus prepared all the formulae needed for FM-BIEM. Using formulae presented above and the algorithm described in chapter 2, one can implement FM-BIEM.

3.2.4 Numerical procedure

Discretisation of the regularised integral equation with piecewise constant shape functions

Discretising the regularised integral equation (3.16) with piecewise constant shape functions, one obtains the following equation:

$$-\frac{\partial u^\infty(\mathbf{x})}{\partial n_x} = \sum_J \oint_{\partial S_J} n_j(\mathbf{x}) e_{jpl} \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial y_p} dy_l \phi_J, \quad (3.38)$$

where S_J is a plane element in S and ϕ_J represents ϕ on S_J . In (3.38) the right-hand screw convention is applied to the direction of the integration along ∂S_J . We use (3.38) for the direct computation instead of (3.16). In the similar way the multipole moment $\tilde{M}_{j,n,m}(O)$ in (3.31) is rewritten as

$$\tilde{M}_{j,n,m}(O) = \sum_L \oint_{\partial S_L} e_{jpl} \frac{\partial R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}})}{\partial y_p} dy_l \phi_L, \quad (3.39)$$

where S_L is a plane element in S_y and ϕ_L represents ϕ on S_L .

Analytical computation of the multipole moment $\tilde{M}_{j,n,m}$

Noting that $R_{n,m}$ is a homogeneous polynomial of degree n , one can compute the right-hand side in (3.39) analytically when S_L is a polygon as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{M}_{j,n,m}(O) &= \sum_{L=1}^{N_L} \oint_{\partial S_L} e_{jpl} \frac{\partial R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}})}{\partial y_p} dy_l \phi_L \\ &= \sum_{L=1}^{N_L} \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \sum_{I=1}^K R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{OP_I^L}) \int_{P_I^L P_{I+1}^L} e_{jpl} \frac{\partial R_{n-n',m-m'}(\overrightarrow{P_I^L \mathbf{y}})}{\partial y_p} dy_l \phi_L \end{aligned}$$

$$= \sum_{L=1}^{N_L} \sum_{I=1}^K \sum_{n'=0}^{n-1} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{OP_I^L}) e_{jpl} \frac{1}{n-n'} \frac{\partial R_{n-n',m-m'}(\overrightarrow{P_I^L P_{I+1}^L})}{\partial y_p} \phi_L, \quad (3.40)$$

where we have used (3.21) in (3.40), N_L is the number of the plane elements in S_y , $P_I^L (I = 1, 2, \dots, K)$ are the vertices of S_L and $P_{K+1}^L = P_1^L$ (See Fig.3.4). In FM-BIEM with the regularised integral equation we can use (3.40) for the computation of the multipole moment in (3.31). The computational cost for $\widetilde{M}_{j,n,m}(O)$ for a given pair of n and m is $O(3N_L K n^2)$. On the other hand, we compute the integral in

Figure 3.4: Line integration for analytical computation of $\widetilde{M}_{j,n,m}$

(3.23) numerically with Gaussian quadrature as follows:

$$M_{n,m}(O) = \int_{S_y} \frac{\partial R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{Oy})}{\partial n_y} \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y = \sum_{L=1}^{N_L} \sum_{I=1}^{N_g} w_I \frac{\partial R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{Oy^I})}{\partial n_y} \phi(\mathbf{y}^I) \Delta(S_L), \quad (3.41)$$

where w_I and \mathbf{y}_I^I are the Gaussian weight and Gaussian point on S_L , N_g is the number of the Gaussian points and $\Delta(S_L)$ is the area of S_L . Therefore, the computational cost for $M_{n,m}(O)$ for a given pair of n and m is $O(N_g N_L)$. As n increases, the computational cost for $\widetilde{M}_{j,n,m}(O)$ for a given pair of n and m becomes large whereas, that for $M_{n,m}(O)$ does not depend on n . Since the computational cost for the multipole moments is not so dominant in FMM, this is not so serious as we shall see. As we have mentioned above, however, the difference in the cost for M2L translations is considerably more serious than that in the cost for the multipole moments.

Algorithm

We briefly describe the usage of formulae presented here in each step in the algorithm of FM-BIEM with the hypersingular integral equation [resp. the regularised integral equation] (See chapter 2 for more details).

Steps 1–2. Same as the steps 1–2 in the algorithm described in chapter 2.

Step 3. Computation of the multipole moments:

In this step we use (3.23) [resp. (3.40)] for the computation of the multipole moments associated with leaves. Also, we use (3.24) [(3.32)] for M2M translations tracing the tree structure of cells upward (decreasing $l(\geq 2)$).

Step 4. Computation of the local expansion:

In this step we use (3.27) [(3.35)] for M2L translations and (3.29) [(3.37)] for L2L translations tracing the tree structure of cells downward (increasing $l(\geq 2)$).

Step 5. Evaluation of the integral in (3.15):

In this step we use (3.38) [(3.38)] for the direct computation and use (3.26) [(3.34)] for the evaluation of contributions with the local expansion.

Computation of $R_{n,m}$ and $S_{n,m}$

Compute $R_{n,m}$ and $S_{n,m}$ and their derivatives using recurrence formulae in Appendix C and relations in Appendix D.

3.2.5 Numerical examples

The proposed techniques have been implemented in Fortran 77, and have been tested on a computer having a DEC Alpha 21264(500 MHz) chip as the CPU. In FMM, we truncate the infinite series in (3.22) [(3.30)] and (3.26) [(3.34)] taking 10 terms. Namely we take 121 [363] multipole moments and coefficients of the local expansion into consideration. Because of the relations in (3.25) [(3.33)] and (3.28) [(3.36)] we store 66 [198] multipole moments and coefficient of the local expansion. Also, we set the maximum number of boundary elements in a leaf to be 100. To solve the resulting matrix equation we use the preconditioned GMRES and adopt the block diagonal matrix corresponding to the leaves as the preconditioner according to Nishida and Hayami [62]. In GMRES we terminate the iteration when the relative error is less than 10^{-5} . In this thesis we mainly use BLAS, LAPACK and SLATEC as mathematical libraries. These are available from Netlib (<http://www.netlib.org/>).

One penny-shaped crack

To begin with we consider a penny-shaped crack having the radius of a_0 and the unit normal vector of $\mathbf{n} = (0, 0, 1)$. The asymptotic field $u^\infty(\mathbf{x})$ is given by $u^\infty(\mathbf{x}) = u_0 x_3 / a_0$. This problem is solved with the conventional BIEM, FM-BIEM with the hypersingular integral equation and the regularised integral equation. In this example we carry out numerical experiments using the following four schemes:

NE1 Conventional BIEM

NE2 FM-BIEM with the hypersingular integral equation

 Compute multipole moments (3.23) numerically with 1 point Gaussian quadrature

NE3 FM-BIEM with the hypersingular integral equation

 Compute multipole moments (3.23) numerically with 3 point Gaussian quadrature

NE4 FM-BIEM with the regularised integral equation

Fig.3.5 shows the 9592 DOF mesh. Fig.3.6 plots the total CPU time (sec) required with numerical experiments NE1, NE2, NE3 and NE4 vs the number of unknowns. This figure shows that FM-BIEM is faster than the conventional BIEM when the number of unknowns is larger than several thousands. Fig.3.7 shows the CPU time per iteration (sec) vs the number of unknowns. Fig.3.8 shows ratios of the computational times required with FM-BIEM (NE2,NE3,NE4) to the computational time required with the conventional BIEM (NE1). Fig.3.9 shows the L_2 -norm error defined as

$$\text{Error} = \frac{\|\tilde{\phi} - \phi\|}{\|\phi\|},$$

where $\|\cdot\|$ denotes the L_2 -norm, $\tilde{\phi}$ is the corresponding numerical result obtained with FM-BIEM (NE2,NE3,NE4) and ϕ is the numerical result obtained with the conventional BIEM (NE1), respectively. Fig.3.10, Fig.3.11 and Fig.3.12 show the crack opening displacement ϕ/u_0 obtained with numerical experiments when the number of unknowns is 1912. In these figures the line marked “analytic” indicates the analytical solution (Chen and Huang [9]). Also, Fig.3.13 shows the crack opening displacement when the number of unknowns is 888, 4344 and 20728, respectively. The inaccuracy of the numerical results is due to collocation method with piecewise constant shape functions but not to FMM.

The numerical results show that the FM-BIEM with the hypersingular integral equation is more efficient than that with the regularised integral equation. Although in the regularised formulation we can compute the multipole moments analytically, the results obtained with the formulation without regularisation are more accurate than that with regularisation. It seems that these unexpected results are due to the fact that a canceling may occur in computation of the zero-valued integral (See (L.3) in Appendix L.1) with FMM which is used to regularise the hypersingular integral equation (See Appendix L.1).

Many penny-shaped cracks

We now consider an infinite space which contains an array of $4 \times 4 \times 4 (= 64)$ penny-shaped cracks, each having the same radius a_0 subjected to the same asymptotic condition as in the previous example. The centroids of these cracks are located regularly with an interval of $4a_0$ in each coordinate direction, but the orientation of each crack is taken random. Fig.3.14 shows the mesh for 64 cracks (total DOF=30,208), with each crack having 472 DOF. Fig.3.15 shows the crack opening displacements; we superimposed the non-dimensional crack opening displacement ϕ/u_0 plotted in the normal direction on the non-dimensional mesh \mathbf{x}/a_0 . The required CPU time with FM-BIEM is 2426 (sec).

Figure 3.5: Crack mesh (DOF=9592)

Figure 3.6: Total CPU time (sec)

Figure 3.7: CPU time per iteration (sec)

Figure 3.8: Ratio of the time required with FM-BIEM (TimeFM-BIEM) to the time required with the conventional BIEM (TimeBIEM)

Figure 3.9: L_2 -norm Error

Figure 3.10: Crack opening displacement ϕ/u_0 obtained with NE1 and NE2

Figure 3.11: Crack opening displacement ϕ/u_0 obtained with NE1 and NE3

Figure 3.12: Crack opening displacement ϕ/u_0 obtained with NE1 and NE4

Figure 3.13: Crack opening displacement

Figure 3.14: Crack mesh (DOF=30,208)

Figure 3.15: Crack opening displacement (DOF=30,208)

3.3 Crack problems for three-dimensional elastostatics with collocation method

In this section we discuss an application of FM-BIEM to crack problems for three-dimensional elastostatics. Applications of FM-BIEM to ordinary problems in three-dimensional elastostatics are found in Fu et al. [18, 19], Fukui and Kutsumi [27] and Takahashi et al. [78]. In our formulation we use 4 multipole moments for both ordinary problems and crack problems. On the other hand, Fu et al. use 12 multipole moments in their FMM formulation and Fukui and Kutsumi use the Neuber-Papkovich representation to obtain the same 4 multipole moment formulation as the present one. Also, Takahashi et al. use our formulation. In this section we use collocation method and piecewise constant shape functions for discretisation of BIEs. In elastostatics we can compute the multipole moments analytically in the regularised formulation. Although we have shown that FM-BIEM with the regularised integral equation is slower than FM-BIEM with the hypersingular integral equation in Laplace's equation, it is of interest to examine if the same conclusion is true in elasticity as well. Hence, we describe the regularised formulation as well as the non-regularised formulation once again.

The material in this section is from Yoshida et al. [84].

3.3.1 Integral equation

Our problem is to find a solution \mathbf{u} of the equation of elastostatics

$$C_{ijkl}u_{k,lj}(\mathbf{x}) = 0 \quad \text{in } R^3 \setminus \bar{S},$$

subject to the boundary condition

$$t_i^\pm(\mathbf{x}) := C_{ijkl}u_{k,l}^\pm(\mathbf{x})n_j(\mathbf{x}) = 0 \quad \text{on } S, \quad (3.42)$$

regularity condition

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}) := \mathbf{u}^+(\mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{u}^-(\mathbf{x}) = 0 \quad \text{on } \partial S, \quad (3.43)$$

and an asymptotic condition

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}) \rightarrow \mathbf{u}^\infty(\mathbf{x}) \quad \text{as } |\mathbf{x}| \rightarrow \infty,$$

where \mathbf{u} , C_{ijkl} , \mathbf{t} , \mathbf{u}^∞ and ϕ stand for the displacement, elasticity tensor, traction vector, a solution of the equation of elastostatics in the whole space and the crack opening displacement, respectively. The components of C_{ijkl} are expressed with Lamé's constants λ, μ and Kronecker's delta δ_{ij} as

$$C_{ijkl} = \lambda\delta_{ij}\delta_{kl} + \mu(\delta_{ik}\delta_{jl} + \delta_{il}\delta_{jk}).$$

The solution \mathbf{u} to this problem has an integral representation given by (See (3.7))

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{u}^\infty(\mathbf{x}) + \int_S C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) n_c(\mathbf{y}) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) dS_y, \quad \mathbf{x} \in R^3 \setminus \bar{S}, \quad (3.44)$$

where $\Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})$ is the fundamental solution of the equation of elastostatics expressed as

$$\Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) = \frac{1}{8\pi\mu} \left(\delta_{ij} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} - \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \right) |\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|. \quad (3.45)$$

Using (3.42) and (3.44), one obtains the following hypersingular integral equation given by (See (3.9))

$$t_a^\infty(\mathbf{x}) = - \int_S n_b(\mathbf{x}) C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) C_{cdjl} n_c(\mathbf{y}) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) dS_y, \quad \mathbf{x} \in S, \quad (3.46)$$

where \int stands for the finite part of a divergent integral and $\mathbf{t}^\infty(\mathbf{x})$ indicates the traction associated with $\mathbf{u}^\infty(\mathbf{x})$. The hypersingular integral equation (3.46) can be regularised as (See Appendix L.2)

$$t_a^\infty(\mathbf{x}) = \int_S n_b(\mathbf{x}) C_{abik} e_{rck} C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) e_{rqs} \frac{\partial \phi_d(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_q} n_s(\mathbf{y}) dS_y, \quad (3.47)$$

where \int stands for the Cauchy principal value of a singular integral. We use (3.47) for a direct computation of (3.46). In the following sections we describe two types of FM-BIEM; one is FM-BIEM with the hypersingular integral equation and the other is FM-BIEM with the regularised integral equation.

3.3.2 FM-BIEM with hypersingular integral equation

In this section we use the hypersingular integral equation (3.46) for the formulation. In the application of FMM to BIEM our starting point is to expand the fundamental solution $\Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})$ into a series of products of functions of \mathbf{x} and those of \mathbf{y} . From the expression of (3.45) one finds that it is necessary to expand $|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|$ into a series. Thus, we expand $|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|$ as (See Appendix F)

$$|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}| = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \left(\frac{\overline{S_{n,m}(\overline{\mathbf{x}})} |\overline{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{y}}|^2 R_{n,m}(\overline{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{y}})}{2n+3} - \frac{|\overline{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{x}}|^2 \overline{S_{n,m}(\overline{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{x}})} R_{n,m}(\overline{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{y}})}{2n-1} \right), |\overline{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{x}}| > |\overline{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{y}}|. \quad (3.48)$$

Using (3.48), we rewrite (3.45) as (See Appendix G)

$$\Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) = \frac{1}{8\pi\mu} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \left(\overline{F_{ij,n,m}^S(\overline{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{x}})} R_{n,m}(\overline{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{y}}) + \overline{G_{i,n,m}^S(\overline{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{x}})} (\overline{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{y}})_j R_{n,m}(\overline{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{y}}) \right), \quad (3.49)$$

where $F_{ij,n,m}^S$ and $G_{i,n,m}^S$ are functions defined as

$$F_{ij,n,m}^S(\overline{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{x}}) = \frac{\lambda + 3\mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \delta_{ij} S_{n,m}(\overline{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{x}}) - \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} (\overline{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{x}})_j \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} S_{n,m}(\overline{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{x}}), \quad (3.50)$$

$$G_{i,n,m}^S(\overline{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{x}}) = \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} S_{n,m}(\overline{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{x}}). \quad (3.51)$$

We now compute the integral on the right-hand side of (3.46) over a subset of S denoted by S_y for \mathbf{x} which is away from S_y . Using (3.49), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{S_y} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) C_{cdjl} n_c(\mathbf{y}) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &= \frac{1}{8\pi\mu} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \overline{F_{ij,n,m}^S(\overline{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{x}})} M_{j,n,m}^1(O) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \overline{G_{i,n,m}^S(\overline{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{x}})} M_{n,m}^2(O) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (3.52)$$

where $M_{j,n,m}^1(O)$ and $M_{n,m}^2(O)$ are the multipole moments centred at O , expressed as

$$M_{j,n,m}^1(O) = \int_{S_y} C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} R_{n,m}(\overline{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{y}}) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) n_c(\mathbf{y}) dS_y, \quad (3.53)$$

$$M_{n,m}^2(O) = \int_{S_y} C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} ((\overline{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{y}})_j R_{n,m}(\overline{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{y}})) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) n_c(\mathbf{y}) dS_y. \quad (3.54)$$

Notice that $M_{j,n,m}^1(O)$ has three components and $M_{n,m}^2(O)$ has one component for a given pair of n and m , and therefore the number of multipole moments in this formulation is 4. Fu et al. [18] applied FM-BIEM to three-dimensional elastostatics and used 4 and 12 multipole moments for the single- and double-layer potentials in their formulation, whereas in our formulation we use 4 multipole moments for ordinary problems where the single- and double-layer potentials are used as well as for crack problems (details of formulations for the single- and double-layer potentials are given later). It is seen that the number multipole moments in our formulation is related to the fact that in the Neuber-Papkovich representation the displacement field is expressed in terms of four harmonics functions. Also, Fukui and Kutsumi [27] use 4 moment formulation for ordinary problems.

Noting (A.5) and the fact that ϕ_i is real-valued one can find that the multipole moments have the following properties:

$$M_{j,n,-m}^1(O) = (-1)^m \overline{M_{j,n,m}^1(O)} \quad (m \geq 0), \quad (3.55)$$

$$M_{n,-m}^2(O) = (-1)^m \overline{M_{n,m}^2(O)} \quad (m \geq 0). \quad (3.56)$$

The multipole moments are translated according to the following formulae as the centre of multipole expansion is shifted from O to O' :

$$M_{j,n,m}^1(O') = \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\overline{O'O}) M_{j,n-n',m-m'}^1(O), \quad (3.57)$$

$$M_{n,m}^2(O') = \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\overline{O'O}) (M_{n-n',m-m'}^2(O) - (\overline{O'O})_j M_{j,n-n',m-m'}^1(O)), \quad (3.58)$$

where we have used (3.21), (3.53) and (3.54) (See Appendix H.1). The procedures given by (3.57) and (3.58) are called ‘‘M2M translation’’.

In the evaluation of the integral on the right-hand side of (3.46) one can use not only the multiple moments but also the coefficients of local expansion in the following manner:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{S_y} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) C_{cdjl} n_c(\mathbf{y}) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &= \frac{1}{8\pi\mu} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} F_{ij,n,m}^R(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) L_{j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} G_{i,n,m}^R(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) L_{n,m}^2(\mathbf{x}_0) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (3.59)$$

where $L_{j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0)$ and $L_{n,m}^2(\mathbf{x}_0)$ are the coefficients of the local expansion centred at \mathbf{x}_0 and are expressed with $M_{j,n,m}^1(O)$ and $M_{n,m}^2(O)$ by

$$L_{j,n',m'}^1(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n (-1)^{n'} \overline{S_{n+n',m+m'}}(\overline{O\mathbf{x}_0}) M_{j,n,m}^1(O), \quad (3.60)$$

$$L_{n',m'}^2(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n (-1)^{n'} \overline{S_{n+n',m+m'}}(\overline{O\mathbf{x}_0}) (M_{n,m}^2(O) - (\overline{O\mathbf{x}_0})_j M_{j,n,m}^1(O)). \quad (3.61)$$

Also, $F_{ij,n,m}^R$ and $G_{i,n,m}^R$ are functions obtained by replacing $S_{n,m}$ with $R_{n,m}$ in (3.50) and (3.51). In these formulae we have used (3.20) and have assumed that the inequality $|\overline{O\mathbf{x}_0}| > |\overline{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}|$ holds (See Appendix H.2). The procedures given by (3.60) and (3.61) are called ‘‘M2L translation’’. Notice that $L_{j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0)$ has three components and $L_{n,m}^2(\mathbf{x}_0)$ has one component for a given pair of n and m , and therefore the number of the coefficients of the local expansion in this formulation is 4. Also, $L_{j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0)$ and $L_{n,m}^2(\mathbf{x}_0)$ have the following properties:

$$L_{j,n,-m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0) = (-1)^m \overline{L_{j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0)} \quad (m \geq 0), \quad (3.62)$$

$$L_{n,-m}^2(\mathbf{x}_0) = (-1)^m \overline{L_{n,m}^2(\mathbf{x}_0)} \quad (m \geq 0). \quad (3.63)$$

The coefficients of the local expansion are translated according to the following formulae when the centre of the local expansion is shifted from \mathbf{x}_0 to \mathbf{x}_1

$$L_{j,n'',m''}^1(\mathbf{x}_1) = \sum_{n'=n''}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n'-n'',m'-m''}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}_1}) L_{j,n',m'}^1(\mathbf{x}_0), \quad (3.64)$$

$$L_{n'',m''}^2(\mathbf{x}_1) = \sum_{n'=n''}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n'-n'',m'-m''}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}_1}) \left(L_{n',m'}^2(\mathbf{x}_0) - (\overline{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}_1})_p L_{p,n',m'}^1(\mathbf{x}_0) \right), \quad (3.65)$$

where we have used (3.21) and (3.59) (See Appendix H.3). The procedures given by (3.64) and (3.65) are called ‘‘L2L translation’’.

3.3.3 FM-BIEM with regularised integral equation

In this section we use the regularised integral equation (3.47) for the formulation. We now compute the integral on the right-hand side of (3.47) over a subset of S denoted by S_y for \mathbf{x} which is away from S_y . Using (3.49), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{S_y} e_{rck} C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) e_{rqs} \frac{\partial \phi_d(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_q} n_s(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &= \frac{1}{8\pi\mu} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \left(\overline{F_{ij,n,m}^S(\overline{O\mathbf{x}})} \widetilde{M}_{k,j,n,m}^1(O) + \overline{G_{i,n,m}^S(\overline{O\mathbf{x}})} \widetilde{M}_{k,n,m}^2(O) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (3.66)$$

where $\widetilde{M}_{k,j,n,m}^1(O)$ and $\widetilde{M}_{k,n,m}^2(O)$ are the multipole moments centred at O , expressed as

$$\widetilde{M}_{k,j,n,m}^1(O) = \int_{S_y} e_{rck} C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} R_{n,m}(\overline{O\mathbf{y}}) e_{rqs} \frac{\partial \phi_d(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_q} n_s(\mathbf{y}) dS_y, \quad (3.67)$$

$$\widetilde{M}_{k,N,M}^2(O) = \int_{S_y} e_{rck} C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} ((\overline{O\mathbf{y}})_j R_{n,m}(\overline{O\mathbf{y}})) e_{rqs} \frac{\partial \phi_d(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_q} n_s(\mathbf{y}) dS_y. \quad (3.68)$$

Notice that $\widetilde{M}_{k,j,n,m}^1(O)$ has nine components and $\widetilde{M}_{k,n,m}^2(O)$ has three components for a given pair of n and m , and therefore the number of multipole moments in this formulation is 12. Also, the multipole moments have the following properties:

$$\widetilde{M}_{k,j,n,-m}^1(O) = (-1)^m \overline{\widetilde{M}_{k,j,n,m}^1(O)} \quad (m \geq 0), \quad (3.69)$$

$$\widetilde{M}_{k,n,-m}^2(O) = (-1)^m \overline{\widetilde{M}_{k,n,m}^2(O)} \quad (m \geq 0). \quad (3.70)$$

The multipole moments are translated according to the following formulae as the centre of multipole expansion is shifted from O to O' :

$$\widetilde{M}_{k,j,n,m}^1(O') = \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{O'O}) \widetilde{M}_{k,j,n-n',m-m'}^1(O), \quad (3.71)$$

$$\widetilde{M}_{k,n,m}^2(O') = \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{O'O}) (\widetilde{M}_{k,n-n',m-m'}^2(O) - (\overrightarrow{OO'})_j \widetilde{M}_{k,j,n-n',m-m'}^1(O)), \quad (3.72)$$

where we have used (3.21), (3.67) and (3.68). In the evaluation of the integral on the right-hand side of (3.47) one can use not only the multipole moments but also the coefficients of local expansion in the following manner:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{S_y} e_{rck} C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) e_{rqs} \frac{\partial \phi_d(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_q} n_s(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &= \frac{1}{8\pi\mu} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n (F_{ij,n,m}^R(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) \widetilde{L}_{k,j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0) + G_{i,n,m}^R(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) \widetilde{L}_{k,n,m}^2(\mathbf{x}_0)), \end{aligned} \quad (3.73)$$

where $\widetilde{L}_{k,j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0)$ and $\widetilde{L}_{k,n,m}^2(\mathbf{x}_0)$ are the coefficients of the local expansion centred at \mathbf{x}_0 and are expressed with $\widetilde{M}_{k,j,n,m}^1(O)$ and $\widetilde{M}_{k,n,m}^2(O)$ by

$$\widetilde{L}_{k,j,n',m'}^1(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n (-1)^{n'} \overline{S_{n+n',m+m'}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0})} \widetilde{M}_{k,j,n,m}^1(O), \quad (3.74)$$

$$\widetilde{L}_{k,n',m'}^2(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n (-1)^{n'} \overline{S_{n+n',m+m'}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0})} (\widetilde{M}_{k,n,m}^2(O) - (\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0})_j \widetilde{M}_{k,j,n,m}^1(O)). \quad (3.75)$$

In these formulae we have used (3.20) and have assumed that the inequality $|\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0}| > |\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}|$ holds. Notice that $\widetilde{L}_{k,j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0)$ has nine components and $\widetilde{L}_{k,n,m}^2(\mathbf{x}_0)$ has three component for a given pair of n and m , and therefore the number of coefficients of the local expansion in this formulation is 12. Also, the coefficients of the local expansion have the following properties:

$$\widetilde{L}_{k,j,n,-m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0) = (-1)^m \overline{\widetilde{L}_{k,j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0)} \quad (m \geq 0), \quad (3.76)$$

$$\widetilde{L}_{k,n,-m}^2(\mathbf{x}_0) = (-1)^m \overline{\widetilde{L}_{k,n,m}^2(\mathbf{x}_0)} \quad (m \geq 0). \quad (3.77)$$

The coefficients of the local expansion are translated according to the following formulae when the centre of the local expansion is shifted from \mathbf{x}_0 to \mathbf{x}_1

$$\widetilde{L}_{k,j,n'',m''}^1(\mathbf{x}_1) = \sum_{n'=n''}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n'-n'',m'-m''}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}_1}) \widetilde{L}_{k,j,n',m'}^1(\mathbf{x}_0), \quad (3.78)$$

$$\widetilde{L}_{k,n'',m''}^2(\mathbf{x}_1) = \sum_{n'=n''}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n'-n'',m'-m''}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}_1}) \left(\widetilde{L}_{k,n',m'}^2(\mathbf{x}_0) - (\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}_1})_j \widetilde{L}_{k,j,n',m'}^1(\mathbf{x}_0) \right), \quad (3.79)$$

where we have used (3.21) and (3.73).

As we shall see in FM-BIEM with the regularised integral equation we can compute the multipole moments analytically (See the following section), but the multipole moments and the coefficients of the local expansion have twelve components for a given pair of n and m . Namely, the number of the multipole moments in the regularised formulation is triple that in the hypersingular one. This trade-off issue will be settled through a numerical experiment in section 3.3.5.

3.3.4 Numerical procedures

Discretisation of the regularised integral equation with piecewise constant shape functions

Discretising the regularised integral equation (3.47) with piecewise constant shape functions, one obtains the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned} t_a^\infty(\mathbf{x}) &= \int_S n_b(\mathbf{x}) C_{abik} e_{rck} C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) e_{rqs} \frac{\partial \phi_d(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_q} n_s(\mathbf{y}) dy_r \\ &= \sum_J \oint_{\partial S_J} n_b(\mathbf{x}) C_{abik} e_{rck} C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) dy_r \phi_d^J, \end{aligned} \quad (3.80)$$

where S_J is a plane element in S and ϕ_d^J represents ϕ on S_J . In (3.80) the right-hand screw convention is applied to the direction of the integration along ∂S_J . We use (3.80) for the direct computation instead of (3.47). In the similar way $\widetilde{M}_{kj,n,m}^1(O)$ and $\widetilde{M}_{k,n,m}^2(O)$ are rewritten as

$$\widetilde{M}_{kj,n,m}^1(O) = \sum_J \oint_{\partial S_J} e_{rck} C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) dy_r \phi_d^J, \quad (3.81)$$

$$\widetilde{M}_{k,n,m}^2(O) = \sum_J \oint_{\partial S_J} e_{rck} C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} ((\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}})_j R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}})) dy_r \phi_d^J. \quad (3.82)$$

Analytical computation of the multipole moment $\widetilde{M}_{kj,n,m}^1$ and $\widetilde{M}_{k,n,m}^2$

Noting that $R_{n,m}$ is a homogeneous polynomial of degree n , one can compute the right-hand side in (3.81) and (3.82) analytically as follows when S_J is a polygon:

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{M}_{kj,n,m}^1(O) &= \sum_J \oint_{\partial S_J} e_{rck} C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) dy_r \phi_d^J \\ &= \sum_J \sum_{I=1}^K \sum_{n'=1}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n-n',m-m'}(\overrightarrow{OP_I^J}) e_{rck} C_{cdjl} \frac{1}{n'} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{P_I^J P_{I+1}^J}) (\overrightarrow{P_I^J P_{I+1}^J})_r \phi_d^J, \end{aligned} \quad (3.83)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{M}_{k,n,m}^2(O) &= \sum_J \oint_{\partial S_J} e_{rck} C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} ((\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}})_j R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}})) dy_r \phi_d^J \\ &= \sum_J \sum_{I=1}^K \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n-n',m-m'}(\overrightarrow{OP_I^J}) e_{rck} C_{cdjl} (\overrightarrow{P_I^J P_{I+1}^J})_r \left(\frac{1}{n'+1} \delta_{lj} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{P_I^J P_{I+1}^J}) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{n'+1} (\overrightarrow{P_I^J P_{I+1}^J})_j \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{P_I^J P_{I+1}^J}) \right) \phi_d^J \\ &\quad + \sum_J \sum_{I=1}^K \sum_{n'=1}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n-n',m-m'}(\overrightarrow{OP_I^J}) e_{rck} C_{cdjl} (\overrightarrow{P_I^J P_{I+1}^J})_r \frac{1}{n'} (\overrightarrow{OP_I^J})_j \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{P_I^J P_{I+1}^J}) \phi_d^J, \end{aligned} \quad (3.84)$$

where we have used (3.21). In (3.83) and (3.84) $P_I^J (I = 1, 2, \dots, K)$ are the vertices of S_J and $P_{K+1}^J = P_1^J$. In FM-BIEM with the regularised integral equation we use (3.83) and (3.84) for the computation of the multipole moments in (3.67) and (3.68).

Algorithm

We briefly describe the usage of formulae presented here in each step in the algorithm of FM-BIEM with the hypersingular integral equation [the regularised integral equation] (See chapter 2 for more details).

Steps 1–2. Same as the steps 1–2 in the algorithm described in chapter 2.

Step 3. Computation of the multipole moments:

In this step we use (3.53) and (3.54) [(3.83) and (3.84)] for the computation of the multipole moments associated with leaves. Also, we use (3.57) and (3.58) [(3.71) and (3.72)] for M2M translations tracing the tree structure of cells upward (decreasing $l (\geq 2)$).

Figure 3.16: Line integration for analytical computation of $\widetilde{M}_{k,j,n,m}^1$ and $\widetilde{M}_{k,n,m}^2$

Step 4. Computation of the local expansion:

In this step we use (3.60) and (3.61) [(3.74) and (3.75)] for M2L translations and (3.64) and (3.65) [(3.78) and (3.79)] for L2L translations tracing the tree structure of cells downward (increasing $l(\geq 2)$).

Step 5. Evaluation of the integral in (3.46):

In this step we use (3.80) [(3.80)] for the direct computation and use (3.59) [(3.73)] for the evaluation of contributions with the local expansion.

3.3.5 Numerical examples

The proposed techniques have been implemented in Fortran 77 and have been tested on a computer having a DEC Alpha 21264(500 MHz) as the CPU. The integrals in the multipole moments in (3.53) and (3.54) are computed numerically with Gaussian quadrature. The sums in the finite series (3.52) [(3.66)] and (3.59) [(3.73)] are truncated at 10 terms. Namely we take 484 [1452] multipole moments and coefficients of the local expansion into consideration in FM-BIEM with the hypersingular integral equation [the regularised integral equation]. Because of the relations in (3.55) [(3.69)], (3.56) [(3.70)], (3.62) [(3.76)] and (3.63) [(3.77)] we store 264 [792] multipole moments and coefficient of the local expansion. The maximum number of boundary elements in a leaf is set to be 100. To solve the resulting matrix equation we use the preconditioned GMRES and adopt the block diagonal matrix corresponding to the leaves as the preconditioner according to Nishida and Hayami [62]. In GMRES the iteration is stopped when the relative error is below 10^{-5} .

One penny-shaped crack

To begin with we consider a penny-shaped crack having the radius of a_0 and the unit normal vector of $\mathbf{n} = (0, 0, 1)$. The function $\mathbf{t}^\infty(\mathbf{x})$ is given by $\mathbf{t}^\infty(\mathbf{x}) = \boldsymbol{\sigma}^\infty(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{n}(\mathbf{x})$ where

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^\infty(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & p_0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (3.85)$$

and, hence, $\mathbf{t}^\infty = (0, 0, p_0)$. The asymptotic condition (3.85) indicates that the domain is subjected to a uniform uniaxial tension. Also, Poisson's ratio is set to be 0.25. This problem is solved with the conventional BIEM, FM-BIEM with the hypersingular integral equation and the regularised integral equation. In this example we carry out numerical experiments using the following four schemes:

NE1 Conventional BIEM

NE2 FM-BIEM with hypersingular integral equation

Compute multipole moments (3.53) and (3.54) numerically with 1 point Gaussian quadrature

NE3 FM-BIEM with hypersingular integral equation

Compute multipole moments (3.53) and (3.54) numerically with 3 point Gaussian quadrature

NE4 FM-BIEM with regularised integral equation:

Fig.3.17 plots the total CPU time (sec) required with numerical experiments NE1, NE2, NE3 and NE4, respectively vs the number of unknowns. This figure shows that the FM-BIEM is faster than the conventional BIEM when the number of unknowns is larger than several thousands. Fig.3.18 shows the CPU time per iteration (sec). Fig.3.19 shows ratios of the computational times required with FM-BIEM (NE2,NE3,NE4) to the computational time required with the conventional BIEM (NE1). Fig.3.20 shows the L_2 -norm error defined as

$$\text{error} = \frac{\|\tilde{\phi} - \phi\|}{\|\phi\|}$$

where $\|\cdot\|$ denotes the L_2 -norm, $\tilde{\phi}$ is the corresponding numerical results obtained with FM-BIEM (NE2,NE3,NE4) and ϕ is the numerical result obtained with conventional BIEM, respectively. Fig.3.21, Fig.3.22 and Fig.3.23 show the non-dimensional crack opening displacement $\mu\phi_3/a_0p_0$ obtained with numerical experiments when the number of unknowns is 1912. In these figures the line marked “analytic” indicates the analytical solution (Green and Zerna [32]). Also, Fig.3.24 shows the crack opening displacement when the number of unknowns is 2664, 5736 and 28776 respectively.

The results show that the hypersingular formulation is more efficient than the regularised one. As in the case of Laplace’s equation, the regularised formulation is inferior to the non-regularised one in both computational time and precision. Considering results obtained through numerical experiments in Laplace’s equation and elastostatics, we can see that the non-regularised formulation is suitable for FM-BIEM.

Many penny-shaped cracks

We now consider an infinite space which contains an array of $8 \times 8 \times 8 (= 512)$ (total DOF=380,928) penny-shaped cracks, each having the same radius a_0 subjected to the same asymptotic condition as in the previous example. The centroids of these cracks are located regularly with an interval of $4a_0$ in each coordinate direction, but the orientation of each crack is taken random. Fig.3.25 shows the mesh for 512 cracks (total DOF=380,928), with each crack having 744 DOF. Fig.3.26 shows the crack opening displacements obtained with FM-BIEM. In this figure we superimposed the non-dimensional crack opening displacement $\mu\phi/a_0p_0$ on the non-dimensional mesh \mathbf{x}/a_0 . The required CPU time with FM-BIEM is 6739 (sec).

Figure 3.17: Total CPU time (sec)

Figure 3.18: CPU time per iteration (sec)

Figure 3.19: Ratio of the time required with FM-BIEM (TimeFM-BIEM) to the time required with the conventional BIEM (TimeBIEM)

Figure 3.20: L_2 -norm Error

Figure 3.21: Crack opening displacement NE1 and NE2

Figure 3.22: Crack opening displacement NE1 and NE3

Figure 3.23: Crack opening displacement NE1 and NE4

Figure 3.24: Crack opening displacement

Figure 3.25: Crack mesh (DOF=380,928)

Figure 3.26: Crack opening displacement (DOF=380,928)

3.3.6 Comparison of formulations for the single- and double-layer potentials

In this section we compare our FMM formulation with the formulation proposed by Fu et al. [18] and attempt to clarify the difference between these formulations. In this section we deal with both single- and double-layer potentials.

Fu et al. noted that the fundamental solution in (3.45) is expressed as

$$\Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) = P_{ij}(\mathbf{x}) \left(\frac{1}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} \right) + Q_i(\mathbf{x}) \left(\frac{y_j}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} \right), \quad (3.86)$$

where $P_{ij}(\mathbf{x})$ and $Q_i(\mathbf{x})$ are given by

$$P_{ij}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{8\pi\mu} \left(\frac{\lambda + 3\mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \delta_{ij} - \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} x_j \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \right), \quad Q_i(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{8\pi\mu} \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}.$$

To interpret their expression for the double layer kernel T_{ij} defined by

$$T_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ik}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) C_{klpj} n_p(\mathbf{y}), \quad (3.87)$$

we see that the following alternative to (3.87) is available:

$$T_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = -\frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} \Gamma_{ik}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) C_{klpj} n_p(\mathbf{y}). \quad (3.88)$$

From (3.86) and (3.88) we obtain

$$T_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = -n_p(\mathbf{y}) C_{klpj} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} \left(P_{ik}(\mathbf{x}) \left(\frac{1}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} \right) + Q_i(\mathbf{x}) \left(\frac{y_k}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} \right) \right), \quad (3.89)$$

which can further be reduced to

$$T_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \Theta_{ijp}(\mathbf{x}) \left(\frac{n_p(\mathbf{y})}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} \right) + \Lambda_{ip}(\mathbf{x}) \left(\frac{y_j n_p(\mathbf{y})}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} \right), \quad (3.90)$$

where Θ_{ijk} and Λ_{ij} are certain operators defined in Fu et al. [18]. In this way they could maintain the term $1/|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|$ in their expression for T_{ij} , thus making the use of the FMM for Laplace's equation possible in their formulation. The single- and double-layer potentials

$$U_i(\mathbf{x}) := \int_S \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \varphi_j(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \quad (3.91)$$

$$W_i(\mathbf{x}) := \int_S T_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \varphi_j(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \quad (3.92)$$

are now written as

$$U_i(\mathbf{x}) = P_{ij}(\mathbf{x}) \int_S \left(\frac{\varphi_j(\mathbf{y})}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} \right) dS_y + Q_i(\mathbf{x}) \int_S \left(\frac{y_j \varphi_j(\mathbf{y})}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} \right) dS_y \quad (3.93)$$

$$W_i(\mathbf{x}) = \Theta_{ijp}(\mathbf{x}) \int_S \left(\frac{n_p(\mathbf{y}) \varphi_j(\mathbf{y})}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} \right) dS_y + \Lambda_{ip}(\mathbf{x}) \int_S \left(\frac{n_p(\mathbf{y}) y_j \varphi_j(\mathbf{y})}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} \right) dS_y. \quad (3.94)$$

Substituting (3.17) into (3.93) and (3.94), one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} U_i(\mathbf{x}) &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n P_{ij}(\mathbf{x}) \overline{S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})} \acute{M}_{j,n,m}^{1U}(O) + Q_i(\mathbf{x}) \overline{S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})} \acute{M}_{n,m}^{2U}(O), \\ W_i(\mathbf{x}) &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \Theta_{ijp}(\mathbf{x}) \overline{S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})} \acute{M}_{jp,n,m}^{1W}(O) + \Lambda_{ip}(\mathbf{x}) \overline{S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})} \acute{M}_{p,n,m}^{2W}(O), \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \acute{M}_{j,n,m}^{1U}(O) &= \int_S \varphi_j(\mathbf{y}) R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) dS_y, & \acute{M}_{n,m}^{2U}(O) &= \int_S y_j \varphi_j(\mathbf{y}) R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) dS_y, \\ \acute{M}_{jp,n,m}^{1W}(O) &= \int_S n_p(\mathbf{y}) \varphi_j(\mathbf{y}) R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) dS_y, & \acute{M}_{p,n,m}^{2W}(O) &= \int_S n_p(\mathbf{y}) y_j \varphi_j(\mathbf{y}) R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) dS_y. \end{aligned}$$

The multipole moments $\hat{M}_{j,n,m}^{1U}(O)$ has three components and $\hat{M}_{n,m}^{2U}(O)$ has one. Also, the multipole moments $\hat{M}_{jp,n,m}^{1W}(O)$ has nine components and $\hat{M}_{p,n,m}^{2W}(O)$ has three. Thus, one can see that Fu et al. [18] use 4 and 12 multipole moments for the single- and double-layer potentials, respectively.

It is seen that the expression used by Fu et al. [18] is not the only possibility in elastostatics which allows the use of the FMM for Laplace's equation. For example one uses (3.89) instead of (3.90) to have

$$W_i(\mathbf{x}) = -\frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} P_{ik}(\mathbf{x}) \int_S \left(\frac{C_{klpj} n_p(\mathbf{y}) \varphi_j(\mathbf{y})}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} \right) dS_y - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} Q_i(\mathbf{x}) \int_S \left(\frac{C_{klpj} n_p(\mathbf{y}) y_k \varphi_j(\mathbf{y})}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} \right) dS_y. \quad (3.95)$$

Substituting (3.17) into (3.95) one obtains

$$W_i(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n -\frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} P_{ik}(\mathbf{x}) \overline{S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})} \hat{M}_{kl,n,m}^1(O) - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} Q_i(\mathbf{x}) \overline{S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})} \hat{M}_{l,n,m}^2(O)$$

where $\hat{M}_{j,l,N,M}^1(O)$ and $\hat{M}_{l,N,M}^2(O)$ are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{M}_{kl,n,m}^1(O) &= \int_S C_{klpj} R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) n_p(\mathbf{y}) \varphi_j(\mathbf{y}) dS_y, \\ \hat{M}_{l,n,m}^2(O) &= \int_S C_{klpj} R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) y_k n_p(\mathbf{y}) \varphi_j(\mathbf{y}) dS_y. \end{aligned}$$

The moments $\hat{M}_{kl,n,m}^1(O)$ have 6 components (since $\hat{M}_{kl,n,m}^1(O) = \hat{M}_{lk,n,m}^1(O)$) and $\hat{M}_{l,n,m}^2(O)$ have 3. Hence in this case the number of multipole moments for the double-layer potential is 9 for a given pair of n and m .

On the other hand, in order to obtain our formulations for the single- and double-layer potentials we first substitute (3.17) into (3.86):

$$\Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \left(P_{ij}(\mathbf{x}) \overline{S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})} \right) R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) + \left(Q_i(\mathbf{x}) \overline{S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})} \right) R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) y_j. \quad (3.96)$$

Noting the following identities

$$P_{ij}(\mathbf{x}) S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) = \frac{1}{8\pi\mu} F_{ij,n,m}^S(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}), \quad Q_i(\mathbf{x}) S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) = \frac{1}{8\pi\mu} G_{i,n,m}^S(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}),$$

one sees that (3.96) is identical with (3.49).

In order to obtain our expression for the double-layer kernel we use (3.87), instead of (3.88), with (3.49) to have

$$T_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \frac{1}{8\pi\mu} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \left(\frac{\overline{F_{ik,n,m}^S(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})}}{\partial y_l} \frac{\partial R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}})}{\partial y_l} C_{klpj} n_p(\mathbf{y}) + \overline{G_{i,n,m}^S(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})} \frac{\partial \left((\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}})_k R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) \right)}{\partial y_l} C_{klpj} n_p(\mathbf{y}) \right). \quad (3.97)$$

Substituting (3.96) and (3.97) into (3.93) and (3.94) we obtain

$$U_i(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{8\pi\mu} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \overline{F_{ij,n,m}^S(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})} \hat{M}_{j,n,m}^{1U}(O) + \overline{G_{i,n,m}^S(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})} \hat{M}_{n,m}^{2U}(O) \quad (3.98)$$

$$W_i(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{8\pi\mu} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \overline{F_{ik,n,m}^S(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})} \hat{M}_{k,n,m}^{1W}(O) + \overline{G_{i,n,m}^S(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})} \hat{M}_{n,m}^{2W}(O) \quad (3.99)$$

where

$$\hat{M}_{j,n,m}^{1U}(O) = \int_S R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) \varphi_j(\mathbf{y}) dS_y, \quad \hat{M}_{n,m}^{2U}(O) = \int_S R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) y_j \varphi_j(\mathbf{y}) dS_y,$$

$$\hat{M}_{k,n,m}^{1W}(O) = \int_S \frac{\partial R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}})}{\partial y_l} C_{klpj} n_p(\mathbf{y}) \varphi_j(\mathbf{y}) dS_y, \quad \hat{M}_{n,m}^{2W}(O) = \int_S \frac{\partial \left((\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}})_k R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) \right)}{\partial y_l} C_{klpj} n_p(\mathbf{y}) \varphi_j(\mathbf{y}) dS_y.$$

The multipole moments $\hat{M}_{j,n,m}^{1U}(O)$ has three components and $\hat{M}_{n,m}^{2U}(O)$ has one. Also, the multipole moments $\hat{M}_{j,n,m}^{1W}(O)$ has three components and $\hat{M}_{n,m}^{2W}(O)$ has one. In our formulations for both the single- and double-layer potentials the number of the multipole moments is 4 and, moreover, $\hat{M}_{j,n,m}^{1W}(O)$ and $\hat{M}_{n,m}^{2W}(O)$ are the same as the multipole moments (3.53) and (3.54) for crack problems.

Notice that in this case the 4 moment formulation may not necessarily be three times faster than the 12 moment formulation. However, it is seen that our formulation is probably more efficient than Fu et al.'s one because the reduction of the number of the multipole moments leads to the reduction of M2L translations which dominate the performance of FMM.

3.4 Crack problems for three-dimensional elastostatics with Galerkin's method

In this section we discuss an application of the Fast Multipole Galerkin Boundary Integral Equation Method (FM-GBIEM) to crack problems for three-dimensional elastostatics. Applications of FMM to GBIEM are found in Miyakoshi et al. [60] for two-dimensional Laplace's equation and Coifman et al. [12] and Geng et al. [29] for three-dimensional electromagnetic scattering. In application of FMM to GBIEM we have modified the fast multipole algorithm (details of the modification are given in 3.4.3). This modification is significant to implement FM-GBIEM. In order to discretise the variational boundary integral equation we use Galerkin's method and piecewise linear shape functions.

The material in this section is from Yoshida et al. [87].

3.4.1 Variational Boundary Integral Equation

Multiplying (3.46) by a test function $\psi(\mathbf{x})$ which satisfies the following condition:

$$\psi(\mathbf{x}) = 0 \quad \text{on } \partial S$$

and then integrating the resulting expressions on S , one obtains

$$\int_S \psi_a(\mathbf{x}) t_a^\infty(\mathbf{x}) dS_x = - \int_S \psi_a(\mathbf{x}) \oint_S n_b(\mathbf{x}) C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) C_{cdjl} n_c(\mathbf{y}) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) dS_y dS_x. \quad (3.100)$$

The non-regularised variational equation in (3.100) is used as the basis for the Galerkin BIEM.

Note that an arbitrary equilibrated stress field possesses an expression in terms of a stress function. Specifically, the "stress" computed from the fundamental solution can be expressed in terms of the stress function $\Phi_{pqrs}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})$ as (See Nishimura and Kobayashi [63])

$$C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) C_{cdjl} = e_{aip} e_{bjq} e_{ckr} e_{dls} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Phi_{pqrs}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}), \quad (3.101)$$

where e_{ijk} is the permutation symbol and the function $\Phi_{pqrs}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})$ is given by

$$\Phi_{pqrs}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) = \frac{\mu}{8\pi(\lambda + 2\mu)} (2\lambda \delta_{pq} \delta_{rs} + (\lambda + 2\mu)(\delta_{pr} \delta_{qs} + \delta_{ps} \delta_{qr})) |\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|. \quad (3.102)$$

With (3.100) and (3.101), one derives the following variational equation given by (See Appendix L.3)

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_S \psi_a(\mathbf{x}) t_a^\infty(\mathbf{x}) dS_x \\ &= - \int_S n_b(\mathbf{x}) e_{bjq} \frac{\partial \psi_a(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_j} \int_S e_{aip} e_{dls} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Phi_{pqrs}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) n_c(\mathbf{y}) e_{ckr} \frac{\partial \phi_d(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_k} dS_y dS_x. \end{aligned} \quad (3.103)$$

The variational equation in (3.103) has been considered useful in the standard Galerkin BIEM since the kernel function is regularised to an integrable one. In the present investigation with FMM, however, the variational equation in (3.100) is more useful. It is because we are interested in applying FMM in evaluating contributions to the integrals in (3.100) or (3.103) from distant \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} , and because the kernel function in (3.100) decays more quickly than that in (3.103) as $|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}| \rightarrow \infty$. Actually, FMM formulations with regularised integral equations have been tested in section 3.3 with collocation and were shown to introduce more moments than formulations without regularisation. Also, the numerical

experiments in section 3.3 showed that the FMM with regularised integral equations is slower than that without regularisation. Notice, however, that the following identity holds for arbitrary smooth functions ψ and ϕ having supports within S :

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_S \psi_a(\mathbf{x}) \int_S n_b(\mathbf{x}) C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) C_{cdjl} n_c(\mathbf{y}) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) dS_y dS_x \\ &= \int_S n_b(\mathbf{x}) e_{bjq} \frac{\partial \psi_a(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_j} \int_S e_{aip} e_{dls} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Phi_{pqrs}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) n_c(\mathbf{y}) e_{ckr} \frac{\partial \phi_d(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_k} dS_y dS_x. \end{aligned} \quad (3.104)$$

We shall use the regularised expression on the right-hand side of (3.104) in an auxiliary manner to compute the integral on the left-hand side of (3.104) with ψ_a and ϕ_a , respectively, taken as one of the basis functions (sometimes referred to as global shape functions) for the crack opening displacement. This calculation will be needed in the 5th step of the FMM algorithm in 3.4.3 when the supports of ψ_a and ϕ_a are not separated sufficiently.

3.4.2 FM-GBIEM

This section prepares formulae needed for FM-GBIEM in elastostatics.

We now compute a part of the double integral in the right-hand side of (3.100). Namely, we consider the contribution to this integral from $(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \in S_x \times S_y$, where S_x and S_y are disjoint parts of S . Using (3.49) and taking the origin O near S_y , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & - \int_{S_x} \psi_a(\mathbf{x}) \int_{S_y} n_b(\mathbf{x}) C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) C_{cdjl} n_c(\mathbf{y}) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) dS_y dS_x \\ &= - \frac{1}{8\pi\mu} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \left(\int_{S_x} \psi_a(\mathbf{x}) n_b(\mathbf{x}) C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \overline{F_{ij,n,m}^S(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})} M_{j,n,m}^1(O) dS_x \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{S_x} \psi_a(\mathbf{x}) n_b(\mathbf{x}) C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \overline{G_{i,n,m}^S(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})} M_{n,m}^2(O) dS_x \right), \end{aligned} \quad (3.105)$$

where we have assumed that the inequality $|\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}| > |\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}|$ ($\mathbf{x} \in S_x$, $\mathbf{y} \in S_y$) holds. Notice that the multipole moments $M_{j,n,m}^1(O)$ and $M_{n,m}^2(O)$ are identical with (3.53) and (3.54) and M2M translation formulae are given by (3.57) and (3.58).

With (3.105) the evaluation of the left-hand side of (3.100) is made efficient since the multipole moments are common to many evaluation points \mathbf{x} and can be reused. This efficiency is further enhanced by using the local expansion as

$$\begin{aligned} & - \int_{S_x} \psi_a(\mathbf{x}) \int_{S_y} n_b(\mathbf{x}) C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) C_{cdjl} n_c(\mathbf{y}) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) dS_y dS_x \\ &= - \frac{1}{8\pi\mu} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \left(\int_{S_x} \psi_a(\mathbf{x}) n_b(\mathbf{x}) C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} F_{ij,n,m}^R(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) L_{j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0) dS_x \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{S_x} \psi_a(\mathbf{x}) n_b(\mathbf{x}) C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} G_{i,n,m}^R(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) L_{n,m}^2(\mathbf{x}_0) dS_x \right), \end{aligned} \quad (3.106)$$

where we have assumed that the inequality $|\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0}| > |\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}|$ ($\mathbf{x} \in S_x$) holds. Notice that the coefficients of the local expansion $L_{j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0)$ and $L_{n,m}^2(\mathbf{x}_0)$ are the same as (3.60) and (3.61) and L2L translation formulae are given by (3.64) and (3.65).

One may be interested in obtaining stress and displacement distributions within the domain $D = R^3 \setminus \overline{S}$ after the crack opening displacements are computed. In the rest of this section we shall prepare formulae needed for the fast computation of the stress components with the help of FMM. One may similarly compute displacements, but the detail is omitted here.

It is immediate to obtain the following integral representation for the stress from (3.44):

$$\sigma_{ab}(\mathbf{x}) = \sigma_{ab}^{\infty}(\mathbf{x}) + \int_S C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) C_{cdjl} n_c(\mathbf{y}) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) dS_y, \quad \mathbf{x} \in R^3 \setminus \overline{S} \quad (3.107)$$

where σ_{ab}^{∞} is the stress associated with u_i^{∞} . The integral on the right-hand side of (3.107) is regularised with the help of the stress function in (3.101) as

$$\int_S C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) C_{cdjl} n_c(\mathbf{y}) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) dS_y$$

$$= - \int_S e_{aip} e_{bjq} e_{ckr} e_{dls} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Phi_{pqrs}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) n_c(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial \phi_d(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_k} dS_y, \quad \mathbf{x} \in R^3 \setminus \bar{S}, \quad (3.108)$$

As a matter of fact, (3.108) holds identically for any continuous ϕ_i having support within S . We now compute the contribution to the integral on the right-hand side of (3.107) from S_y , where S_y is a part of S located sufficiently far from the evaluation point \mathbf{x} . Using (3.49), (3.53) and (3.54), we rewrite the integral on the right-hand side of (3.107) as

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{S_y} C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) C_{cdjl} n_c(\mathbf{y}) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &= \frac{1}{8\pi\mu} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \left(C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \overline{F_{ij,n,m}^S(\vec{O}\vec{\mathbf{x}})} M_{j,n,m}^1(O) + C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \overline{G_{i,n,m}^S(\vec{O}\vec{\mathbf{x}})} M_{n,m}^2(O) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (3.109)$$

where we have assumed that the origin is near S_y so that the inequality $|\vec{O}\vec{\mathbf{x}}| > |\vec{O}\vec{\mathbf{y}}|$ ($\mathbf{y} \in S_y$) holds. The local expansion of (3.109) around \mathbf{x}_0 is written in terms of the coefficients of the local expansion in (3.60) and (3.61) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{S_y} C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) C_{cdjl} n_c(\mathbf{y}) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &= \frac{1}{8\pi\mu} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \left(C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} F_{ij,n,m}^R(\vec{\mathbf{x}}_0\vec{\mathbf{x}}) L_{j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0) + C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} G_{i,n,m}^R(\vec{\mathbf{x}}_0\vec{\mathbf{x}}) L_{n,m}^2(\mathbf{x}_0) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (3.110)$$

where we have assumed that the inequality $|\vec{O}\vec{\mathbf{x}}_0| > |\vec{\mathbf{x}}_0\vec{\mathbf{x}}|$ holds.

3.4.3 Algorithm

In FM-GBIEM we shall use a modified version of the original FMM by Greengard [33], the outline of which will be included here in order to explain how the tools prepared so far can be incorporated into the FMM algorithm (See Greengard [33] for further details). We note that this algorithm will be used not only in solving the variational boundary integral equation in (3.100), but also in the computation of quantities such as stresses and displacements in the interior of the domain D .

Algorithm for the discretised BIE

In this section we shall describe our algorithm to compute the integrals in the discretised variational equation in (3.100) efficiently. The method presented here will be used to solve the discretised integral equation for the crack opening displacement in conjunction with certain iterative solvers for matrix equations. Before we start, we have to define some words precisely. Boundary elements refer to small disjoint patches that cover the crack S . Each boundary element has local nodes on its boundary or in its interior. Local shape functions are defined in the interior of each element, and each of these local shape functions is associated with a local node where it takes the value of 1, while at other local nodes it is equal to 0. Some local nodes of different boundary elements may share a global position called a global node. The union of all the local shape functions that takes the value of 1 at a global node is called a basis function, or a global shape function associated with that global node. The combination of such global shape function and the union of the relevant boundary elements are called the global boundary element associated with the global node. We take Gauss points on each global boundary element to compute the outer integral on the right-hand side of (3.100).

We now move on to the description of the algorithm. We assume that the function ϕ_i is known on the crack, and is discretised as

$$\sum_J N^J(\mathbf{x}) \phi_i^J \quad (3.111)$$

where $N^J(\mathbf{x})$ is the basis function associated with the global node x^J and ϕ_i^J is the nodal value of ϕ_i (See Fig.3.27). The global nodes are taken only in the interior of S so that the regularity condition in (3.43) is satisfied. Our objective is to compute a vector whose $(3I + a - 3)$ th components are equal to the right-hand side of (3.100) with ψ_a replaced by N^I .

Figure 3.27: Piecewise linear shape function N^J and global node x^J

Figure 3.28: Global boundary element belongs to a cell or not

Steps 1–2. Same as the steps 1–2 in the algorithm described in chapter 2. In FM-GBIEM a global boundary element is considered to belong to a cell if the associated global node is in a cell (See Fig.3.28).

Step 3. Computation of the multipole moments (Upward)

First compute the multipole moments associated with leaves using (3.53) and (3.54). Here the multipole moments associated with a cell C mean the integrals in (3.53) and (3.54) with O taken as the centroid of C and ϕ_i understood as

$$\sum_{x^I \in C} N^I(\mathbf{x}) \phi_i^I.$$

Now consider a non-leaf cell C of level l . We compute the multipole moments associated with C by adding all the multipole moments of C 's children after shifting the origin from the centroids of C 's children to that of C via (3.57) and (3.58). We repeat this procedure tracing the tree structure of cells obtained in step 2 upward (decreasing l) until we reach level 2 cells.

Step 4. Computation of the coefficients of the local expansion (Downward)

We first compute the coefficients of the local expansion of cells of level 2 according to the definition using (3.60) and (3.61). After that, the coefficients of the local expansion of a level l cell C are computed recursively in 2 steps. Namely, we first add together the contributions of the forms in (3.60) and (3.61) from cells of the level l which are well-separated from C . This is followed by the addition of the coefficients of the local expansion of the parent of C with the origin shifted from the centroid of the parent to that of C via (3.64) or (3.65).

Step 5. Evaluation of the integral in (3.100)

We now compute the right-hand side of (3.100) with the test function ψ_i replaced by a basis function N^I : this integral is denoted by a^I . Let C be a cell of the level l to which x^I belongs, and let C' be a cell of level l adjacent to C . We then compute the following sum if either C or C' is a leaf:

$$\sum_{J:x^J \in C'} \int_S N^J(\mathbf{x}) \oint_S n_b(\mathbf{x}) C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) C_{cdjl} n_c(\mathbf{y}) N^J(\mathbf{y}) dS_y dS_x \phi_d^J. \quad (3.112)$$

This computation is carried out directly with the help of the regularised expression on the right-hand side of (3.104). When C is a leaf, we also compute the right-hand side of (3.106) using the coefficients of the local expansion associated with C for $L_{\cdot,N,M}^{1,2}$ and N^I for ψ_i . The sum of all the terms thus computed as one increases l from 2 to its maximum value is equal to the desired quantity, i.e., a^I .

In the actual computation the 4th and 5th steps are carried out at the same time in a single do loop with respect to l . It is seen that the computational cost for the above algorithm is of the order of N if one truncates the infinite sums in (3.60), etc. at a fixed number P . Notice, however, that the size of the boundary elements has to be fine enough so that the conditions of validity of various expansions such as the one stated after (3.105) are not violated.

3.4.4 Algorithm for computing stress

FMM can be used also in the computation of the stress or displacement within the domain $R^3 \setminus \bar{S}$. The algorithm used to this end is essentially the same as the one presented above, except that two tree structures of cells are used. We here describe necessary modifications to the FMM presented in 3.4.3 in the computation of the stress.

In step 2, the cell of the level 0 is taken as a cube which contains all the global boundary elements and all the points of observation where the stresses are computed. From this cell, we construct two tree structures of cells, i.e. the boundary element tree and observation point tree. We construct the former (latter) by subdividing parent cells into 8 sub cubes and by retaining those to which some boundary elements (observation points) belong. The boundary element tree has already been used in the FMM for the discretised BIE in 3.4.3. In the stress computation we use (3.53)–(3.58) to obtain the multipole moments in cells in the boundary element tree, and use (3.60)–(3.65) to calculate the coefficients of local expansion at the centroids of cells in the observation point tree. Hence the cells in step 3 are now understood to be from the boundary element tree, while cells denoted by C (C') in steps 4 and 5 are taken from the observation point tree (boundary element tree). The rest of the calculation proceeds in an obvious manner as one replaces (3.100), (3.104), (3.106), etc. by (3.107), (3.108), (3.110), etc., respectively, in the algorithm described in 3.4.3.

3.4.5 Numerical examples

The proposed techniques have been implemented in Fortran 77, and tested on a computer having a DEC Alpha 21164(600 MHz) chip as the CPU.

In FMM, we truncate the infinite series in (3.105), (3.106), (3.109) and (3.110) taking 10 terms, or 264 moments, into consideration. Also, we set the maximum number of boundary elements in a leaf to be 60, since this number turned out to be the most efficient choice in a separate parameter study. As

regards the integration, we calculate the inner integrals on the right-hand side of (3.104) and those on the right-hand side of (3.108) analytically when direct evaluation is needed. The outer integrals in the right-hand side of (3.104) and the integrals in (3.53), (3.54) and (3.106) are computed numerically with Gaussian quadrature. Notice that the definition of the belonging of a global boundary element to a cell in the second step in 3.4.3 makes this calculation easy. Indeed this definition guarantees that a global boundary element is never divided between two or more cells. Because of this we never have to deal with discontinuities of the shape functions in the direct evaluation of the integrals in (3.112), thus making the use of (3.104) possible. If a global boundary element with a basis function $N^J(\mathbf{x})$ had been divided between adjacent cells C and C' in (3.112), however, one would have had to deal with an integral of the form

$$\int_{S \cap C} N^J(\mathbf{x}) \int_{S \cap C'} n_b(\mathbf{x}) C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) C_{cdjln_c}(\mathbf{y}) N^J(\mathbf{y}) dS_y dS_x \phi_d^J.$$

which is actually divergent since the inner integral includes a singularity proportional to the reciprocal of the distance from the line of discontinuity of $N^J(\mathbf{x})$.

In the present implementation of the FM-GBIEM the basis functions are chosen to be piecewise linear. With this choice the square root behaviour of the crack opening displacement near the tip is not taken into account. There would be, however, no essential difficulty in including this effect into the analysis.

To solve the discretised integral equation we use the preconditioned GMRES. As the preconditioner, we use the block diagonal matrix corresponding to the leaves, following the technique proposed by Nishida and Hayami [62]. In GMRES we terminate the iteration when the relative error is less than 10^{-5} . In all the examples to follow this convergence condition was met after less than 20 iterations.

One penny-shaped crack

To begin with we consider a simple problem where the exact solution is available. Namely, we consider a penny-shaped crack having the radius of a_0 opened by a uniform remote normal tension having the magnitude of p_0 . Taking the 3rd axis of a Cartesian coordinate system into the direction of the unit normal vector $\mathbf{n} = (0, 0, 1)$ on S , we write the boundary condition in the following form: $\mathbf{t}^\infty = (0, 0, p_0)$ on S . The Lamé constants are chosen to be $\lambda = \mu$, hence Poisson's ratio is $1/4$.

Fig.3.29 shows the 471 DOF mesh and the bird's-eye view of the non-dimensional crack opening displacement $\mu\phi_3/(a_0p_0)$ obtained with FM-GBIEM using this mesh. Fig.3.30 shows the crack opening displacement vs the distance from the centre of the crack. In this figure the line and symbols marked "galerkin", "collocation" and "analytic" indicate numerical results obtained with FM-GBIEM, those obtained with FM-BIEM with collocation and the analytic solution (Green and Zerna [32]), respectively. The BIE results are obtained with the mesh shown in Fig.3.29, and the basis functions are piecewise linear in FM-GBIEM and piecewise constant in collocation. This figure shows the high accuracy of the FM-GBIEM. Also noteworthy is the poor quality of the collocation results. This inaccuracy is due to the combination of the collocation and the piecewise constant basis functions, but not to FMM. This is because the collocation FMM results were essentially identical with those of the conventional collocation BIEM obtained with the same mesh and basis functions. Fig.3.31 compares the normal stress (σ_{33}) near the crack tip obtained with FM-GBIEM using a 471 DOF mesh, the same stress obtained with a 981 DOF mesh, and the analytical solution. Here again the agreement is satisfactory. We expect further improvement of the results near the tip with basis functions having the square root behaviour since this introduces the correct singularity in the stress at the tip while the piecewise linear basis function leads to a weaker logarithmic singularity. Fig.3.32 plots the total CPU time (sec) vs the number of unknowns N . In Fig.3.32 the solid (broken) line marked T_{fmm} (T_{dir}) indicates the CPU time required with FM-GBIEM (conventional GBIEM). We use Crout's method as the solver for conventional GBIEM. We did not compare FM-GBIEM and conventional collocation BIEM results in this figure because the conventional collocation BIEM will not work with piecewise linear base functions since the C^1 continuity of the base function does not hold, and because the accuracies of the Galerkin and collocation BIEMs are not identical with the same number of unknowns. This figure shows that FM-GBIEM is faster than the conventional GBIEM when N is more than about 1200. Fig.3.33 shows the CPU time per iteration in GMRES vs N . The slope of this graph is seen to approach the theoretical value of 1 as N increases.

Many penny-shaped cracks

We now consider a multi-crack problem. Namely, we compute crack opening displacements and the stresses within the body having many cracks in its interior. Analyses of this type have applications in the fracture mechanics of rock-like materials.

Specifically, we consider an infinite elastic body which contains an array of $8 \times 8 \times 8 (=512)$ penny-shaped cracks of the same radius a_0 . The centres of these cracks are located regularly at the interval of $4a_0$ in all the coordinate directions. The directions of these cracks are taken random. The whole system is subjected to a uniform remote tension of the magnitude p_0 . Hence the function $\mathbf{t}^\infty(\mathbf{x})$ which appears in (3.100) is written as $\mathbf{t}^\infty(\mathbf{x}) = \boldsymbol{\sigma}^\infty(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{n}(\mathbf{x})$ where

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^\infty(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & p_0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3.113)$$

Again, the material constants are chosen as $\lambda = \mu$.

Fig.3.34 shows the mesh for 512 cracks (total DOF=241,152), where each crack is discretised with the 471 DOF mesh shown in Fig.3.29. In Fig.3.35 we display the computed crack opening displacements by superposing the non-dimensional crack opening displacement $\mu\phi/(a_0p_0)$ on the non-dimensional position vector \mathbf{x}/a_0 . The required CPU time for computing the crack opening displacements was 20,854 (sec), and the number of iterations needed for the convergence of GMRES was 10. We next show the results of the stress computation. We take a surface Π , shown in Fig.3.36, which has no intersection with the cracks. Observation points are taken to be the 200×200 lattice points located on Π at an equal interval. Fig.3.37 shows the distribution of the second invariant of the stress deviator defined by

$$J_2 = \frac{1}{2}\sigma'_{ij}\sigma'_{ij}, \quad \sigma'_{ij} = \sigma_{ij} - \frac{1}{3}\delta_{ij}\sigma_{kk}$$

computed on these observation points. The additional CPU time required for the calculation of stress components at these 40,000 points was 477 (sec) after the computation of the crack opening displacements. Finally, Fig.3.38 shows the crack opening displacements for a case similar to the one in Fig.3.35 except that the radius of each crack is also varied randomly between $a_0/2$ and a_0 . The CPU time was almost the same as in the constant radius case.

Figure 3.29: Mesh and crack opening displacement

Figure 3.30: Crack opening displacement vs distance from the centre of the crack

Figure 3.31: Stress σ_{33} vs distance from the crack tip

Figure 3.32: CPU time (sec) vs number of unknowns

Figure 3.33: CPU time (sec) per iteration vs number of unknowns

Figure 3.34: Mesh for 512 cracks (DOF=241,152)

Figure 3.35: Crack opening displacements of 512 cracks (DOF=241,152)

Figure 3.36: Surface Π

Figure 3.37: J_2 on surface Π

Figure 3.38: Crack opening displacements of 512 cracks with random radii (DOF=241,152).

3.5 Three-dimensional scattering of scalar waves by cracks

In this section we discuss an application of FM-BIEM to three-dimensional scattering of scalar waves by cracks. Acoustic and electromagnetic scattering problems are interesting subjects in engineering and therefore many researchers have investigated such problems using FMM. However, most of them use Rokhlin's diagonal form which have numerical instabilities in dealing with static problems and low frequency problems. If one implements the original FMM for scattering problems to avoid these problems one uses the Wigner-3j symbols for the FMM formulation. In literature, however, numerical implementations of FMM with the Wigner-3j symbols are scarcely found because of the complexity for treatment. Therefore, we investigate the use of Wigner-3j symbols in the implementation of the original FMM for low frequency problems and carry out numerical experiments. In order to discretise the hypersingular BIE we use collocation method and piecewise constant shape functions. In this section we assume that the wave field is time-harmonic and the time factor is $e^{-i\omega t}$.

The material in this section is from Yoshida et al. [86]

3.5.1 Integral equation

Our problem is to find a solution u of Helmholtz's equation

$$(\Delta + k^2) u(\mathbf{x}) = 0 \quad \text{in } R^3 \setminus \bar{S},$$

subject to the boundary condition

$$\frac{\partial u^\pm(\mathbf{x})}{\partial n} = 0 \quad \text{on } S, \quad (3.114)$$

regularity condition

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}) := \mathbf{u}^+(\mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{u}^-(\mathbf{x}) = 0 \quad \text{on } \partial S, \quad (3.115)$$

and the radiation condition (Sommerfeld [75]) for $u(\mathbf{x}) - u_I(\mathbf{x})$, where Δ , k , u , ϕ and u_I indicate the Laplacian operator, the wave number, the total wave field, the discontinuity of u on S and the incident field.

The solution $u(\mathbf{x})$ to this problem has an integral representation given by

$$u(\mathbf{x}) = u_I(\mathbf{x}) + \int_S \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial n_y} \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y, \quad \mathbf{x} \in R^3 \setminus \bar{S}, \quad (3.116)$$

where $G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})$ is the fundamental solution of Helmholtz's equation given by

$$G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) = \frac{e^{ikR}}{4\pi R}, \quad R = |\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|. \quad (3.117)$$

Using (3.114) and (3.116), one obtains the hypersingular integral equation:

$$-\frac{\partial u_I}{\partial n_x}(\mathbf{x}) = \oint_S \frac{\partial^2 G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial n_x \partial n_y} \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y, \quad \mathbf{x} \in S, \quad (3.118)$$

where \oint stands for the finite part of a divergent integral. The hypersingular integral equation (3.118) can be regularised as (See Appendix L.4)

$$-\frac{\partial u_I}{\partial n_x}(\mathbf{x}) = -n_j(\mathbf{x}) e_{jpl} \oint_S \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial y_p} n_i(\mathbf{y}) e_{iql} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y_q}(\mathbf{y}) dS_y + k^2 \int_S n_j(\mathbf{x}) n_j(\mathbf{y}) G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y. \quad (3.119)$$

where \oint stands for the Cauchy principal value of a singular integral. This regularised integral equation (3.119) is utilised for the direct computation in FM-BIEM.

3.5.2 FM-BIEM

Using Gegenbauer's addition theorem (See [2]), we can expand the fundamental solution in (3.117) into the following series

$$\frac{e^{ikR}}{4\pi R} = \frac{ik}{4\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n (2n+1) \overline{\mathcal{I}}_n^m(k, \overrightarrow{\mathcal{O}\mathbf{y}}) \mathcal{O}_n^m(k, \overrightarrow{\mathcal{O}\mathbf{x}}), \quad |\overrightarrow{\mathcal{O}\mathbf{x}}| > |\overrightarrow{\mathcal{O}\mathbf{y}}|, \quad (3.120)$$

where $R = |\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|$, $\bar{\cdot}$ denotes the complex conjugate and the functions $\mathcal{O}_n^m(k, \overrightarrow{\mathcal{O}\mathbf{x}})$ and $\overline{\mathcal{I}}_n^m(k, \overrightarrow{\mathcal{O}\mathbf{x}})$ are defined as

$$\mathcal{O}_n^m(k, \overrightarrow{\mathcal{O}\mathbf{x}}) = h_n^{(1)}(k|\overrightarrow{\mathcal{O}\mathbf{x}}|) Y_n^m(\widehat{\mathcal{O}\mathbf{x}}), \quad (3.121)$$

$$\overline{\mathcal{I}}_n^m(k, \overrightarrow{\mathcal{O}\mathbf{x}}) = j_n(k|\overrightarrow{\mathcal{O}\mathbf{x}}|) Y_n^m(\widehat{\mathcal{O}\mathbf{x}}). \quad (3.122)$$

In these formulae $j_n(k|\overrightarrow{\mathcal{O}\mathbf{x}}|)$ and $h_n^{(1)}(k|\overrightarrow{\mathcal{O}\mathbf{x}}|)$ are the spherical Bessel function and the spherical Hankel function of the first kind, respectively, $\widehat{\mathcal{O}\mathbf{x}}$ indicates the unit vector given by $\overrightarrow{\mathcal{O}\mathbf{x}}/|\overrightarrow{\mathcal{O}\mathbf{x}}|$ and the spherical harmonics $Y_n^m(\widehat{\mathcal{O}\mathbf{x}})$ is defined as

$$Y_n^m(\widehat{\mathcal{O}\mathbf{x}}) = \sqrt{\frac{(n-m)!}{(n+m)!}} P_n^m(\cos \theta) e^{im\phi}.$$

The functions \mathcal{O}_n^m and $\overline{\mathcal{I}}_n^m$ have the following properties (See Epton and Dembart [17]):

$$\overline{\mathcal{I}}_n^m(k, \overrightarrow{\mathcal{O}\mathbf{y}}) = \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \sum_{\substack{l=|n-n'| \\ n'+n-l:\text{even}}}^{n+n'} (2n'+1)(-1)^{m'} W_{n,n',m,m',l} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_{n'}^{m'}(k, \overrightarrow{\mathcal{O}\mathbf{y}}) \mathcal{I}_l^{-m-m'}(k, \overrightarrow{\mathcal{O}\mathbf{O}}), \quad (3.123)$$

$$\mathcal{O}_n^m(k, \overrightarrow{\mathcal{O}\mathbf{x}}) = \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \sum_{\substack{l=|n-n'| \\ n'+n-l:\text{even}}}^{n+n'} (2n'+1)(-1)^{m+n'} W_{n,n',m,m',l} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_{n'}^{m'}(k, \overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}\mathbf{x}_0}) \mathcal{O}_l^{m+m'}(k, \overrightarrow{\mathcal{O}\mathbf{x}_0}), \quad |\overrightarrow{\mathcal{O}\mathbf{x}_0}| > |\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}\mathbf{x}_0}|, \quad (3.124)$$

where $W_{n,n',m,m',l}$ is given by

$$W_{n,n',m,m',l} = (2l+1) i^{n'-n+l} \begin{pmatrix} n & n' & l \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} n & n' & l \\ m & m' & -m-m' \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3.125)$$

In (3.125) $\begin{pmatrix} \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \end{pmatrix}$ stands for the Wigner-3j symbol (See Messiah [59]). The explicit form of the Wigner-3j symbol is expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{pmatrix} j_1 & j_2 & j_3 \\ m_1 & m_2 & m_3 \end{pmatrix} &= \left[\frac{(j_1+j_2-j_3)!(j_1-j_2+j_3)!(-j_1+j_2+j_3)!}{(j_1+j_2+j_3+1)!} \right]^{1/2} \\ &\times [(j_1+m_1)!(j_1-m_1)!(j_2+m_2)!(j_2-m_2)!(j_3+m_3)!(j_3-m_3)!]^{1/2} \\ &\times \sum_i \frac{(-1)^{i+j_1-j_2-m_3}}{i!(j_1+j_2-j_3-i)!(j_1-m_1-i)!(j_2+m_2-i)!(j_3-j_2+m_1+i)!(j_3-j_1-m_2+i)!}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.126)$$

The summation is over such i that the numbers in the parentheses in the denominator are all non-negative. The recurrence formula for the Wigner-3j symbol are found in Schulten and Gordon [74]. Their implementation is available from Netlib (<http://www.netlib.org/>).

In this section we use the hypersingular integral equation (3.118) for the formulation. We now compute the integral on the right-hand side of (3.118) over a subset of S denoted by S_y for \mathbf{x} which is away from S_y . Using (3.120), we obtain

$$\int_{S_y} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial n_x \partial n_y} \frac{e^{ikR}}{4\pi R} \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y = \frac{ik}{4\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n (2n+1) \frac{\partial}{\partial n_x} \mathcal{O}_n^m(k, \overrightarrow{\mathcal{O}\mathbf{x}}) M_n^m(k, \mathcal{O}), \quad (3.127)$$

where $R = |\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|$ and $M_n^m(k, O)$ is the multipole moment centred at O defined as

$$M_n^m(k, O) = \int_{S_y} \frac{\partial}{\partial n_y} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_n^m(k, \overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y. \quad (3.128)$$

In (3.127) we have assumed that the inequality $|\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}| > |\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}|$ ($\mathbf{y} \in S_y$) holds.

The multipole moments are translated according to the following formulae as the centre of the multipole expansion is shifted from O to O' :

$$M_n^m(k, O') = \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \sum_{\substack{l=|n-n'| \\ n'+n-l:\text{even}}}^{n+n'} (2n'+1)(-1)^{m'} W_{n,n',m',l} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_l^{-m-m'}(k, \overrightarrow{O'\overrightarrow{O}}) M_{n'}^{-m'}(k, O) \quad (3.129)$$

where we have used (3.123) (See Appendix I.1). In the evaluation of the integral on the right-hand side of (3.118) one can use not only the multipole moments but also the coefficients of local expansion in the following manner:

$$\int_{S_y} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial n_x \partial n_y} \frac{e^{ikR}}{4\pi R} \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y = \frac{ik}{4\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n (2n+1) \frac{\partial}{\partial n_x} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_n^m(k, \overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) L_n^m(k, \mathbf{x}_0), \quad (3.130)$$

where $R = |\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|$, $L_n^m(k, \mathbf{x}_0)$ is expressed with $M_n^m(k, O)$ by (See Appendix I.2)

$$L_n^m(k, \mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \sum_{\substack{l=|n-n'| \\ n'+n-l:\text{even}}}^{n+n'} (2n'+1) W_{n',n,m',l} \tilde{\mathcal{O}}_l^{-m-m'}(k, \overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0}) M_{n'}^{m'}(k, O), \quad (3.131)$$

and $\tilde{\mathcal{O}}_n^m$ is defined as

$$\tilde{\mathcal{O}}_n^m(k, \overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) = h_n^{(1)}(k|\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}|) \overline{Y}_n^m(\widehat{O\mathbf{x}}).$$

In the derivation of (3.131) we have used (3.124) and have assumed that the inequality $|\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0}| > |\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}|$ holds.

The coefficients of the local expansion are translated according to the following formulae as the centre of the local expansion is shifted from \mathbf{x}_0 to \mathbf{x}_1 :

$$L_n^m(k, \mathbf{x}_1) = \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \sum_{\substack{l=|n-n'| \\ n'+n-l:\text{even}}}^{n+n'} (2n'+1)(-1)^m W_{n',n,m',-m,l} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_l^{m-m'}(k, \overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}_1}) L_{n'}^{m'}(k, \mathbf{x}_0), \quad (3.132)$$

where we have used (3.123) (See Appendix I.3).

Notice that in this formulation the multipole moment and the coefficient do not have the properties like those of (3.23) and (3.27) in Laplace's equation because ϕ is complex-valued. Therefore, we can not save the memory with the use of symmetries.

We have thus prepared all the formulae needed for FM-BIEM. Using formulae presented above and the algorithm described in chapter 2, one can implement FM-BIEM.

3.5.3 Numerical procedures

Truncation of the infinite series

In FM-BIEM, we follow the techniques proposed by Song et al. [76] to truncate the infinite series taking P terms, where

$$P(kR) = kR + 5 \ln(\pi + kR), \quad (3.133)$$

k is the wave number and R is the diameter of a sphere which circumscribes a cell. One has $R = \sqrt{3}D$, where D is the edge length of a cell. This means that we must change P as the level changes. Also, P increases as the size of a cell or the wave number becomes large. This property leads to a lot of computational cost when one deals with high frequency problems or large-scale problems. In order to overcome this problem some techniques are proposed by several authors (e.g. Rokhlin et al. [71] or Greengard et al. [34]). However, we do not use these techniques in this thesis since we are interested in low frequency problems.

Figure 3.39: kR vs P

Direct computation

Discretising the regularised integral equation (3.119) with piecewise constant shape functions, one obtains

$$-\frac{\partial u_I}{\partial n_x}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_J \int_{\partial S_J} n_j(\mathbf{x}) e_{jpl} \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial y_p} dy_l \phi_J + k^2 \sum_J \int_{S_J} n_j(\mathbf{x}) n_j(\mathbf{y}) G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) dS_y \phi_J, \quad (3.134)$$

where S_J is a plane element in S_y and ϕ_J represents ϕ on S_J . In (3.134) the right-hand screw convention is applied to the direction of the integration along ∂S_J . In the evaluation of the integral in (3.134) we divide (3.117) into the static part (the fundamental solution of three-dimensional Laplace's equation) and the residual part as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) &= G^S(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) + G^R(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) \\ &= \frac{1}{4\pi R} + \frac{2i \sin(kR/2) e^{ikR/2}}{4\pi R}, \quad R = |\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|. \end{aligned}$$

When kR is small we use the following series for the computation of $G^R(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})$

$$G^R(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(ik)^n R^{n-1}}{n!}$$

We compute the integrals related to the static part $G^S(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})$ analytically and the rest numerically with Gaussian quadrature.

Computation of Y_n^m

Noting the following identity

$$Y_n^m(\widehat{O\mathbf{x}}) = \sqrt{(n-m)!(n+m)!} R_{n,m}(\widehat{O\mathbf{x}}),$$

we compute $Y_{n,m}$ and their derivatives using recurrence formulae in Appendix C and relations in Appendix D.

Algorithm

We briefly describe the usage of formulae presented here in each step in the algorithm of FM-BIEM (See chapter 2 for more details).

Steps 1–2. Same as the steps 1–2 in the algorithm described in chapter 2.

Step 3. Computation of the multipole moments:

In this step we use (3.128) for the computation of the multipole moments associated with leaves. Also, we use (3.129) for M2M translations tracing the tree structure of cells upward (decreasing $l(\geq 2)$).

Step 4. Computation of the local expansion:

In this step we use (3.131) for M2L translations and (3.132) for L2L translations tracing the tree structure of cells downward (increasing $l(\geq 2)$).

Step 5. Evaluation of the integral in (3.118):

In this step we use (3.134) for the direct computation and use (3.130) for the evaluation of contributions from the local expansion.

3.5.4 Numerical examples

The proposed techniques have been implemented in Fortran 77, and have been tested on a computer having a DEC Alpha 21164(533 MHz) chip as the CPU (except for the results in Fig.3.49). In FMM, we truncate the infinite series via (3.133). Also, we set the maximum number of boundary elements in a leaf to be 100. The integrals in (3.128) are computed numerically with Gaussian quadrature. In GMRES we terminate the iteration when the relative error is less than 10^{-5} . To solve the resulting matrix equation we use the preconditioned GMRES (The issue of the choice of the preconditioners will be touched upon later).

One penny-shaped crack

To begin with we consider an infinite space which contains one penny-shaped crack having the radius of a_0 and the unit normal vector of $\mathbf{n} = (0, 0, 1)$. We compute the crack opening displacement subject to a plane wave of normal incidence. The incident wave field u_I is given by

$$u_I(\mathbf{x}) = u_0 e^{ikz}, \quad u_0 : \text{const.}$$

In this example we call the side where the incident wave reaches directly the “bright side (-)” and the

Figure 3.40: Scattering problem

other side the “shadow side (+)” (See Fig.3.40). This problem is solved with the conventional BIEM and FM-BIEM when $ka_0 = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$. In GMRES we use the block diagonal matrix corresponding to the

leaves as the preconditioner according to Nishida and Hayami [62]. Fig.3.41 plots the total CPU time (sec) vs the number of unknowns. In Fig.3.41 the lines marked “Tdir_ka=5” and “Tfmm_ka=1,2,3,4,5” indicate the CPU time required with the conventional BIEM when $ka_0 = 5$ and FM-BIEM when $ka_0 = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$, respectively. Because the computational times required with the conventional BIEM are almost identical when $ka_0 = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$ we plot only the “Tdir_ka=5” result in Fig.3.41. This figure shows that the FM-BIEM is faster than the conventional BIEM when the number of unknowns is larger than several thousands. Fig.3.42 shows the CPU time per iteration. In Fig.3.42 the lines marked “Tfmm_per_itr_ka=1,2,3,4,5” show the CPU time per iteration when $ka_0 = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$. Fig.3.43, Fig.3.45 and Fig.3.47 show the crack opening displacement $|\phi|/u_0$ when $ka_0 = 1, 2, 3$. In these figures “conv” and “fmm” indicate the numerical solutions with the conventional BIEM and FM-BIEM, respectively. Fig.3.44, Fig.3.46 and Fig.3.48 show $|u|$ on both sides and the analytical solution (Leitner [53]) when $ka_0 = 1, 2, 3$. In these figures “bside_analy” and “bside_numer” denote the analytical solution and the numerical one on the bright side and “sside_analy” and “sside_numer” denote the analytical solution and the numerical one on the shadow side. In Fig.3.49 the lines marked “Laplace” and “Helmholtz” show the computational times required with FM-BIEM for Laplace’s equation and Helmholtz’s equation ($ka_0 = 1$), respectively. We note that these computational times are obtained on a DEC Alpha 21264(600MHz). This figure shows that the computational time required with Helmholtz’s equation is slower than that required with Laplace’s equation.

Many penny-shaped cracks

We now consider an infinite space which contains an array of $4 \times 4 \times 4 (=64)$ (total DOF=32,256) penny-shaped cracks, each having the same radius a_0 subjected to the same incident wave field ($ka_0 = 1$) as in the previous example. The centroids of these cracks are located regularly with an interval of $4a_0$ in each coordinate direction, but the orientation of each crack is taken random. In GMRES we use the block diagonal matrix corresponding to the cracks as the preconditioner. In Fig.3.50 and Fig.3.51 we have superimposed the real part and the imaginary part of the non-dimensional crack opening displacement $|\phi|/u_0$ plotted in the normal direction on the non-dimensional mesh \mathbf{x}/a_0 , respectively. The required CPU time with FM-BIEM is 8706(sec).

Figure 3.41: Total CPU time (sec) ($ka_0 = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$)

Figure 3.42: CPU time per iteration (sec) ($ka_0 = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$)

Figure 3.43: Crack opening displacement $|\phi|/u_0$ ($ka_0 = 1$)

Figure 3.44: Displacement $|u|/u_0$ at both sides ($ka_0 = 1$)

Figure 3.45: Crack opening displacement $|\phi|/u_0$ ($ka_0 = 2$)

Figure 3.46: Displacement $|u|/u_0$ at both sides ($ka_0 = 2$)

Figure 3.47: Crack opening displacement $|\phi|/u_0$ ($ka_0 = 3$)

Figure 3.48: Displacement $|u|/u_0$ at both sides ($ka_0 = 3$)

Figure 3.49: Comparison of computational times for Laplace's equation and Helmholtz's equation ($ka_0=1$)

Figure 3.50: Real part of crack opening displacement (DOF=32,256, $ka_0 = 1$)

Figure 3.51: Imaginary part of crack opening displacement (DOF=32,256, $ka_0 = 1$)

3.5.5 Relation between formulations in Laplace's equation and Helmholtz's equation

We can consider Laplace's equation to be the special case Helmholtz's equation as k tends to 0. Therefore one expects that the FMM formulation for Laplace's equation is obtained as the limit of $k \rightarrow 0$ in the FMM formulation for Helmholtz's equation. However, the formulation obtained above does not allow such operation in the form as it is. It is because the behaviours of $j_n(k|\overrightarrow{Ox}|)$ and $h_n(k|\overrightarrow{Ox}|)$ near $k = 0$ are $O(k^{-n-1})$ and $O(k^n)$ and, hence,

$$\begin{aligned}\lim_{k \rightarrow 0} \mathcal{I}_n^m(k, \overrightarrow{Ox}) &= 0 \\ \lim_{k \rightarrow 0} \mathcal{O}_n^m(k, \overrightarrow{Ox}) &= \infty\end{aligned}$$

In order to obtain a formulation allowing an obvious transition between these governing equations we need some modifications to cancel these behaviours.

Noting the power series of $j_n(k|\overrightarrow{Oy}|)$ and $h_n(k|\overrightarrow{Ox}|)$, we obtain the following formulation

$$\frac{e^{ikR}}{4\pi R} = \frac{1}{4\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \widehat{\mathcal{I}}_n^m(k, \overrightarrow{Oy}) \hat{\mathcal{O}}_n^m(k, \overrightarrow{Ox}) \quad (3.135)$$

where $\widehat{\mathcal{I}}_n^m(k, \overrightarrow{Oy})$ and $\hat{\mathcal{O}}_n^m(k, \overrightarrow{Ox})$ are defined as

$$\begin{aligned}\widehat{\mathcal{I}}_n^m(k, \overrightarrow{Oy}) &= \frac{(2n+1)! j_n(k|\overrightarrow{Oy}|)}{2^{2n} n! (k|\overrightarrow{Oy}|)^n} R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{Oy}), \\ \hat{\mathcal{O}}_n^m(k, \overrightarrow{Ox}) &= i \frac{2^n n!}{(2n)!} (k|\overrightarrow{Ox}|)^{n+1} h_n(k|\overrightarrow{Ox}|) S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{Ox}).\end{aligned}$$

Since

$$\begin{aligned}\lim_{k \rightarrow 0} \widehat{\mathcal{I}}_n^m(k, \overrightarrow{Oy}) &= R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{Oy}), \\ \lim_{k \rightarrow 0} \hat{\mathcal{O}}_n^m(k, \overrightarrow{Ox}) &= S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{Ox}),\end{aligned}$$

the expression in (3.135) is seen to approach (3.120) as $k \rightarrow 0$.

3.6 Three-dimensional scattering of elastic waves by a crack

In this section we discuss an application of FM-BIEM to three-dimensional scattering of elastic waves by a crack. As far as we know, an application of FMM to three-dimensional elastodynamics is found only in Fujiwara [22]. Fujiwara uses Rokhlin's diagonal form and his FMM formulation requires 6 moments for the double-layer potential. On the other hand, we use Wigner 3-j symbols for the FMM formulation because we are interested in low frequency problems and in our formulation the number of the multipole moments is 4. In order to discretise the hypersingular BIE we use collocation method and piecewise constant shape functions. In this section we deal with low frequency problems assuming that the wave field is time-harmonic and that the time factor is $e^{-i\omega t}$.

This material in this section is from Yoshida et al. [85]

3.6.1 Integral equation

Our problem is to find a solution \mathbf{u} of the equation of three-dimensional elastodynamics

$$C_{ijkl}u_{k,lj}(\mathbf{x}) + \rho\omega^2 u_i(\mathbf{x}) = 0 \quad \text{in } R^3 \setminus \bar{S},$$

subject to the boundary condition

$$t_i^\pm(\mathbf{x}) := C_{ijkl}u_{k,l}^\pm(\mathbf{x})n_j(\mathbf{x}) = 0 \quad \text{on } S, \quad (3.136)$$

regularity condition

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}) := \mathbf{u}^+(\mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{u}^-(\mathbf{x}) = 0 \quad \text{on } \partial S, \quad (3.137)$$

and the radiation condition for $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{u}^I(\mathbf{x})$ (See Kupradze [51]), where \mathbf{u} , C_{ijkl} , \mathbf{t} , \mathbf{u}^I and ϕ stand for the displacement, elasticity tensor, traction vector, an incident wave and the crack opening displacement, respectively.

The solution \mathbf{u} to this problem has an integral representation given by

$$u_i(\mathbf{x}) = u_i^I(\mathbf{x}) + \int_S C_{jknlp} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_n} \Gamma_{ip}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) n_k(\mathbf{y}) \phi_j(\mathbf{y}) dS_y, \quad \mathbf{x} \in R^3 \setminus \bar{S}, \quad (3.138)$$

where $\Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})$ is the fundamental solution of the equation of elastodynamics in the frequency domain expressed as

$$\Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) = \frac{1}{4\pi\mu} \left(\frac{e^{ik_T R}}{R} \delta_{ij} + \frac{1}{k_T^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y_i \partial y_j} \left(\frac{e^{ik_T R}}{R} - \frac{e^{ik_L R}}{R} \right) \right), \quad R = |\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}| \quad (3.139)$$

and k_T and k_L are the transverse wave number and the longitudinal wave number given by

$$k_T = \sqrt{\frac{\rho}{\mu}}\omega, \quad k_L = \sqrt{\frac{\rho}{\lambda + 2\mu}}\omega.$$

Using (3.136) and (3.138), one obtains the following hypersingular integral equation given by

$$t_a^I(\mathbf{x}) = -n_b(\mathbf{x}) C_{ablm} \int_S C_{jknlp} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_l \partial y_n} \Gamma_{mp}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) n_k(\mathbf{y}) \phi_j(\mathbf{y}) dS_y, \quad \mathbf{x} \in S, \quad (3.140)$$

where \int stands for the finite part of a divergent integral and \mathbf{t}^I is a traction vector associated with \mathbf{u}^I .

The hypersingular integral equation (3.140) can be regularised as (See Appendix L.5)

$$\begin{aligned} t_a^I(\mathbf{x}) &= n_b(\mathbf{x}) C_{ablm} \int_S e_{rkl} C_{jknlp} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_n} \Gamma_{mp}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) e_{riq} \phi_{j,i}(\mathbf{y}) n_q(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &\quad - n_b(\mathbf{x}) C_{ablm} \rho \omega^2 \int_S \Gamma_{mj}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) n_l(\mathbf{y}) \phi_j(\mathbf{y}) dS_y. \end{aligned} \quad (3.141)$$

where \int stands for the Cauchy principal value of a singular integral. We use (3.141) for a direct computation in FM-BIEM.

3.6.2 FM-BIEM

In FM-BIEM our first step is to expand the fundamental solution (3.139) into a series of products of functions of \mathbf{x} and those of \mathbf{y} . To this end we notice that the fundamental solution (3.139) can be rewritten as

$$\Gamma_{ip}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) = \frac{1}{4\pi\mu k_T^2} \left(e_{rqi} e_{rsp} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_q} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_s} \frac{e^{ik_T R}}{R} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_p} \frac{e^{ik_L R}}{R} \right), \quad (3.142)$$

where we have used the following identity:

$$(\Delta + k_T^2) \frac{e^{ik_T R}}{R} = 0 \quad (R \neq 0).$$

Using (3.120) and (3.142), we obtain a series expansion of the fundamental solution as follows:

$$\Gamma_{ip}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n D_{ri,n,m}^{T,\mathcal{O}}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) e_{rsp} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_s} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_n^m(k_T, \overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n D_{i,n,m}^{L,\mathcal{O}}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) \frac{\partial}{\partial y_p} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_n^m(k_L, \overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}), \quad (3.143)$$

where the function $\overline{\mathcal{I}}_n^m$ is given by (3.121) and the functions $D_{ri,n,m}^{T,\mathcal{O}}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})$ and $D_{i,n,m}^{L,\mathcal{O}}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})$ are defined as

$$D_{ri,n,m}^{T,\mathcal{O}}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) = \frac{i(2n+1)}{4\pi\mu k_T} e_{rqi} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_q} \mathcal{O}_n^m(k_T, \overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}), \quad (3.144)$$

$$D_{i,n,m}^{L,\mathcal{O}}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) = \frac{ik_L(2n+1)}{4\pi\mu k_T^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \mathcal{O}_n^m(k_L, \overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}). \quad (3.145)$$

In (3.144) and (3.145) the function \mathcal{O}_n^m is given by (3.122).

Now we compute the integral on the right-hand side of (3.140) over a subset of S denoted by S_y for an \mathbf{x} which is away from S_y . Using (3.143) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{S_y} C_{jktp} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_l \partial y_t} \Gamma_{ip}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) n_k(\mathbf{y}) \phi_j(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} D_{ri,n,m}^{T,\mathcal{O}}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) M_{r,n,m}^T(O) + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} D_{i,n,m}^{L,\mathcal{O}}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) M_{n,m}^L(O), \end{aligned} \quad (3.146)$$

where $M_{r,n,m}^T(O)$ and $M_{n,m}^L(O)$ are the multipole moments centred at O defined as

$$M_{r,n,m}^T(O) = \int_{S_y} C_{jktp} e_{rsp} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y_t \partial y_s} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_n^m(k_T, \overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) \phi_j(\mathbf{y}) n_k(\mathbf{y}) dS_y, \quad (3.147)$$

$$M_{n,m}^L(O) = \int_{S_y} C_{jktp} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y_t \partial y_p} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_n^m(k_L, \overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) \phi_j(\mathbf{y}) n_k(\mathbf{y}) dS_y. \quad (3.148)$$

In (3.146) we have assumed that the inequality $|\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}| > |\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}|$ ($\mathbf{y} \in S_y$) holds. Notice that $M_{r,n,m}^T(O)$ has three components and $M_{n,m}^L(O)$ has one component for a fixed pair of n and m and therefore the number of the multipole moments is 4. The number of the multipole moments is thus seen to be the same as that in three-dimensional elastostatics. Fujiwara [22] uses FMM to compute the double-layer potential in three-dimensional elastodynamics and in Fujiwara's formulation the number of the multipole moments is 6. If one adopts our formulation, the number of the multipole moments for the double-layer potential is 4 (details of the difference between our formulation and Fujiwara's one are given later). Also, Fukui and Inoue [24] use 4 multipole moments in FM-BIEM for ordinary problems in two-dimensional elastodynamics. However, replacing e_{rsp} with e_{3sp} in (3.147), one can find that the number of the multipole moments is 2 in our formulation for two-dimensional elastodynamics.

The multipole moments are translated according to the following formulae as the centre of the multipole expansion is shifted from O to O' :

$$M_{r,n,m}^T(O') = \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \sum_{\substack{l=|n-n'| \\ n'+n-l:\text{even}}}^{n+n'} (2n'+1)(-1)^{m'} W_{n,n',m,m',l} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_l^{-m-m'}(k_T, \overrightarrow{O'O}) M_{r,n',-m'}^T(O), \quad (3.149)$$

$$M_{n,m}^L(O') = \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \sum_{\substack{l=|n-n'| \\ n'+n-l:\text{even}}}^{n+n'} (2n'+1)(-1)^{m'} W_{n,n',m,m',l} \mathcal{I}_l^{-m-m'}(k_L, \overrightarrow{O'O}) M_{n',-m'}^L(O). \quad (3.150)$$

where we have used (3.123).

One can evaluate the integral on the right-hand side of (3.140) with the local expansion in the following manner:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{S_y} C_{jktp} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_l \partial y_t} \Gamma_{ip}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) n_k(\mathbf{y}) \phi_j(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} D_{ri,n,m}^{T,\bar{\mathcal{I}}}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}}) L_{r,n,m}^T(\mathbf{x}_0) + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} D_{i,n,m}^{L,\bar{\mathcal{I}}}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}}) L_{n,m}^L(\mathbf{x}_0), \end{aligned} \quad (3.151)$$

where $L_{r,n,m}^T(\mathbf{x}_0)$ and $L_{n,m}^L(\mathbf{x}_0)$ are the coefficients of the local expansion centred at \mathbf{x}_0 defined as

$$L_{r,n,m}^T(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \sum_{\substack{l=|n-n'| \\ n'+n-l:\text{even}}}^{n+n'} (2n'+1) W_{n',n,m',m',l} \tilde{\mathcal{O}}_l^{-m-m'}(k_T, \overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0}) M_{r,n',m'}^T(O), \quad (3.152)$$

$$L_{n,m}^L(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \sum_{\substack{l=|n-n'| \\ n'+n-l:\text{even}}}^{n+n'} (2n'+1) W_{n',n,m',m',l} \tilde{\mathcal{O}}_l^{-m-m'}(k_L, \overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0}) M_{n',m'}^L(O), \quad (3.153)$$

and the functions $D^{T,\bar{\mathcal{I}}}$ and $D^{L,\bar{\mathcal{I}}}$ are obtained by replacing $\mathcal{O}_{n,m}$ with $\bar{\mathcal{I}}_{n,m}$ in (3.144) and (3.145). In the derivation of (3.152) and (3.153) we have used (3.124) and have assumed that the inequality $|\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0}| > |\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}}|$ holds.

The coefficients of the local expansion are translated according to the following formulae as the centre of the local expansion is shifted from \mathbf{x}_0 to \mathbf{x}_1 :

$$L_{r,n,m}^T(\mathbf{x}_1) = \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \sum_{\substack{l=|n-n'| \\ n'+n-l:\text{even}}}^{n+n'} (2n'+1)(-1)^m W_{n',n,m',-m,l} \mathcal{I}_l^{m-m'}(k_T, \overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}_1}) L_{r,n',m'}^T(\mathbf{x}_0), \quad (3.154)$$

$$L_{n,m}^L(\mathbf{x}_1) = \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \sum_{\substack{l=|n-n'| \\ n'+n-l:\text{even}}}^{n+n'} (2n'+1)(-1)^m W_{n',n,m',-m,l} \mathcal{I}_l^{m-m'}(k_L, \overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}_1}) L_{n',m'}^L(\mathbf{x}_0). \quad (3.155)$$

where we have used (3.123).

Notice that M2M translations in (3.149) and (3.150), M2L translations in (3.152) and (3.153) and L2L translations in (3.154) and (3.155) have the same form as the M2M translation in (3.129), M2L translation in (3.131) and L2L translation in (3.132) in Helmholtz's equation. Also, the derivation of translation formulae in elastodynamics is similar to that in Helmholtz's equation.

We have thus prepared all the formulae needed for FM-BIEM. Using formulae presented above and the algorithm described in chapter 2, one can implement FM-BIEM.

3.6.3 Numerical procedure

Truncation of the infinite series

In FM-BIEM, we truncate the infinite series in (3.146), (3.151), etc. via (3.133). For example we may truncate (3.146) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{S_y} C_{jktp} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_l \partial y_t} \Gamma_{ip}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) n_k(\mathbf{y}) \phi_j(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{P_T} \sum_{m=-n}^n \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} D_{ri,n,m}^{T,\mathcal{O}}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) M_{r,n,m}^T(O) + \sum_{n=0}^{P_L} \sum_{m=-n}^n \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} D_{i,n,m}^{L,\mathcal{O}}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) M_{n,m}^L(O), \end{aligned} \quad (3.156)$$

where P_T and P_L are given by (See (3.133))

$$P_T = P(k_T R), \quad P_L = P(k_L R),$$

and the inequality $P_T > P_L$ ($k_T > k_L$) holds. However, if one uses (3.156) in this manner the implementation becomes somewhat complicated. Therefore, in the present implementation we truncate the right-hand side of (3.146) taking P_T terms for simplicity as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{S_y} C_{jktp} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_l \partial y_t} \Gamma_{ip}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) n_k(\mathbf{y}) \phi_j(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{P_T} \sum_{m=-n}^n \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} D_{ri,n,m}^{T,\mathcal{O}}(\overline{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{x}}) M_{r,n,m}^T(O) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} D_{i,n,m}^{L,\mathcal{O}}(\overline{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{x}}) M_{n,m}^L(O) \right). \end{aligned}$$

In the same way we treat other infinite series in (3.151), etc.

Direct computation

Discretising the regularised integral equation (3.141) with piecewise constant shape functions, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} t_a^I(\mathbf{x}) &= n_b(\mathbf{x}) C_{ablm} \sum_L \oint_{\partial S_L} e_{rkl} C_{jknp} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_n} \Gamma_{mp}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) dy_r \phi_j^L \\ &\quad - n_b(\mathbf{x}) C_{ablm} \rho \omega^2 \sum_L \int_{S_L} \Gamma_{mj}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) n_l(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \phi_j^L, \end{aligned} \quad (3.157)$$

where S_J is a plane element in S_y and ϕ^J represents ϕ on S_J . In the evaluation of the integral in (3.157) we divide (3.139) into the static part (the fundamental solution of the equation of elastostatics) and the residual part as follows:

$$\Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) = \Gamma_{ij}^S(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) + \Gamma_{ij}^R(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}),$$

where $\Gamma_{ij}^S(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})$ and $\Gamma_{ij}^R(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})$ are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma_{ij}^S(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) &= \frac{1}{8\pi\mu} \left(\delta_{ij} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} - \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_j} \right) R, \\ \Gamma_{ij}^R(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) &= \frac{1}{4\pi\mu} \left(\frac{e^{ik_T R} - 1}{R} \delta_{ij} + \frac{1}{k_T^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_j} \left(\frac{e^{ik_T R}}{R} - \frac{e^{ik_L R}}{R} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{k_L^2}{k_T^2} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial y_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_j} R \right), \end{aligned} \quad (3.158)$$

where $R = |\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|$. Namely, we treat four integrals to compute (3.157) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} t_a^I(\mathbf{x}) &= n_b(\mathbf{x}) C_{ablm} \sum_L \oint_{\partial S_L} e_{rkl} C_{jknp} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_n} \Gamma_{mp}^S(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) dy_r \phi_j^L \\ &\quad - n_b(\mathbf{x}) C_{ablm} \rho \omega^2 \sum_L \int_{S_L} \Gamma_{mj}^S(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) n_l(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \phi_j^L \\ &\quad + n_b(\mathbf{x}) C_{ablm} \sum_L \oint_{\partial S_L} e_{rkl} C_{jknp} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_n} \Gamma_{mp}^R(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) dy_r \phi_j^L \\ &\quad - n_b(\mathbf{x}) C_{ablm} \rho \omega^2 \sum_L \int_{S_L} \Gamma_{mj}^R(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) n_l(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \phi_j^L \end{aligned} \quad (3.159)$$

In the computation of the integrals related to $\Gamma_{ij}^R(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})$ we expand (3.158) into the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} & \Gamma_{ij}^R(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) \\ &= \frac{1}{4\pi\mu} \left\{ \delta_{ij} \left[\frac{e^{ik_T R}}{R} - \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \left(\frac{k_L}{k_T} \right)^2 \right) \frac{1}{R} + \left(\frac{i}{k_T R} - \frac{1}{(k_T R)^2} \right) \frac{e^{ik_T R}}{R} \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. - \left(\frac{k_L}{k_T} \right)^2 \left(\frac{i}{k_T R} - \frac{1}{(k_T R)^2} \right) \frac{e^{ik_T R}}{R} \right] - R_{,j} R_{,m} \left[\left(1 + \frac{3i}{k_T R} - \frac{3}{(k_T R)^2} \right) \frac{e^{ik_T R}}{R} \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. - \left(\frac{k_L}{k_T} \right)^2 \left(1 + \frac{3i}{k_T R} - \frac{3}{(k_T R)^2} \right) \frac{e^{ik_T R}}{R} + \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \left(\frac{k_L}{k_T} \right)^2 \right) \right] \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (3.160)$$

When $k_T R$ is small we use the following series instead of (3.160)

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma_{ij}^R(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) &= \frac{1}{4\pi\mu} \left\{ \delta_{ij} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(ik_T)^{n+1} R^n}{(n+1)!(n+3)} \left(n+2 + \left(\frac{k_L}{k_T} \right)^{n+3} \right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - R_{,i} R_{,j} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(ik_T)^{n+1} n R^n}{(n+1)!(n+3)} \left(1 - \left(\frac{k_L}{k_T} \right)^{n+3} \right) \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (3.161)$$

We compute the integrals related to the static part in (3.159) analytically and the rest numerically with Gaussian quadrature.

Algorithm

We briefly describe the usage of formulae presented here in each step in the algorithm of FM-BIEM (See chapter 2 for more details).

Steps 1–2. Same as the steps 1–2 in the algorithm described in chapter 2.

Step 3. Computation of the multipole moments:

In this step we use (3.147) and (3.148) for the computation of the multipole moments associated with leaves. Also, we use (3.149) and (3.150) for M2M translations tracing the tree structure of cells upward (decreasing $l(\geq 2)$).

Step 4. Computation of the local expansion:

In this step we use (3.152) and (3.153) for M2L translations and (3.154) and (3.155) for L2L translations tracing the tree structure of cells downward (increasing $l(\geq 2)$).

Step 5. Evaluation of the integral in (3.118):

In this step we use (3.119) for the direct computation and use (3.130) for the evaluation of contributions from the local expansion.

3.6.4 Numerical examples

The proposed techniques have been implemented in Fortran 77, and have been tested on a computer having a DEC Alpha 21264(500 MHz) chip as the CPU. In FMM, we truncate the infinite series via (3.133) with $k = k_T$. Also, we set the maximum number of boundary elements in a leaf to be 100. The integrals in (3.147) and (3.148) are computed numerically with Gaussian quadrature. In GMRES we terminate the iteration when the relative error is less than 10^{-5} . To solve the resulting matrix equation we use the preconditioned GMRES and adopt the block diagonal matrix corresponding to the leaves as the preconditioner according to Nishida and Hayami [62].

We consider an infinite space which contains one penny-shaped crack having the radius of a_0 and the unit normal vector of $\mathbf{n} = (0, 0, 1)$. We compute the crack opening displacement when the crack is subject to a plane longitudinal wave of normal incidence from $-x_3$ direction. The stress magnitude of the incident wave is p_0 . Also, Poisson's ratio is 0.25. This problem is solved with the conventional BIEM and FM-BIEM. Fig.3.52, Fig.3.54 and Fig.3.56 plot the total CPU time (sec) vs the number of unknowns when $k_T a_0 = 1.4, 3.2, 4.4$. In these figures lines marked "Tdir" and "Tfmm" indicate the CPU time required with the conventional BIEM and FM-BIEM, respectively. This figure shows that the FM-BIEM is faster than the conventional BIEM when the number of unknowns is larger than several thousands. Fig.3.53, Fig.3.55 and Fig.3.57 show the crack opening displacement $|\phi|/\phi_0$ where ϕ_0 is the static opening displacement at the centre of the crack and $\phi_0 = 3p_0 a_0 / \pi\mu$. In these figures lines marked "conv" and "fmm" indicate the crack opening displacements obtained with the conventional BIEM and FM-BIEM, respectively. In Fig.3.58 "numer" indicates the crack opening displacement $|\phi|/\phi_0$ obtained with FM-BIEM numerically, and "analytic" stands for analytical solutions (Mal [56]). In Fig.3.59 the lines marked "Elastostatics" and "Elastodynamics" show the computational times required with FM-BIEM for elastostatics and elastodynamics ($k_T a_0 = 1.4$), respectively. As in the case of Helmholtz's equation the computational time required by an elastodynamic analysis is longer than that required with an elastostatic one.

Figure 3.52: Total CPU time (sec) ($k_T a_0 = 1.4$)

Figure 3.53: Crack opening displacement ($k_T a_0 = 1.4$)

Figure 3.54: Total CPU time (sec) ($k_T a_0 = 3.2$)

Figure 3.55: Crack opening displacement ($k_T a_0 = 3.2$)

Figure 3.56: Total CPU time (sec) ($k_T a_0 = 4.4$)

Figure 3.57: Crack opening displacement ($k_T a_0 = 4.4$)

Figure 3.58: Numerical result and analytical solution ($k_T a_0 = 3.2$)

Figure 3.59: Comparison of computational times for elastostatics and elastodynamics ($k_T a_0 = 1.4$)

3.6.5 Comparison of formulations for the double-layer potential

In this section we compare our FMM formulation and Fujiwara's one for the double-layer potential in elastodynamics to clarify the difference between these formulations. In this section S denotes a surface in a domain and \mathbf{n} the unit vector normal to S .

First, we describe our formulation for the double-layer potential. The double-layer potential is written as

$$W_i(\mathbf{x}) = \int_{S_y} C_{j k p l} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{i p}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) u_j(\mathbf{y}) n_k(\mathbf{y}) dS_y. \quad (3.162)$$

where u_i is the displacement vector.

Substituting (3.142) into (3.162), we obtain

$$W_i(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n D_{r i, n, m}^{T, \mathcal{O}}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) \widehat{M}_{r, n, m}^T(O) + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n D_{i, n, m}^{L, \mathcal{O}}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) \widehat{M}_{n, m}^L(O)$$

where $\widehat{M}_{r, n, m}^T(O)$ and $\widehat{M}_{n, m}^L(O)$ are the same as (3.147) and (3.148). In our formulation the number of the multipole moments is 4. Similarly, one can easily find that the number of the multipole moments for the single-layer potential is also 4.

Second, we describe Fujiwara's formulation for the double-layer potential.

Fujiwara's starting point is to write the fundamental solution (3.139) as

$$\Gamma_{i p}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) = \frac{1}{4\pi\mu} \left(\left(\delta_{i p} + \frac{1}{k_T^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y_i \partial y_p} \right) \frac{e^{i k_T R}}{R} - \frac{1}{k_T^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y_i \partial y_p} \frac{e^{i k_L R}}{R} \right) \quad (3.163)$$

Substituting (3.120) into (3.163), one obtains

$$\Gamma_{i p}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n F_{n, m}^T(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) \left(\delta_{i p} + \frac{1}{k_T^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y_i \partial y_p} \right) \overline{\mathcal{I}}_n^m(k_T, \overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) + F_{n, m}^L(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) \frac{1}{k_T^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y_i \partial y_p} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_n^m(k_L, \overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}), \quad (3.164)$$

where functions $F_{i p, n, m}^T(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})$ and $F_{i p, n, m}^L(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})$ are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} F_{n, m}^T(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) &= \frac{i(2n+1)k_T}{4\pi\mu} \mathcal{O}_n^m(k_T, \overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) \\ F_{n, m}^L(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) &= -\frac{i(2n+1)k_L}{4\pi\mu} \mathcal{O}_n^m(k_L, \overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}). \end{aligned}$$

Substituting (3.164) into (3.162), one obtains

$$W_i(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n F_{n, m}^T(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) \widetilde{M}_{i, n, m}^T(O) + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n F_{n, m}^L(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) \widetilde{M}_{i, n, m}^L(O)$$

where $\widetilde{M}_{i, n, m}^T(O)$ and $\widetilde{M}_{i, n, m}^L(O)$ are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{M}_{i, n, m}^T(O) &= \int_{S_y} C_{j k p l} \left(\delta_{i p} + \frac{1}{k_T^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y_i \partial y_p} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_n^m(k_T, \overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) u_j(\mathbf{y}) n_k(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ \widetilde{M}_{i, n, m}^L(O) &= \int_{S_y} C_{j k p l} \frac{1}{k_T^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y_i \partial y_p} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_n^m(k_L, \overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) u_j(\mathbf{y}) n_k(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \end{aligned}$$

Both $\widetilde{M}_{p, n, m}^T(O)$ and $\widetilde{M}_{p, n, m}^L(O)$ have three components. Therefore, the total number of the multipole moment for the double-layer potential is $6(=3 \times 2)$ for a given pair of n and m .

3.7 Concluding remarks

- In chapter 3 we have successfully applied FM-BIEM to crack problems in Laplace's equation, elastostatics, Helmholtz's equation and elastodynamics and have shown the efficiencies of FMM in BIEM. We have shown the potential of the FM-BIEM for large-scale problems in fractures mechanics.

- It can be seen that the regularised formulation is inferior to the non-regularised formulation through numerical examples in 3.2 and 3.3.
- The numerical results obtained with collocation method are considerably inferior to those obtained with Galerkin's method in both performance and precision in elastostatic crack problems. Indeed, comparing Fig.3.24 with Fig.3.30, one can see that the numerical results obtained with Galerkin's method with 471 DOF mesh is more accurate than those obtained with collocation method with 28776 DOF mesh. This is because the solution of the Galerkin boundary integral equation minimises the potential energy in the space of displacement fields spanned by double layer potentials with given set of shape functions [87]. This is in contrast to the collocation solution with discontinuous shape functions where the approximate solution does not even belong to the space with finite energy. In view of this it would be interesting to investigate FM-GBIEM for other crack problems.
- The inefficiency of the evaluation of interior quantities has been one of major shortcomings of BIEM. The FMM approach of evaluating interior stresses proposed in 3.4 is expected to resolve this problem at least when one computes field quantities at many points in the domain.
- In 3.4 we have not utilised the symmetry of the matrices in GBIEM. Hence, we shall use iterative solvers for symmetric matrices in the future.
- In dynamic problems dealing with Helmholtz's equation and elastodynamics the performance of FM-BIEM is considerably worse than that in static problems. In order to apply FM-BIEM to large-scale dynamic problems we need to improve the performance using Rokhlin's diagonal form or the new FMM. As a matter of fact, M2L translation is not the only bottleneck in dynamic problems. Besides M2L translation, the direct computation also deteriorates the performance. For example, one can easily see that the direct computation in (3.157) is time-consuming because we must evaluate the four integrals in (3.159). This could be reduced by using numerical integrations properly.
- In this chapter we use the block diagonal matrix corresponding to the leaves as the preconditioner, following techniques proposed by Nishida and Hayami [62] and succeed in reduction of the number of iterations to achieve convergence. However, in problems considered in [60] the preconditioner of this type has been shown to increase the number of iterations. The preconditioner is considered to be one of the keys to improve the performance of FM-BIEM and, therefore, we need to study the preconditioners further.
- In engineering the singularity of the solution near the crack tip is very important. However, we have not taken it into consideration for simplicity. Because the use of singular elements is not very difficult, we plan to use singular elements in order to consider the behaviour of the solution near the crack tip and compute the stress intensity factor.
- Growths of cracks lead to failures of structures and therefore behaviour of them is very significant. Hence, we plan to apply FM-BIEM to growths of many cracks in the future.
- One can use techniques proposed in this chapter in ordinary problems as well as in crack problems. Techniques obtained in elastodynamics have a great utility value because BIEM is particularly suitable for wave analyses. Applications of BIEM to elastodynamics are often found in analyses of dynamic response characteristics of structures. Dynamic response characteristic of a structure is a very important factor in the earthquake-resistant design. Also, recent underground structures are crossing three-dimensionally and, therefore, analyses of such structures inevitably become large-scale. FM-BIEM is considered to be a powerful tool in such cases. Hence, we plan to apply FM-BIEM to such problems.

Chapter 4

Applications of the new FMM to three-dimensional problems

In this chapter we apply new Fast Multipole Boundary Integral Equation Method (new FM-BIEM) to crack problems for three-dimensional Laplace’s equation and three-dimensional elastostatics. We compare the results obtained with the new FMM with those obtained in chapter 3. We shall call the FM-BIEM described in chapter 3 the “original FM-BIEM” to distinguish the “FM-BIEM” from the “new FM-BIEM” clearly. The new FMM provides techniques to reduce the computational cost for M2L translation which is the bottleneck in the original FMM. We achieve reduction of the computational cost by replacing procedures for M2L translation in the original FM-BIEM obtained in the chapter 3 with three procedures called M2X, X2X and X2L translations (details of M2X, X2X and X2L are given later).

Figure 4.1: Computational cost for M2L and M2X+X2X+X2L

Here we briefly describe the outline of the new FMM (See Greengard and Rokhlin [36] for more details). In the original FMM in three dimensions, if one truncates the infinite series in the multipole expansion

taking p terms then the computational costs for M2M, M2L and L2L translations are proportional to $O(p^4)$, $O(189p^4)$ in the worst case and $O(p^4)$, respectively. In particular, M2L translation deteriorates the performance of FMM in dealing with three-dimensional problems where boundary elements are distributed densely. In order to reduce the cost for M2M, M2L and L2L translations, Greengard and Rokhlin proposed the new FMM on the basis of an integral representation for a fundamental solution. In this chapter we use techniques to reduce the computational cost for M2L translation because the complexity for M2L translation is dominant in FMM. In the new FMM we use the exponential expansion besides the multipole expansion and the local expansion. The M2X, X2X and X2L translation formulae are to convert the multipole expansion to the exponential expansion, the exponential expansion to another exponential expansion and the exponential expansion to the local expansion, respectively. The total computational costs for M2X, X2X and X2L translations are $O(p^3)$, $O(p^2)$ and $O(p^3)$, respectively, and therefore the total cost is $O(p^3)$ (See Fig.4.1). This is why the new FMM is more efficient than the original FMM.

4.1 Crack problems for three-dimensional Laplace's equation

As far as we know, applications of the new FMM to numerical implementation of BIEM are not found in literature. Therefore, first of all, we applied the new FMM to BIEM for three-dimensional crack problems in Laplace's equation in this section, using techniques obtained in section 3.2.

The material in this section is from Yoshida et al. [88]

4.1.1 New FM-BIEM

Suppose that we evaluate the contribution from a cell C_s to the coefficients of the local expansion in a cell C_t contained in the interaction list of C_s . The cells C_s and C_t are called a source cell and a target cell, respectively. We divide the interaction list of C_s into 6 lists called the uplist, downlist, northlist, southlist, eastlist and westlist of C_s . The uplist and downlist contain target cells located in $+x_3$ and $-x_3$ directions of C_s , respectively. The northlist and southlist contain target cells located in $+x_2$ and $-x_2$ directions of C_s except those in the uplist or downlist, respectively. The eastlist and westlist contain target cells located in $+x_1$ and $-x_1$ directions of C_s except those in the uplist, downlist, northlist or southlist, respectively. In this section we discuss the case where target cells are included in the uplist of C_s and each of the cells is a cube having a volume of d^3 . Suppose that a source point \mathbf{y} is located at (y_1, y_2, y_3) in C_s and a target point \mathbf{x} at (x_1, x_2, x_3) in C_t . It is easy to see that the following integral representation [61] holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{(x_1 - y_1)^2 + (x_2 - y_2)^2 + (x_3 - y_3)^2}} \\ &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty e^{-\lambda(x_3 - y_3)} \int_0^{2\pi} e^{i\lambda((x_1 - y_1) \cos \alpha + (x_2 - y_2) \sin \alpha)} d\alpha d\lambda \end{aligned} \quad (4.1)$$

where we have assumed that the inequality $x_3 > y_3$ holds. The inner integral with respect to α in (4.1) is computed with the trapezoidal rule and the outer integral with generalised Gaussian quadrature rules [83], yielding

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{(x_1 - y_1)^2 + (x_2 - y_2)^2 + (x_3 - y_3)^2}} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{s(\varepsilon)} \sum_{j=1}^{M(k)} \frac{\omega_k}{M(k)d} e^{-(\lambda_k/d)(x_3 - y_3)} e^{i(\lambda_k/d)((x_1 - y_1) \cos \alpha_j(k) + (x_2 - y_2) \sin \alpha_j(k))} + \varepsilon, \end{aligned} \quad (4.2)$$

($x_3 > y_3$)

where $\alpha_j(k)$ is given by

$$\alpha_j(k) = \frac{2\pi j}{M(k)},$$

ε is the error term and the numbers $s(\varepsilon)$, $M(k)$, Gaussian weights ω_k and nodes λ_k are given in Yarvin and Rokhlin [83]. These numbers are available from Netlib (<http://www.netlib.org/pdes/multipole/>). One may determine these parameters considering the required accuracy.

Figure 4.2: Uplist of source cell

Noting (4.2) and the following formulae: (See (3.19) and Appendix B)

$$S_{n,m}(\vec{Ox}) = (-1)^n \partial_+^m \partial_z^{n-m} \left(\frac{1}{|\vec{Ox}|} \right) \quad (m \geq 0), \quad (4.3)$$

$$S_{n,-m}(\vec{Ox}) = (-1)^{n+m} \partial_-^m \partial_z^{n-m} \left(\frac{1}{|\vec{Ox}|} \right) \quad (m \geq 0), \quad (4.4)$$

$$\partial_{\pm} = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \pm i \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \right), \quad (4.5)$$

one can evaluate the integral in (3.22) in the following manner: (See Appendix J.1)

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{S_y} \frac{\partial^2 G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial n_x \partial n_y} \varphi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &= \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{\partial}{\partial n_x} \sum_{k=1}^{s(\varepsilon)} \sum_{j=1}^{M(k)} X(k, j; O) e^{-\lambda_k/d} (\vec{Ox})_3 + i(\lambda_k/d) ((\vec{Ox})_1 \cos \alpha_j(k) + (\vec{Ox})_2 \sin \alpha_j(k)) \end{aligned}$$

where $X(k, j; O)$ is the coefficient of the exponential expansion at O , defined by

$$X(k, j; O) = \frac{\omega_k}{M(k)d} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} (-i)^m e^{-im\alpha_j(k)} \sum_{n=|m|}^{\infty} (\lambda_k/d)^n M_{n,m}(O). \quad (4.6)$$

This formula converts the multipole moments into the exponential expansion coefficients. We call the procedure given by (4.6) “M2X (Multipole moment to (2) exponential expansion) translation”. The coefficients of the exponential expansion is translated according to the following formula when the centre of the exponential expansion is shifted from O to \mathbf{x}_0 : (See Appendix J.2)

$$X(k, j; \mathbf{x}_0) = X(k, j; O) e^{-\lambda_k/d} (\vec{Ox}_0)_3 + i(\lambda_k/d) ((\vec{Ox}_0)_1 \cos \alpha_j(k) + (\vec{Ox}_0)_2 \sin \alpha_j(k)) \quad (4.7)$$

where $(\mathbf{x})_i$ stand for the components of the vector \mathbf{x} . We call the procedure given by (4.7) “X2X (eXponential expansion to(2) eXponential expansion) translation”.

We next need to convert the coefficients of the exponential expansion into the coefficients of the local expansion (See (3.27)). Noting that the integral in (3.22) is expressed with $X(k, j; \mathbf{x}_0)$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{S_y} \frac{\partial^2 G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial n_x \partial n_y} \varphi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &= \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{\partial}{\partial n_x} \sum_{k=1}^{s(\varepsilon)} \sum_{j=1}^{M(k)} X(k, j; \mathbf{x}_0) e^{-(\lambda_k/d)(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}})_3 + i(\lambda_k/d)((\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}})_1 \cos \alpha_j(k) + (\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}})_2 \sin \alpha_j(k))} \end{aligned} \quad (4.8)$$

and using (3.26) and the following formula (See (3.18) and Hobson [43]):

$$\frac{((\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})_3 - i(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})_1 \cos \alpha_j(k) - i(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})_2 \sin \alpha_j(k))^n}{n!} = \sum_{m=-n}^n (-i)^m e^{-im\alpha_j(k)} R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) \quad (4.9)$$

we obtain the following formula which converts the coefficients of the exponential expansion into the coefficient of the local expansion: (See Appendix J.3)

$$L_{n,m}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{k=1}^{s(\varepsilon)} \sum_{j=1}^{M(k)} X(k, j; \mathbf{x}_0) (-i)^m (-\lambda_k/d)^n e^{-im\alpha_j(k)}. \quad (4.10)$$

We call the procedure given by (4.10) “X2L (eXponential expansion to(2) Local expansion) translation”. In the new FM-BIEM we replace M2L translation given by (3.27) with M2X, X2X and X2L translation given by (4.6), (4.7) and (4.10).

4.1.2 Rotation of coefficients

The discussion in the previous section has been restricted to the case where the target cell is in the uplist of C_s . We now consider the general case. If the target cell is included in lists other than the uplist we rotate the coordinate system so that the target cell is in the positive \tilde{x}_3 direction viewed from the source cell, where \tilde{x}_i denotes the new axis. Accordingly, the multipole moments in the new coordinate system are obtained as follows:

$$\widetilde{M}_{n,m}(O) = \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m,m'}(\boldsymbol{\nu}, \alpha) M_{n,m'}(O) \quad (4.11)$$

where $\mathcal{R}_{n,m,m'}(\boldsymbol{\nu}, \alpha)$ is the coefficient of rotation, $\boldsymbol{\nu}$ is a unit vector parallel to the rotation axis and α is a rotation angle. The explicit form of the coefficient $\mathcal{R}_{n,m,m'}(\boldsymbol{\nu}, \alpha)$ is given by (See Biedenharn and Louck [6])

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{R}_{n,m,m'}(\boldsymbol{\nu}, \alpha) &= (-1)^{m+m'} (n+m')!(n-m')! \\ & \sum_k \frac{(\alpha_0 - i\alpha_3)^{n+m-k} (-i\alpha_1 - \alpha_2)^{m'-m+k} (-i\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)^k (\alpha_0 + i\alpha_3)^{n-m'-k}}{(n+m-k)!(m'-m+k)!k!(n-m'-k)!} \end{aligned} \quad (4.12)$$

where $\alpha_0 = \cos(\alpha/2)$ and $\alpha_i = -\nu_i \sin(\alpha/2)$. The summation is over such k that the numbers in the parentheses in the denominator are all non-negative.

We next describe the M2L translation process for the general case.

1. Rotation:

We first rotate the multipole moments via (4.11). The specific forms of (4.11) vary as follows, as the location of C_t changes:

- $C_t \in$ uplist

$$\widetilde{M}_{n,m}^U(O) = M_{n,m}(O) \quad (4.13)$$

- $C_t \in$ downlist

$$\widetilde{M}_{n,m}^D(O) = \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m,m'}(\mathbf{e}_1, \pi) M_{n,m'}(O) \quad (4.14)$$

- $C_t \in \text{northlist}$

$$\widetilde{M}_{n,m}^N(O) = \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m,m'}(\mathbf{e}_1, \pi/2) M_{n,m'}(O) \quad (4.15)$$

- $C_t \in \text{southlist}$

$$\widetilde{M}_{n,m}^S(O) = \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m,m'}(\mathbf{e}_1, -\pi/2) M_{n,m'}(O) \quad (4.16)$$

- $C_t \in \text{eastlist}$

$$\widetilde{M}_{n,m}^E(O) = \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m,m'}(\mathbf{e}_2, -\pi/2) M_{n,m'}(O) \quad (4.17)$$

- $C_t \in \text{westlist}$

$$\widetilde{M}_{n,m}^W(O) = \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m,m'}(\mathbf{e}_2, \pi/2) M_{n,m'}(O) \quad (4.18)$$

where \mathbf{e}_i is the base vector for the Cartesian coordinates.

2. Compute the coefficients of the exponential expansion:

Compute the coefficients of the exponential expansion via (4.6) as follows:

$$X^\diamond(k, j; O) = \frac{\omega_k}{M(k)d} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} (-i)^m e^{-im\alpha_j} \sum_{n=|m|}^{\infty} (\lambda_k/d)^n \widetilde{M}_{n,m}^\diamond(O) \quad (4.19)$$

where \diamond is an element of $\{U, D, N, S, E, W\}$.

3. Translation of the coefficients of the exponential expansion:

As the centre of the exponential expansion is shifted from O (the centroid of C_s) to \mathbf{x}_0 (the centroid of C_t), the coefficients of the exponential expansion are transformed according to (4.7) as follows:

$$X^\diamond(k, j; \mathbf{x}_0) = X^\diamond(k, j; O) e^{-(\lambda_k/d)(\widetilde{O\mathbf{x}_0})_3 + i(\lambda_k/d)((\widetilde{O\mathbf{x}_0})_1 \cos \alpha_j + (\widetilde{O\mathbf{x}_0})_2 \sin \alpha_j)} \quad (4.20)$$

where \diamond is an element of $\{U, D, N, S, E, W\}$ and the components $(\widetilde{O\mathbf{x}_0})_i$ are obtained by applying the corresponding rotation of coordinates to $\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0}$.

4. Compute the coefficients of the local expansion:

Compute the coefficients of the local expansion from the exponential expansion according to (4.10) as follows:

$$\widetilde{L}_{n,m}^\diamond(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{k=1}^{s(\varepsilon)} \sum_{j=1}^{M(k)} X^\diamond(k, j; \mathbf{x}_0) (-i)^m (-\lambda_k/d)^n e^{-im\alpha_j} \quad (4.21)$$

where \diamond is an element of $\{U, D, N, S, E, W\}$. Then rotate $\widetilde{L}_{n,m}^\diamond$ as follows:

- $C_t \in \text{uplist}$

$$L_{n,m}^U(\mathbf{x}_0) = \widetilde{L}_{n,m}^U(\mathbf{x}_0) \quad (4.22)$$

- $C_t \in \text{downlist}$

$$L_{n,m}^D(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m',m}(\mathbf{e}_1, \pi) \widetilde{L}_{n,m'}^D(\mathbf{x}_0) \quad (4.23)$$

- $C_t \in \text{northlist}$

$$L_{n,m}^N(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m',m}(\mathbf{e}_1, \pi/2) \widetilde{L}_{n,m'}^N(\mathbf{x}_0) \quad (4.24)$$

- $C_t \in \text{southlist}$

$$L_{n,m}^S(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m',m}(\mathbf{e}_1, -\pi/2) \tilde{L}_{n,m'}^S(\mathbf{x}_0) \quad (4.25)$$

- $C_t \in \text{eastlist}$

$$L_{n,m}^E(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m',m}(\mathbf{e}_2, -\pi/2) \tilde{L}_{n,m'}^E(\mathbf{x}_0) \quad (4.26)$$

- $C_t \in \text{westlist}$

$$L_{n,m}^W(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m',m}(\mathbf{e}_2, \pi/2) \tilde{L}_{n,m'}^W(\mathbf{x}_0) \quad (4.27)$$

Finally add L^U, L^D, L^N, L^S, L^E and L^W together

$$L_{n,m}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{\diamond \in U, D, N, S, E, W} L_{n,m}^{\diamond}(\mathbf{x}_0)$$

to obtain the coefficients of the local expansion.

4.1.3 Algorithm for the new FM-BIEM

The algorithm for the new version of FMM is given as follows:

Steps 1–3. Same as the steps 1–3 in the algorithm described in 3.2.

Step 4. Computation of the coefficients of the exponential expansion:

Compute the coefficients of the exponential expansion at each cell using (4.13)–(4.18) and (4.19), taking the origin at the centroid of the cell.

Step 5. Computation of the coefficients of the local expansion:

We compute the coefficients of the local expansion of cells of level l , starting from $l = 2$ and increasing l . In the evaluation of the coefficients of the local expansion of a level l cell C , we first consider the contribution from the interaction list of C , to which a cell C' is assumed to belong. Depending on the position of C' relative to C , we use (4.20) to shift the centre of the exponential expansion of C' from the centroid of C' to that of C . Next convert the contributions from all the cells in the uplist, downlist, northlist, southlist, eastlist and westlist to the coefficients of the local expansion via (4.21), (4.22)–(4.27) and add them together to obtain the contributions to the coefficients of the local expansion of C from the interaction list of C . To these we add the coefficients of the local expansion of the parent of C with the origin shifted from the centroid of the parent to that of C via (3.29) to obtain the coefficients of the local expansion of C .

Step 6. Evaluation of the integral in (3.15):

This step is the same as the step 5 in the algorithm describe in 3.2.

4.1.4 Numerical examples

The proposed techniques have been implemented in Fortran 77, and have been tested on a computer having a DEC Alpha 21264(500 MHz) chip as the CPU. In FMM, we truncate the infinite series in (3.22) and (3.26) taking 10 terms and compute the series in (4.6), (4.8) and (4.10) using the 109 point generalised Gaussian quadrature formula given in Yarvin and Rokhlin [83]. Also, we set the maximum number of boundary elements in a leaf to be 100. The integrals in (3.23) are computed numerically with Gaussian quadrature. To solve the resulting matrix equation we use the preconditioned GMRES and adopt the block diagonal matrix corresponding to the leaves as the preconditioner following the technique proposed by Nishida and Hayami [62]. In GMRES we terminate the iteration when the relative error is less than 10^{-5} . The inverse of the preconditioner is obtained with Crout's method.

One penny-shaped crack

To begin with we consider a penny-shaped crack having the radius of a_0 and the unit normal vector of $\mathbf{n} = (0, 0, 1)$. The asymptotic field $u^\infty(\mathbf{x})$ is given by $u^\infty(\mathbf{x}) = u_0 x_3 / a_0$. This problem is solved with the conventional BIEM, FM-BIEM with the original FMM and with FM-BIEM with the new version of FMM. The numerical solutions obtained with these methods were found to be essentially identical. Fig.4.3 shows the 1912 DOF mesh and Fig.4.4 plots the non-dimensional crack opening displacement (ϕ/u_0) obtained with this mesh. In Fig.4.4 the symbols marked “conv”, “fmm” and “newfmm” indicate numerical results computed with the conventional BIEM, the original FM-BIEM and the new FM-BIEM, respectively. Fig.4.4 shows good agreement between numerical results. Fig.4.5 plots the total CPU time (sec) vs the number of unknowns. In Fig.4.5 the lines marked “Tdir”, “Tfmm” and “Tfmmnew” indicate the CPU time required with the conventional BIEM, the original FM-BIEM and the new FM-BIEM, respectively. This figure shows that the new FM-BIEM is slightly faster than the original FM-BIEM. This small improvement is to be expected since the computational cost for M2L is not dominant in the single crack case, where the cell arrangement is essentially two-dimensional. Hence the improvement of the efficiency achieved with the new FM-BIEM in this particular numerical example may not necessarily be very typical. Therefore we consider many crack problems in the next example to show the efficiency of the new approach more clearly.

Many penny-shaped cracks

We now consider an infinite space which contains an array of $8 \times 8 \times 8 (= 512)$ penny-shaped cracks, each having the same radius a_0 subjected to the same asymptotic condition as in the previous example. The centroids of these cracks are located regularly with an interval of $4a_0$ in each coordinate direction, but the orientation of each crack is taken random. Fig.4.6 shows the mesh for 512 cracks (total DOF=241,664), with each crack having 472 DOF. Fig.4.7 shows the crack opening displacements; we superimposed the non-dimensional crack opening displacement (ϕ/u_0) plotted in the normal direction on the non-dimensional mesh \mathbf{x}/a_0 . The required CPU times with the original FM-BIEM and the new FM-BIEM are 4930(sec) and 3633(sec), respectively, while the numerical results obtained with these methods coincided. This result shows that the new FM-BIEM is more efficient than the original FM-BIEM when the boundary elements are distributed densely in the domain.

Figure 4.3: Crack mesh (DOF=1912)

Figure 4.4: Crack opening displacement

Figure 4.5: CPU time (sec)

Figure 4.6: Crack mesh (DOF=241,664)

Figure 4.7: Crack opening displacement (DOF=241,664)

4.2 Crack problems for three-dimensional elastostatics

In this section we discuss an application of the new FM-BIEM to three-dimensional elastostatic crack problems, using techniques obtained in sections 3.3 and 4.1. As far as we know, applications of the new FMM to three-dimensional elastostatics are not found in literature. Indeed, an application of the new FMM to three-dimensional elastostatics is mentioned in Fu et al. [19] but they present only an integral representation for the fundamental solution of anisotropic elastostatics without FMM formulation or numerical examples.

The material in this section is from Yoshida et al. [89]

4.2.1 New FM-BIEM

Now we consider a source point \mathbf{y} located at (y_1, y_2, y_3) and a target point \mathbf{x} at (x_1, x_2, x_3) and denote a cell including a source point by C_s and a cell including a target point by C_t . Suppose that each of the cells C_s and C_t has a volume of d^3 . Here we use the integral representation (4.1) again. The integral in (4.1) converges under an assumption that the inequality $x_3 > y_3$ is valid. This is why we restrict the discussion to the case where C_t is located in $+x_3$ direction of C_s for the present.

Noting (4.2) and (4.3)–(4.5), one can evaluate the integral in (3.14) in the following manner: (See Appendix K.1)

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{S_y} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) C_{cdjln_c}(\mathbf{y}) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &= \frac{1}{8\pi} \sum_{p=1}^{s(\varepsilon)} \sum_{q=1}^{M(p)} \left(X_j^1(p, q; O) \mathcal{F}_{kij}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) + X^2(p, q; O) \mathcal{G}_{ki}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) \right) \\ & \quad e^{-(\lambda_p/d)(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})_3 + i(\lambda_p/d)((\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})_1 \cos \alpha_q(p) + (\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})_2 \sin \alpha_q(p))} \end{aligned}$$

where $X_j^1(p, q; O)$ and $X^2(p, q; O)$ are the coefficients of the exponential expansion at O , defined in terms of the multipole moments (3.53) and (3.54) as

$$X_j^1(p, q; O) = \frac{\omega_p}{M(p)d} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} (-i)^m e^{-im\alpha_q(p)} \sum_{n=|m|}^{\infty} (\lambda_p/d)^n M_{j,n,m}^1(O) \quad (4.28)$$

$$X^2(p, q; O) = \frac{\omega_p}{M(p)d} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} (-i)^m e^{-im\alpha_q(p)} \sum_{n=|m|}^{\infty} (\lambda_p/d)^n M_{n,m}^2(O) \quad (4.29)$$

and \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} are operators defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}_{kij}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) &= \frac{\lambda + 3\mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \delta_{ij} - \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} (\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})_j \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \\ \mathcal{G}_{ki}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) &= \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \end{aligned}$$

These formulae (4.28) and (4.29) convert the multipole moments into the coefficients of the exponential expansion. We call the procedures given by (4.28) and (4.29) ‘‘M2X translation’’. The coefficients of the exponential expansion is translated according to the following formulae when the centre of the exponential expansion is shifted from O to \mathbf{x}_0 : (See Appendix K.2)

$$X_j^1(p, q; \mathbf{x}_0) = X_j^1(p, q; O) e^{-(\lambda_p/d)(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0})_3 + i(\lambda_p/d)((\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0})_1 \cos \alpha_q(p) + (\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0})_2 \sin \alpha_q(p))} \quad (4.30)$$

$$X^2(p, q; \mathbf{x}_0) = (X^2(p, q; O) - (\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0})_k X_k^1(p, q; O)) e^{-(\lambda_p/d)(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0})_3 + i(\lambda_p/d)((\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0})_1 \cos \alpha_q(p) + (\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0})_2 \sin \alpha_q(p))} \quad (4.31)$$

where $X_j^1(p, q; \mathbf{x}_0)$ and $X^2(p, q; \mathbf{x}_0)$ are the coefficients of the exponential expansion at \mathbf{x}_0 and $(\mathbf{x})_i$ stand for the components of the vector \mathbf{x} . We call the procedures given by (4.30) and (4.31) ‘‘X2X translation’’.

We next need to convert the coefficients of the exponential expansion into the coefficients of the local expansion. Noting that the integral in (2.3) is evaluated with $X_j^1(p, q; \mathbf{x}_0)$ and $X^2(p, q; \mathbf{x}_0)$ as follows:

(See Appendix K.3)

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{S_y} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) C_{cdjln_c}(\mathbf{y}) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &= \frac{1}{8\pi} \sum_{p=1}^{s(\varepsilon)} \sum_{q=1}^{M(p)} \left(X_j^1(p, q; \mathbf{x}_0) \mathcal{F}_{kij}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}}) + X^2(p, q; \mathbf{x}_0) \mathcal{G}_{ki}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}}) \right) \\ & \quad e^{-(\lambda_p/d)(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}})_3 + i(\lambda_p/d)((\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}})_1 \cos \alpha_q(p) + (\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}})_2 \sin \alpha_q(p))} \end{aligned}$$

and using (2.9) and (4.9), we obtain the following formulae which convert the coefficients of the exponential expansion into the coefficients of the local expansion (3.60) and (3.61):

$$L_{j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{p=1}^{s(\varepsilon)} \sum_{q=1}^{M(p)} X_j^1(p, q; \mathbf{x}_0) (-i)^m (-\lambda_p/d)^n e^{-im\alpha_q(p)} \quad (4.32)$$

$$L_{n,m}^2(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{p=1}^{s(\varepsilon)} \sum_{q=1}^{M(p)} X^2(p, q; \mathbf{x}_0) (-i)^m (-\lambda_p/d)^n e^{-im\alpha_q(p)} \quad (4.33)$$

We call the procedures given by (4.32) and (4.33) ‘‘X2L translation’’.

The procedures given by (4.28)–(4.33) correspond to the M2L translation given by (3.60) and (3.61) in the original FMM described in 3.3.

4.2.2 Rotation of coefficients

The discussion in the previous section has been restricted to the case where C_t is in $+x_3$ direction of C_s . In this section we shall remove this assumption to generalise the discussion in the same way as in 4.1. If the target cell is included in lists except the uplist of C_s (See Fig.4.2) we rotate the coordinate system so that the target cell is in the positive \tilde{x}_3 direction viewed from the source cell, where \tilde{x}_i denotes the new axis. In general the multipole moments in the new coordinate system are obtained as follows:

$$\widetilde{M}_{j,n,m}^1(O) = \mathcal{A}_{ji} \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m,m'}(\boldsymbol{\nu}, \alpha) M_{i,n,m'}^1(O) \quad (4.34)$$

$$\widetilde{M}_{n,m}^2(O) = \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m,m'}(\boldsymbol{\nu}, \alpha) M_{n,m'}^2(O) \quad (4.35)$$

where $\mathcal{R}_{n,m,m'}(\boldsymbol{\nu}, \alpha)$ is the coefficient of rotation (See (4.12)), $\boldsymbol{\nu}$ is a unit vector parallel to the rotation axis, α is a rotation angle and \mathcal{A}_{ji} is a rotation matrix.

We next describe the generalised M2L translation process in the new FMM.

1. Rotation:

First we rotate the multipole moments via (4.34) and (4.35) so as to make the procedure presented in 4.2.1 applicable. The specific forms of (4.34) and (4.35) depend on the location of C_t and are described as follows:

- $C_t \in$ uplist

$$\widetilde{M}_{j,n,m}^{1U}(O) = \mathcal{A}_{ji}^U M_{i,n,m}^1(O) \quad (4.36)$$

$$\widetilde{M}_{n,m}^{2U}(O) = M_{n,m}^2(O) \quad (4.37)$$

- $C_t \in$ downlist

$$\widetilde{M}_{j,n,m}^{1D}(O) = \mathcal{A}_{ji}^D \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m,m'}(\mathbf{e}_1, \pi) M_{i,n,m'}^1(O) \quad (4.38)$$

$$\widetilde{M}_{n,m}^{2D}(O) = \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m,m'}(\mathbf{e}_1, \pi) M_{n,m'}^2(O) \quad (4.39)$$

- $C_t \in \text{northlist}$

$$\widetilde{M}_{j,n,m}^{1N}(O) = \mathcal{A}_{ji}^N \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m,m'}(\mathbf{e}_1, \pi/2) M_{i,n,m'}^1(O) \quad (4.40)$$

$$\widetilde{M}_{n,m}^{2N}(O) = \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m,m'}(\mathbf{e}_1, \pi/2) M_{n,m'}^2(O) \quad (4.41)$$

- $C_t \in \text{southlist}$

$$\widetilde{M}_{j,n,m}^{1S}(O) = \mathcal{A}_{ji}^S \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m,m'}(\mathbf{e}_1, -\pi/2) M_{i,n,m'}^1(O) \quad (4.42)$$

$$\widetilde{M}_{n,m}^{2S}(O) = \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m,m'}(\mathbf{e}_1, -\pi/2) M_{n,m'}^2(O) \quad (4.43)$$

- $C_t \in \text{eastlist}$

$$\widetilde{M}_{j,n,m}^{1E}(O) = \mathcal{A}_{ji}^E \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m,m'}(\mathbf{e}_2, -\pi/2) M_{i,n,m'}^1(O) \quad (4.44)$$

$$\widetilde{M}_{n,m}^{2E}(O) = \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m,m'}(\mathbf{e}_2, -\pi/2) M_{n,m'}^2(O) \quad (4.45)$$

- $C_t \in \text{westlist}$

$$\widetilde{M}_{j,n,m}^{1W}(O) = \mathcal{A}_{ji}^W \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m,m'}(\mathbf{e}_2, \pi/2) M_{i,n,m'}^1(O) \quad (4.46)$$

$$\widetilde{M}_{n,m}^{2W}(O) = \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m,m'}(\mathbf{e}_2, \pi/2) M_{n,m'}^2(O) \quad (4.47)$$

where \mathbf{e}_i is the base vector for the Cartesian coordinates and superposed indices $\{U, D, N, S, E, W\}$ correspond to the initial letters of $\{\text{uplist, downlist, northlist, southlist, eastlist, westlist}\}$, respectively.

2. Compute the coefficients of the exponential expansion:

Compute the coefficients of the exponential expansion via (4.28) and (4.29) as follows:

$$X_j^{1\Diamond}(p, q; O) = \frac{\omega_p}{M(p)d} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} (-i)^m e^{-im\alpha_q(p)} \sum_{n=|m|}^{\infty} (\lambda_p/d)^n \widetilde{M}_{j,n,m}^{1\Diamond}(O) \quad (4.48)$$

$$X^{2\Diamond}(p, q; O) = \frac{\omega_p}{M(p)d} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} (-i)^m e^{-im\alpha_q(p)} \sum_{n=|m|}^{\infty} (\lambda_p/d)^n \widetilde{M}_{n,m}^{2\Diamond}(O) \quad (4.49)$$

where \Diamond is an element of $\{U, D, N, S, E, W\}$.

3. Translation of the coefficients of the exponential expansion:

As the centre of the exponential expansion is shifted from the centroid of $C_s(O)$ to the centroid of $C_t(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0)$, the coefficients of the exponential expansion are translated according to (4.30) and (4.31) as follows:

$$X_j^{1\Diamond}(p, q; \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0) = X_j^{1\Diamond}(p, q; O) e^{-(\lambda_p/d)(\widetilde{O\mathbf{x}}_0)_3 + i(\lambda_p/d)((\widetilde{O\mathbf{x}}_0)_1 \cos \alpha_q(p) + (\widetilde{O\mathbf{x}}_0)_2 \sin \alpha_q(p))} \quad (4.50)$$

$$X^{2\Diamond}(p, q; \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0) = (X^{2\Diamond}(p, q; O) - X_k^{1\Diamond}(p, q; O)(\widetilde{O\mathbf{x}}_0)_k) e^{-(\lambda_p/d)(\widetilde{O\mathbf{x}}_0)_3 + i(\lambda_p/d)((\widetilde{O\mathbf{x}}_0)_1 \cos \alpha_q(p) + (\widetilde{O\mathbf{x}}_0)_2 \sin \alpha_q(p))} \quad (4.51)$$

$$(\widetilde{O\mathbf{x}}_0)_i = A_{ij}^{\Diamond}(\widetilde{O\mathbf{x}}_0)_j$$

where \Diamond is an element of $\{U, D, N, S, E, W\}$.

4. Compute the coefficients of the local expansion:

Compute the coefficients of the local expansion from the exponential expansion according to (4.32) and (4.33) as follows:

$$\tilde{L}_{j,n,m}^{1\Diamond}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0) = \sum_{p=1}^{s(\varepsilon)} \sum_{q=1}^{M(p)} X_j^{1\Diamond}(p, q; \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0) (-i)^m (-\lambda_p/d)^n e^{-im\alpha_q(p)} \quad (4.52)$$

$$\tilde{L}_{n,m}^{2\Diamond}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0) = \sum_{p=1}^{s(\varepsilon)} \sum_{q=1}^{M(p)} X^{2\Diamond}(p, q; \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0) (-i)^m (-\lambda_p/d)^n e^{-im\alpha_q(p)} \quad (4.53)$$

where \Diamond is an element of $\{U, D, N, S, E, W\}$. Then rotate $\tilde{L}_{n,m}^{\Diamond}$ as follows:

- $C_t \in \text{uplist}$

$$L_{j,n,m}^{1U}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \mathcal{A}_{ij}^U \tilde{L}_{i,n,m}^{1U}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0) \quad (4.54)$$

$$L_{n,m}^{2U}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \tilde{L}_{n,m}^{2U}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0) \quad (4.55)$$

- $C_t \in \text{downlist}$

$$L_{j,n,m}^{1D}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \mathcal{A}_{ij}^D \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m',m}(\mathbf{e}_1, \pi) \tilde{L}_{i,n,m'}^{1D}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0) \quad (4.56)$$

$$L_{n,m}^{2D}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m',m}(\mathbf{e}_1, \pi) \tilde{L}_{n,m'}^{2D}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0) \quad (4.57)$$

- $C_t \in \text{northlist}$

$$L_{j,n,m}^{1N}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \mathcal{A}_{ij}^N \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m',m}(\mathbf{e}_1, \pi/2) \tilde{L}_{i,n,m'}^{1N}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0) \quad (4.58)$$

$$L_{n,m}^{2N}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m',m}(\mathbf{e}_1, \pi/2) \tilde{L}_{n,m'}^{2N}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0) \quad (4.59)$$

- $C_t \in \text{southlist}$

$$L_{j,n,m}^{1S}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \mathcal{A}_{ij}^S \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m',m}(\mathbf{e}_1, -\pi/2) \tilde{L}_{i,n,m'}^{1S}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0) \quad (4.60)$$

$$L_{n,m}^{2S}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m',m}(\mathbf{e}_1, -\pi/2) \tilde{L}_{n,m'}^{2S}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0) \quad (4.61)$$

- $C_t \in \text{eastlist}$

$$L_{j,n,m}^{1E}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \mathcal{A}_{ij}^E \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m',m}(\mathbf{e}_2, -\pi/2) \tilde{L}_{i,n,m'}^{1E}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0) \quad (4.62)$$

$$L_{n,m}^{2E}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m',m}(\mathbf{e}_2, -\pi/2) \tilde{L}_{n,m'}^{2E}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0) \quad (4.63)$$

- $C_t \in \text{westlist}$

$$L_{j,n,m}^{1W}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \mathcal{A}_{ij}^W \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m',m}(\mathbf{e}_2, \pi/2) \tilde{L}_{i,n,m'}^{1W}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0) \quad (4.64)$$

$$L_{n,m}^{2W}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{m'=-n}^n \mathcal{R}_{n,m',m}(\mathbf{e}_2, \pi/2) \tilde{L}_{n,m'}^{2W}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0) \quad (4.65)$$

Finally add L^U, L^D, L^N, L^S, L^E and L^W together

$$L_{j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{\Diamond \in U, D, N, S, E, W} L_{j,n,m}^{1\Diamond}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0) \quad (4.66)$$

$$L_{n,m}^2(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{\Diamond \in U, D, N, S, E, W} L_{n,m}^{2\Diamond}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0) \quad (4.67)$$

to obtain the coefficients of the local expansion.

4.2.3 Algorithm for the new FM-BIEM

The algorithm for the new FMM is given as follows:

Steps 1–3. Same as the steps 1–3 in the algorithm described in 3.3.

Step 4. Computation of the coefficients of the exponential expansion:

Compute the coefficients of the exponential expansion at each cell using (4.36)–(4.49), taking the origin (O) at the centroid of the cell.

Step 5. Computation of the coefficients of the local expansion:

We compute the coefficients of the local expansion of cells of level l , starting from $l = 2$ and increasing l . Now we consider a cell C and another cell C' which is contained in the interaction list of C . Considering the position of C' relative to C , we translate the coefficients of the exponential expansion via (4.50) and (4.51) as the centre of the exponential expansion is shifted from the centroid of C (O) to that of C' (\mathbf{x}_0) and then use appropriate formulae in (4.52)–(4.65) to convert the coefficients of the exponential expansion to the coefficients of the local expansion. After carrying out these conversions about all cells in the interaction list of C , we add them together via (4.66) and (4.67) to obtain the contribution from the interaction list of C to the coefficients of the local expansion. To these contributions we add the coefficients of the local expansion of the parent of C with the origin shifted from the centroid of the parent (\mathbf{x}_0) to that of C (\mathbf{x}_1) via (3.64) and (3.65) to obtain the coefficients of the local expansion associated with C .

Step 6. Evaluation of the integral in (3.46):

This step is the same as the step 5 in the algorithm described in 3.3.

4.2.4 Numerical examples

The proposed techniques have been implemented in Fortran 77 and have been tested on a computer having a DEC Alpha 21264(500 MHz) as the CPU. The integrals in the multipole moments in (3.53) and (3.54) are computed numerically with Gaussian quadrature. The sums in the finite series (3.52) and (3.59) are truncated at 10 terms and the series in (4.48), (4.49), (4.52) and (4.53) are computed with the 109 point generalised Gaussian quadrature formula given in Yarvin and Rokhlin [83]. The maximum number of boundary elements in a leaf is set to be 100. To solve the resulting matrix equation we use the preconditioned GMRES and adopt the block diagonal matrix corresponding to the leaves as the preconditioner according to Nishida and Hayami [62]. In GMRES the iteration is stopped when the relative residual norm is below 10^{-5} .

One penny-shaped crack

In the beginning we consider an infinite space which contains a penny-shaped crack having the radius of a_0 and the unit normal vector of $\mathbf{n} = (0, 0, 1)$. The function $\mathbf{t}^\infty(\mathbf{x})$ is given by $\mathbf{t}^\infty(\mathbf{x}) = \boldsymbol{\sigma}^\infty(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{n}(\mathbf{x})$ where

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^\infty(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & p_0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4.68)$$

and, hence, $\mathbf{t}^\infty = (0, 0, p_0)$. The asymptotic condition (4.68) indicates that the domain is subjected to a uniform uniaxial tension. Also, Poisson's ratio is set to be 0.25; i.e. $\lambda = \mu$. This problem is solved with the conventional BIEM, the original FM-BIEM and the new FM-BIEM. Fig.4.8 plots the non-dimensional crack opening displacement $\mu\phi_3/a_0p_0$ obtained with this mesh. In Fig.4.8 the symbols marked "conv", "fmm" and "newfmm" indicate numerical results computed with the conventional BIEM, the original FM-BIEM and the new FM-BIEM, respectively. This figure shows a good agreement between these numerical results. Fig.4.9 plots the total CPU time (sec) vs the number of unknowns. In Fig.4.9 the lines marked "Tdir", "Tfmm" and "Tfmmnew" indicate the CPU time required with the conventional BIEM, the original FM-BIEM and the new FM-BIEM, respectively. This figure shows that the new FM-BIEM is only slightly faster than the original FM-BIEM. As in the Laplace case, this is because this example is essentially a two-dimensional one where the computational cost for the M2L translation is not dominant. In order to show the efficiency of the new FMM more clearly we need to consider an example where boundary elements are distributed three-dimensionally. Therefore we consider many crack problems in the next example.

Many penny-shaped cracks

We now consider an infinite space which contains an array of penny-shaped cracks, each having the same radius a_0 , subjected to the same asymptotic condition as in the previous example. The centroids of these cracks are located at the same interval of $4a_0$ in each coordinate direction, but the direction of each crack is taken random. First, we consider an array of $8 \times 8 \times 8 (= 512)$ penny-shaped cracks in the infinite domain. Fig.4.10 plots the total CPU time (sec) required by the original FM-BIEM and the new FM-BIEM with this array. In Fig.4.10 the lines marked ‘Tfmm’ and ‘Tfmmnew’ indicate the CPU times required with the original FM-BIEM and the new FM-BIEM, respectively. Next we consider an infinite space which contains an array of $12 \times 12 \times 12 (= 1728)$ penny-shaped cracks (total DOF=1,285,632) in the infinite domain. Fig.4.11 plots the non-dimensional crack opening displacement ($\mu\phi/a_0p_0$) on the non-dimensional mesh \mathbf{x}/a_0 . The required CPU times with the original FM-BIEM and the new FM-BIEM are 13954(sec) and 8290(sec), respectively. In this example the error defined as

$$\text{Error} = \frac{\|\tilde{\phi} - \phi\|}{\|\phi\|}$$

is 9.09×10^{-4} , where $\tilde{\phi}$ is the numerical solution obtained with the new FM-BIEM, ϕ the one obtained with the original FM-BIEM and $\|\cdot\|$ denotes the L_2 -norm. These results show that the new FM-BIEM is more efficient than the original FM-BIEM when distribution of the boundary elements is dense in the domain.

Figure 4.8: Crack opening displacement

Figure 4.9: CPU time (sec)

Figure 4.10: CPU time (sec)

Figure 4.11: Crack opening displacement (DOF=1,285,632)

4.3 Concluding remarks

- In chapter 4 we have successfully applied the new FMM to crack problems for Laplace's equation and elastostatics and have shown that the new FMM is faster than the original FMM in these problems. The improvement has been found to be particularly remarkable in problems including many cracks.
- In chapter 4 we have investigated improvements of the M2L operations. But we did not implement techniques to reduce M2M and L2L translations. However, the improved implementation of M2M and L2L translations is not very difficult and will not be as effective as the M2L.
- The fast multipole algorithm employed in this thesis is somewhat simpler but may not necessarily be as efficient as the so-called "adaptive algorithm" used in Cheng et al. [11]. Their adaptive algorithm improves the efficiency by replacing some of direct evaluations used in the present implementation by either multipole moments or local expansions. The algorithm used in this thesis may not be very efficient in problems, where the distribution of boundary elements is far from uniform. Hence, we plan to implement "adaptive algorithm" in the future work.
- In the future work we plan to apply the new FMM and Rokhlin's diagonal form to dynamic problems. The new FMM for Helmholtz's equation based on the integral representation for the fundamental solution of Helmholtz's equation has been proposed by Greengard et al. [34]. The new FMM for Helmholtz's equation can be extended to elastodynamics straightforwardly. Rokhlin's diagonal form seems to work better in high frequency problems than the new FMM, although it has numerical instabilities in low frequency problems. Therefore we must make the proper use of the new FMM and Rokhlin's diagonal form according to the magnitude of the wave number and the scale of a problems. At the final stage of applications of FM-BIEM to dynamic problems we plan to use the hybrid FMM obtained by combination of the new FMM and the diagonal form.

Chapter 5

Final remarks

In this thesis the author has investigated applications of FMM to BIEM for crack problems in three dimensions. The results obtained in this thesis are sufficient to make the author believe that the first step is steadily taken toward practical applications.

The results obtained in this thesis are summarised as follows:

- In chapter 3 FM-BIEM has been successfully applied to crack problems in Laplace's equation, elastostatics, Helmholtz's equation and elastodynamics and the efficiencies of FMM in BIEM have been shown. The results show the potential of the FM-BIEM for large-scale problems in fractures mechanics.
- In chapter 4 the author has succeeded in applications of the new FMM to crack problems for Laplace's equation and elastostatics and has shown that the new FMM is faster than the original FMM in these problems. The improvement has been found to be particularly remarkable in problems including many cracks.
- One can use techniques proposed in this thesis in ordinary problems where the single- and double-layer potentials are used as well as in crack problems. Hence, FM-BIEM has various applications.

As the future work the author has plans to

- apply FM-BIEM to analyses of dynamic response characteristics of underground structures which are crossing three-dimensionally.
- apply FM-BIEM to growths of many cracks.
- use various techniques such as the diagonal form and the new FMM to achieve further reduction of the computational cost.
- apply FM-BIEM to large-scale problems of the order of 10^{7-8} unknowns using libraries for the parallel implementation such as MPI (Message Passing Interface) or PVM (Parallel Virtual Machine). Notice that a 10^7 DOF problem in BIEM corresponds to a 10^{10} DOF problem in FEM when one deals with linear problems in a cubic domain using the same mesh.

Nowadays, FEM and FDM seem to have established the representative positions as numerical solvers for PDEs. On the other hand, BIEM has been applied only to small problems so far because of the full matrix property. However, in this thesis FMM gives BIEM opportunities to become a solver for large-scale problems. Indeed, techniques proposed in elastostatics and elastodynamics have the potential in ordinary large-scale boundary value problems as well as fracture mechanics, and could help to raise the status of BIEM. The author hopes that BIEM becomes a practical solver and would be happy if this thesis could be of some help to someone or could contribute to BIEM community.

Appendix A

Series expansion of $\frac{1}{|\mathbf{x}-\mathbf{y}|}$

Now we take two points \mathbf{y} and \mathbf{x} whose spherical coordinates are (ρ, α, β) and (r, ϕ, θ) . The inverse of the distance between \mathbf{y} and \mathbf{x} can be expanded into the following series [61]

$$\frac{1}{|\mathbf{x}-\mathbf{y}|} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=0}^n \varepsilon_m \frac{(n-m)!}{(n+m)!} P_n^m(\cos \alpha) P_n^m(\cos \theta) \cos m(\beta - \phi) \frac{\rho^n}{r^{n+1}}, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where ε_m is the Neumann factor; $\varepsilon_0 = 1, \varepsilon_i = 2(i = 1, 2, 3, \dots)$ and $P_n^m(x)$ is the associated Legendre function. In this thesis the associated Legendre function is defined by

$$P_n^m(x) = (1-x^2)^{m/2} \frac{d^m}{dx^m} P_n(x) \quad (m \geq 0),$$

where $P_n(x)$ is the Legendre function and the associated Legendre function has the following properties:

$$P_n^m(\cos \theta) = 0, \quad (n < |m|) \quad (\text{A.2})$$

$$P_n^{-m}(\cos \theta) = (-1)^m \frac{(n-m)!}{(n+m)!} P_n^m(\cos \theta) \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$P_n^m(-\cos \theta) = (-1)^{n+m} P_n^m(\cos \theta) \quad (\text{A.4})$$

The right-hand side in (A.1) can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{|\mathbf{x}-\mathbf{y}|} &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=0}^n \varepsilon_m \frac{(n-m)!}{(n+m)!} P_n^m(\cos \alpha) P_n^m(\cos \theta) \cos m(\beta - \phi) \frac{\rho^n}{r^{n+1}} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P_n^0(\cos \alpha) P_n^0(\cos \theta) \frac{\rho^n}{r^{n+1}} + 2 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=1}^n \frac{(n-m)!}{(n+m)!} P_n^m(\cos \alpha) P_n^m(\cos \theta) \cos m(\beta - \phi) \frac{\rho^n}{r^{n+1}} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P_n^0(\cos \alpha) P_n^0(\cos \theta) \frac{\rho^n}{r^{n+1}} \\ &\quad + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=1}^n \frac{(n-m)!}{(n+m)!} P_n^m(\cos \alpha) P_n^m(\cos \theta) (e^{-im(\beta-\phi)} + e^{im(\beta-\phi)}) \frac{\rho^n}{r^{n+1}} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P_n^0(\cos \alpha) P_n^0(\cos \theta) \frac{\rho^n}{r^{n+1}} + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=1}^n \frac{(n-m)!}{(n+m)!} P_n^m(\cos \alpha) P_n^m(\cos \theta) e^{-im(\beta-\phi)} \frac{\rho^n}{r^{n+1}} \\ &\quad + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=1}^n \frac{(n-m)!}{(n+m)!} P_n^m(\cos \alpha) P_n^m(\cos \theta) e^{im(\beta-\phi)} \frac{\rho^n}{r^{n+1}} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P_n^0(\cos \alpha) P_n^0(\cos \theta) \frac{\rho^n}{r^{n+1}} + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-1}^{-n} \frac{(n+m)!}{(n-m)!} P_n^{-m}(\cos \alpha) P_n^{-m}(\cos \theta) e^{im(\beta-\phi)} \frac{\rho^n}{r^{n+1}} \\ &\quad + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=1}^n \frac{(n-m)!}{(n+m)!} P_n^m(\cos \alpha) P_n^m(\cos \theta) e^{im(\beta-\phi)} \frac{\rho^n}{r^{n+1}} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P_n^0(\cos \alpha) P_n^0(\cos \theta) \frac{\rho^n}{r^{n+1}} + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-1}^{-n} \frac{(n-m)!}{(n+m)!} P_n^m(\cos \alpha) P_n^m(\cos \theta) e^{im(\beta-\phi)} \frac{\rho^n}{r^{n+1}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=1}^n \frac{(n-m)!}{(n+m)!} P_n^m(\cos \alpha) P_n^m(\cos \theta) e^{im(\beta-\phi)} \frac{\rho^n}{r^{n+1}} \\
& = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \frac{(n-m)!}{(n+m)!} P_n^m(\cos \alpha) P_n^m(\cos \theta) e^{im(\beta-\phi)} \frac{\rho^n}{r^{n+1}} \\
& = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n R_{n,m}(\vec{Oy}) \overline{S_{n,m}(\vec{Ox})} \\
& = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \overline{R_{n,m}(\vec{Oy})} S_{n,m}(\vec{Ox})
\end{aligned}$$

where we have used (A.3) and functions $R_{n,m}(\vec{Oy})$ and $S_{n,m}(\vec{Ox})$ are defined by

$$\begin{aligned}
R_{n,m}(\vec{Oy}) & = \frac{1}{(n+m)!} P_n^m(\cos \alpha) e^{im\beta} \rho^n, \\
S_{n,m}(\vec{Ox}) & = (n-m)! P_n^m(\cos \theta) e^{im\phi} \frac{1}{r^{n+1}}
\end{aligned}$$

The solid harmonics $R_{n,m}$ and $S_{n,m}$ have the following properties.

$$\begin{aligned}
R_{n,-m}(\vec{Ox}) & = \frac{1}{(n-m)!} P_n^{-m}(\cos \theta) e^{-im\phi} r^n = \frac{1}{(n-m)!} (-1)^m \frac{(n-m)!}{(n+m)!} P_n^m(\cos \theta) e^{-im\phi} r^n \\
& = (-1)^m \frac{1}{(n+m)!} P_n^m(\cos \theta) e^{-im\phi} r^n = (-1)^m \overline{R_{n,m}(\vec{Ox})}
\end{aligned} \tag{A.5}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
S_{n,-m}(\vec{Ox}) & = \frac{(n+m)!}{r^{n+1}} P_n^{-m}(\cos \theta) e^{-im\phi} = \frac{(n+m)!}{r^{n+1}} (-1)^m \frac{(n-m)!}{(n+m)!} P_n^m(\cos \theta) e^{-im\phi} \\
& = (-1)^m \frac{(n-m)!}{r^{n+1}} P_n^m(\cos \theta) e^{-im\phi} = (-1)^m \overline{S_{n,m}(\vec{Ox})}
\end{aligned} \tag{A.6}$$

where we have used (A.3), and

$$\begin{aligned}
R_{n,m}(\vec{xO}) & = \frac{1}{(n+m)!} P_n^m(\cos(\theta + \pi)) e^{im(\phi+\pi)} r^n = \frac{1}{(n+m)!} P_n^m(-\cos \theta) (-1)^m e^{im\phi} r^n \\
& = \frac{1}{(n+m)!} (-1)^{n+m} P_n^m(\cos \theta) (-1)^m e^{im\phi} r^n = (-1)^n R_{n,m}(\vec{Ox})
\end{aligned} \tag{A.7}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
S_{n,m}(\vec{xO}) & = \frac{(n-m)!}{r^{n+1}} P_n^m(\cos(\theta + \pi)) e^{im(\phi+\pi)} = \frac{(n-m)!}{r^{n+1}} P_n^m(-\cos \theta) (-1)^m e^{im\phi} \\
& = \frac{(n-m)!}{r^{n+1}} (-1)^{n+m} P_n^m(\cos \theta) (-1)^m e^{im\phi} = (-1)^n S_{n,m}(\vec{Ox})
\end{aligned} \tag{A.8}$$

where we have used (A.4).

Appendix B

Relations between solid harmonics

$R_{n,m}$ and $S_{n,m}$

Noting the following formulae (See Hobson [43] or Wallace [80]):

$$S_{n,m}(\vec{O}\mathbf{x}) = (-1)^n \partial_{x_+}^m \partial_{x_3}^{n-m} \left(\frac{1}{|\vec{O}\mathbf{x}|} \right) \quad (m \geq 0), \quad (\text{B.1})$$

$$S_{n,-m}(\vec{O}\mathbf{x}) = (-1)^m \overline{S_{n,m}(\vec{O}\mathbf{x})} = (-1)^{n+m} \partial_{x_-}^m \partial_{x_3}^{n-m} \left(\frac{1}{|\vec{O}\mathbf{x}|} \right) \quad (m > 0), \quad (\text{B.2})$$

$$\partial_{x_{\pm}} = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} \pm i \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} \right), \quad (\text{B.3})$$

$$\partial_{x_+} \partial_{x_-} (\text{Harmonics}) = -\partial_{x_3}^2 (\text{Harmonics}) \quad (\text{B.4})$$

one can transform $S_{n,m}(\vec{O}\mathbf{x})$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{n,m}(\vec{O}\mathbf{x}) &= (-1)^n \partial_{x_+}^m \partial_{x_3}^{n-m} \left(\frac{1}{|\vec{O}\mathbf{x}|} \right) \\ &= (-1)^n \partial_{x_+}^m \partial_{x_3}^{n-m} \left(\sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \overline{S_{n',m'}(\vec{y}\mathbf{x})} R_{n',m'}(\vec{y}\vec{O}) \right), \quad |\vec{y}\mathbf{x}| > |\vec{y}\vec{O}| \\ &= (-1)^n \partial_{x_+}^m \partial_{x_3}^{n-m} \left(\sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=0}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\vec{y}\vec{O}) (-1)^{n'} \partial_{X_-}^{m'} \partial_{X_3}^{n'-m'} \left(\frac{1}{|\vec{y}\mathbf{x}|} \right) \right) \\ &+ (-1)^n \partial_{x_+}^m \partial_{x_3}^{n-m} \left(\sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=1}^{n'} R_{n',-m'}(\vec{y}\vec{O}) (-1)^{n'+m'} \partial_{X_+}^{m'} \partial_{X_3}^{n'-m'} \left(\frac{1}{|\vec{y}\mathbf{x}|} \right) \right) \\ &\quad (\text{where } X_i = x_i - y_i) \\ &= \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=0}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\vec{y}\vec{O}) (-1)^{n'+n} \partial_{X_+}^m \partial_{X_-}^{m'} \partial_{X_3}^{n+n'-m-m'} \left(\frac{1}{|\vec{y}\mathbf{x}|} \right) \\ &+ \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=1}^{n'} (-1)^{m'} R_{n',-m'}(\vec{y}\vec{O}) (-1)^{n+n'} \partial_{X_+}^{m+m'} \partial_{X_3}^{n+n'-m-m'} \left(\frac{1}{|\vec{y}\mathbf{x}|} \right) \\ &= \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=0}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\vec{y}\vec{O}) (-1)^{n'+n} \partial_{X_+}^m \partial_{X_-}^{m'} \partial_{X_3}^{n+n'-m-m'} \left(\frac{1}{|\vec{y}\mathbf{x}|} \right) \quad (a) \\ &+ \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=1}^{n'} \overline{R_{n',m'}(\vec{y}\vec{O})} S_{n+n,m+m'}(\vec{y}\mathbf{x}), \end{aligned}$$

where we have used (A.5) and the chain rule:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial X_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial x_k}{\partial X_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}.$$

The underlined part (a) can be rewritten as follows:

In the case where $m \geq m'$

$$\begin{aligned} & R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathcal{O}})(-1)^{n'+n} \partial_{X_+}^m \partial_{X_-}^{m'} \partial_{X_3}^{n+n'-m-m'} \left(\frac{1}{|\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathbf{x}}|} \right) \\ &= R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathcal{O}})(-1)^{n'+n} \partial_{X_+}^{m-m'} (\partial_{X_+}^{m'} \partial_{X_-}^{m'}) \partial_{X_3}^{n+n'-m-m'} \left(\frac{1}{|\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathbf{x}}|} \right) \\ &= R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathcal{O}})(-1)^{n'+n} \partial_{X_+}^{m-m'} (-\partial_{X_3}^2)^{m'} \partial_{X_3}^{n+n'-m-m'} \left(\frac{1}{|\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathbf{x}}|} \right) \\ &= (-1)^{m'} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathcal{O}})(-1)^{n'+n} \partial_{X_+}^{m-m'} \partial_{X_3}^{n+n'-m+m'} \left(\frac{1}{|\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathbf{x}}|} \right) \\ &= \overline{R_{n',-m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathcal{O}})} S_{n+n',m-m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathbf{x}}). \end{aligned}$$

In the case where $m' < m$

$$\begin{aligned} & R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathcal{O}})(-1)^{n'+n} \partial_{X_+}^m \partial_{X_-}^{m'} \partial_{X_3}^{n+n'-m-m'} \left(\frac{1}{|\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathbf{x}}|} \right) \\ &= R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathcal{O}})(-1)^{n'+n} \partial_{X_-}^{m'-m} (\partial_{X_+}^m \partial_{X_-}^m) \partial_{X_3}^{n+n'-m-m'} \left(\frac{1}{|\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathbf{x}}|} \right) \\ &= R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathcal{O}})(-1)^{n'+n} \partial_{X_-}^{m'-m} (-\partial_{X_3}^2)^m \partial_{X_3}^{n+n'-m-m'} \left(\frac{1}{|\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathbf{x}}|} \right) \\ &= (-1)^m R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathcal{O}})(-1)^{n'+n} \partial_{X_-}^{m'-m} \partial_{X_3}^{n+n'+m-m'} \left(\frac{1}{|\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathbf{x}}|} \right) \\ &= (-1)^{m'} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathcal{O}})(-1)^{n'+n+m'-m} \partial_{X_-}^{m'-m} \partial_{X_3}^{n+n'+m-m'} \left(\frac{1}{|\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathbf{x}}|} \right) \\ &= \overline{R_{n',-m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathcal{O}})} S_{n+n',m-m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathbf{x}}). \end{aligned}$$

As a result, the underlined part (a) can be rewritten as

$$(a) = \overline{R_{n',-m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathcal{O}})} S_{n+n',m-m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathbf{x}}).$$

Hence one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{x}}) &= \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=0}^{n'} \overline{R_{n',-m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathcal{O}})} S_{n+n',m-m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathbf{x}}) + \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=1}^{n'} \overline{R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathcal{O}})} S_{n+n',m+m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathbf{x}}) \\ &= \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^0 \overline{R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathcal{O}})} S_{n+n',m+m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathbf{x}}) + \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=1}^{n'} \overline{R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathcal{O}})} S_{n+n',m+m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathbf{x}}) \\ &= \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \overline{R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathcal{O}})} S_{n+n',m+m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathbf{x}}), \quad |\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathbf{x}}| > |\overrightarrow{\mathbf{y}\mathcal{O}}|. \end{aligned} \tag{B.5}$$

Now take two points O and O' where two inequalities $|\overrightarrow{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{y}}| < |\overrightarrow{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{x}}|$ and $|\overrightarrow{\mathbf{O}'\mathbf{y}}| < |\overrightarrow{\mathbf{O}'\mathbf{x}}|$ are valid and consider the following identity:

$$\left(\frac{1}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} \right) \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{y}}) \overline{S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{x}})} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{O}'\mathbf{y}}) \overline{S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{O}'\mathbf{x}})}. \tag{B.6}$$

From (B.5) we obtain the following formula:

$$\overline{S_{n,m}}(\overrightarrow{Ox}) = \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{O'O}) \overline{S_{n+n',m+m'}}(\overrightarrow{O'x}). \quad (\text{B.7})$$

Substituting (B.7) into the left-hand side of (B.6), one obtains

$$\text{LHS of (B.6)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{Oy}) \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{O'O}) \overline{S_{n+n',m+m'}}(\overrightarrow{O'x}). \quad (\text{B.8})$$

Setting $n + n' = n''$, $m + m' = m''$ and deleting n in (B.8), one has

$$\begin{aligned} \text{LHS of (B.6)} &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{Oy}) R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{O'O}) \overline{S_{n+n',m+m'}}(\overrightarrow{O'x}) \\ &= \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \sum_{n''=n'}^{\infty} \sum_{m''=-n''}^{n''} R_{n''-n',m''-m'}(\overrightarrow{Oy}) R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{O'O}) \overline{S_{n'',m''}}(\overrightarrow{O'x}). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.9})$$

Exchanging the order of the summation in (B.9) ($\sum_{n'} \sum_{n''} \rightarrow \sum_{n''} \sum_{n'}$, See Fig.B), one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} \text{LHS side of (B.6)} &= \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \sum_{n''=n'}^{\infty} \sum_{m''=-n''}^{n''} R_{n''-n',m''-m'}(\overrightarrow{Oy}) R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{O'O}) \overline{S_{n'',m''}}(\overrightarrow{O'x}) \\ &= \sum_{n''=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m''=-n''}^{n''} \sum_{n'=0}^{n''} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n''-n',m''-m'}(\overrightarrow{Oy}) R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{O'O}) \overline{S_{n'',m''}}(\overrightarrow{O'x}) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n-n',m-m'}(\overrightarrow{Oy}) R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{O'O}) \overline{S_{n,m}}(\overrightarrow{O'x}). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.10})$$

Finally, comparing the right-hand side of (B.6) with that of (B.10) one obtains the following formula:

$$R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{Oy}) = \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n-n',m-m'}(\overrightarrow{Oy}) R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{O'O}) \quad (\text{B.11})$$

Figure B.1: Exchange of indices

Appendix C

Recurrence formulae for $R_{n,m}$ and $S_{n,m}$

The associated Legendre function P_n^m has the following recurrence formulae:

$$(n-m+1)P_{n+1}^m(\cos\theta) - (2n+1)\cos\theta P_n^m(\cos\theta) + (n+m)P_{n-1}^m(\cos\theta) = 0, \quad (\text{C.1})$$

$$\cos\theta P_n^m(\cos\theta) - P_{n+1}^m(\cos\theta) + (n+m)\sin\theta P_{n,m-1}(\cos\theta) = 0. \quad (\text{C.2})$$

Multiplying (C.1) by $r^{n+1}e^{im\phi}$ one obtains

$$(n+m+1)(n+1-m)R_{n+1,m} - (2n+1)x_3R_{n,m} + r^2R_{n-1,m} = 0.$$

Multiplying (C.2) by $r^{n+1}e^{im\phi}$, setting $m = n+1$ and using (A.2) one obtains

$$R_{n+1,n+1} = \frac{x_1 + ix_2}{2(n+1)}R_{n,n}.$$

In the same manner, one has

$$r^2S_{n+1,m} - (2n+1)x_3S_{n,m} + (n+m)(n-m)S_{n-1,m} = 0.$$

$$S_{n+1,n+1} = \frac{(2n+1)(x_1 + ix_2)}{r^2}S_{n,n}.$$

Using above formulae one can compute $R_{n,m}$ and $S_{n,m}$ as follows:

- Computation of $R_{n,m}$

1. $R_{0,0} = 1$.
2. Compute $R_{n,n}$ recursively for $n = 1, 2, \dots, P$ using

$$R_{n+1,n+1} = \frac{x_1 + ix_2}{2(n+1)}R_{n,n}. \quad (\text{C.3})$$

3. For a fixed m use the following formula:

$$(n+m+1)(n+1-m)R_{n+1,m} - (2n+1)x_3R_{n,m} + r^2R_{n-1,m} = 0 \quad (n \geq m) \quad (\text{C.4})$$

to compute $R_{n,m}$ recursively for $n = m, m+1, \dots, P$.

- Computation of $S_{n,m}$

1. $S_{0,0} = 1/r$.
2. Compute $S_{n,n}$ recursively for $n = 1, 2, \dots, P$ using

$$S_{n+1,n+1} = \frac{(2n+1)(x_1 + ix_2)}{r^2}S_{n,n}.$$

3. For a fixed m use the following formula:

$$r^2S_{n+1,m} - (2n+1)x_3S_{n,m} + (n+m)(n-m)S_{n-1,m} = 0$$

to compute $S_{n,m}$ recursively for $n = m, m+1, \dots, P$.

- Functions $R_{n,m}$ and $S_{n,m}$ for a negative m can be computed via (A.5) and (A.6).

Appendix D

Derivatives of $R_{n,m}$ and $S_{n,m}$

We introduce a vector \vec{Ox} which has components (x_1, x_2, x_3) in the Cartesian coordinates and (r, ϕ, θ) in the polar coordinates. Relations between (x_1, x_2, x_3) and (r, ϕ, θ) are expressed as

$$x_1 = r \cos \phi \sin \theta, \quad x_2 = r \sin \phi \sin \theta, \quad x_3 = r \cos \theta,$$

$$r = \sqrt{x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2}, \quad \phi = \tan^{-1} \frac{x_2}{x_1}, \quad \theta = \tan^{-1} \frac{\sqrt{x_1^2 + x_2^2}}{x_3}.$$

According to the chain rule, we have the following relations:

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} + i \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} \right) = \left(\frac{\partial r}{\partial x_1} + i \frac{\partial r}{\partial x_2} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial r} + \left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x_1} + i \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x_2} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} + \left(\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x_1} + i \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x_2} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta},$$

the coefficients of which are given as

$$\left(\frac{\partial r}{\partial x_1} + i \frac{\partial r}{\partial x_2} \right) = \sin \theta e^{i\phi}, \quad \left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x_1} + i \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x_2} \right) = \frac{i}{r \sin \theta} e^{i\phi}, \quad \left(\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x_1} + i \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x_2} \right) = \frac{\cos \theta}{r} e^{i\phi}.$$

Now we compute $\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} + i \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} \right) R_{n,m}$ for example.

$$\begin{aligned} & (n+m)! \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} + i \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} \right) R_{n,m} \\ &= \left(\left(\frac{\partial r}{\partial x_1} + i \frac{\partial r}{\partial x_2} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial r} + \left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x_1} + i \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x_2} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} + \left(\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x_1} + i \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x_2} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \right) (r^n P_n^m(\cos \theta) e^{im\phi}) \\ &= \sin \theta n r^{n-1} P_n^m(\cos \theta) e^{i(m+1)\phi} - \frac{1}{\sin \theta} m r^{n-1} P_n^m(\cos \theta) e^{i(m+1)\phi} + \cos \theta r^{n-1} \frac{\partial P_n^m(\cos \theta)}{\partial \theta} e^{i(m+1)\phi} \\ &= -r^{n-1} P_{n-1}^{m+1} e^{i(m+1)\phi} \Rightarrow \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} + i \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} \right) R_{n,m} = -R_{n-1,m+1}, \end{aligned} \quad (D.1)$$

where we have used standard formulae given by

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial P_n^m(\cos \theta)}{\partial \theta} &= -P_n^{m+1}(\cos \theta) + m \frac{\cos \theta}{\sin \theta} P_n^m(\cos \theta), \\ (n-m) \sin \theta P_n^m(\cos \theta) - \cos \theta P_n^{m+1}(\cos \theta) &= -P_{n-1}^{m+1}(\cos \theta). \end{aligned}$$

In the same way we obtain formulae given by

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} - i \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} \right) R_{n,m} = R_{n-1,m-1}, \quad (D.2)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_3} R_{n,m} = R_{n-1,m}. \quad (D.3)$$

We can rewrite (D.1), (D.2), (D.3) as

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} R_{n,m} = \frac{1}{2} (R_{n-1,m-1} - R_{n-1,m+1}), \quad (D.4)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} R_{n,m} = \frac{i}{2} (R_{n-1,m-1} + R_{n-1,m+1}), \quad (D.5)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_3} R_{n,m} = R_{n-1,m}. \quad (D.6)$$

Derivatives of $S_{n,m}$ can be obtained in the similar manner as follows:

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} + i\frac{\partial}{\partial x_2}\right) S_{n,m} = -S_{n+1,m+1}, \quad (\text{D.7})$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} - i\frac{\partial}{\partial x_2}\right) S_{n,m} = S_{n+1,m-1}, \quad (\text{D.8})$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} S_{n,m} = \frac{1}{2}(S_{n+1,m-1} - S_{n+1,m+1}), \quad (\text{D.9})$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} S_{n,m} = \frac{i}{2}(S_{n+1,m+1} + S_{n+1,m-1}), \quad (\text{D.10})$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_3} S_{n,m} = -S_{n+1,m}. \quad (\text{D.11})$$

Appendix E

M2M, M2L, L2L in three-dimensional Laplace's equation

E.1 M2M translation formula

The multipole moment centred at O' is given by (See (3.23))

$$M_{n,m}(O') = \int_{S_y} \frac{\partial R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O'y})}{\partial n_y} \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y. \quad (\text{E.1})$$

From (B.11) we obtain

$$R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O'y}) = \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{O'O}) R_{n-n',m-m'}(\overrightarrow{Oy}). \quad (\text{E.2})$$

Substituting (E.2) into (E.1) we have

$$\begin{aligned} M_{n,m}(O') &= \int_{S_y} \frac{\partial R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O'y})}{\partial n_y} \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &= \int_{S_y} \frac{\partial}{\partial n_y} \left(\sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{O'O}) R_{n-n',m-m'}(\overrightarrow{Oy}) \right) \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &= \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{O'O}) \int_{S_y} \frac{\partial R_{n-n',m-m'}(\overrightarrow{Oy})}{\partial n_y} \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &= \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{O'O}) M_{n-n',m-m'}(O). \end{aligned}$$

E.2 M2L translation formula

From (B.5) we obtain

$$\overline{S_{n,m}}(\overrightarrow{Ox}) = \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} (-1)^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{x_0x}) \overline{S_{n+n',m+m'}}(\overrightarrow{Ox_0}). \quad (\text{E.3})$$

Substituting (E.3) into (3.22) we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \frac{\partial \overline{S_{n,m}}(\overrightarrow{Ox})}{\partial n_x} M_{n,m}(O)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \frac{\partial}{\partial n_x} \left(\sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} (-1)^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \hat{\mathbf{x}}}) \overline{S_{n+n',m+m'}(\overline{O \mathbf{x}_0})} \right) M_{n,m}(O) \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \frac{\partial R_{n',m'}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \hat{\mathbf{x}}})}{\partial n_x} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n (-1)^n \overline{S_{n+n',m+m'}(\overline{O \mathbf{x}_0})} M_{n,m}(O) \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \frac{\partial R_{n',m'}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \hat{\mathbf{x}}})}{\partial n_x} L_{n',m'}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \frac{\partial R_{n,m}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \hat{\mathbf{x}}})}{\partial n_x} L_{n,m}(\mathbf{x}_0),
\end{aligned}$$

where $L_{n,m}(\mathbf{x}_0)$ is the coefficient of the local expansion centred at \mathbf{x}_0 defined as

$$L_{n,m}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} (-1)^n \overline{S_{n+n',m+m'}(\overline{O \mathbf{x}_0})} M_{n',m'}(O).$$

E.3 L2L translation formula

From (B.11) we obtain

$$R_{n,m}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \hat{\mathbf{x}}}) = \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \hat{\mathbf{x}}}) R_{n-n',m-m'}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}_1}). \quad (\text{E.4})$$

Substituting (E.4) into the right-hand side of (3.26) we have

$$\begin{aligned}
&\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \frac{\partial R_{n,m}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \hat{\mathbf{x}}})}{\partial n_x} L_{n,m}(\mathbf{x}_0) \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \frac{\partial}{\partial n_x} \left(\sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \hat{\mathbf{x}}}) R_{n-n',m-m'}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}_1}) \right) L_{n,m}(\mathbf{x}_0) \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \frac{\partial R_{n',m'}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \hat{\mathbf{x}}})}{\partial n_x} R_{n-n',m-m'}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}_1}) L_{n,m}(\mathbf{x}_0). \quad (\text{E.5})
\end{aligned}$$

Exchanging an order of summation in (E.5) ($\sum_n \sum_{n'} \rightarrow \sum_{n'} \sum_n$, See Fig.B) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
&\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \frac{\partial R_{n,m}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \hat{\mathbf{x}}})}{\partial n_x} L_{n,m}(\mathbf{x}_0) \\
&= \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \frac{\partial R_{n',m'}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \hat{\mathbf{x}}})}{\partial n_x} \sum_{n=n'}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n R_{n-n',m-m'}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}_1}) L_{n,m}(\mathbf{x}_0) \\
&= \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \frac{\partial R_{n',m'}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \hat{\mathbf{x}}})}{\partial n_x} L_{n',m'}(\mathbf{x}_1) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \frac{\partial R_{n,m}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \hat{\mathbf{x}}})}{\partial n_x} L_{n,m}(\mathbf{x}_1),
\end{aligned}$$

where $L_{n,m}(\mathbf{x}_1)$ is the coefficient of the local expansion centred at \mathbf{x}_1 defined as

$$L_{n,m}(\mathbf{x}_1) = \sum_{n'=n}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n'-n,m'-m}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}_1}) L_{n',m'}(\mathbf{x}_0).$$

Appendix F

Series expansion of $|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|$

We introduce two vectors $\vec{O\mathbf{y}}$ and $\vec{O\mathbf{x}}$ which satisfy the inequality: $|\vec{O\mathbf{y}}| < |\vec{O\mathbf{x}}|$. An expansion for the fundamental solution of three-dimensional Helmholtz's Equation [17] is given by

$$\frac{e^{ik|\mathbf{x}-\mathbf{y}|}}{ik|\mathbf{x}-\mathbf{y}|} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n (2n+1)j_n(k|\vec{O\mathbf{y}}|)h_n^{(1)}(k|\vec{O\mathbf{x}}|)\overline{R_{n,m}(\widehat{Oy})}S_{n,m}(\widehat{Ox}), \quad (\text{F.1})$$

where \widehat{Ox} and \widehat{Oy} are unit vectors defined as

$$\widehat{Ox} = \frac{\vec{O\mathbf{x}}}{|\vec{O\mathbf{x}}|}, \quad \widehat{Oy} = \frac{\vec{O\mathbf{y}}}{|\vec{O\mathbf{y}}|},$$

j_n is the spherical Bessel function, $h_n^{(1)}$ is defined with the spherical Bessel functions j_n and y_n as

$$h_n^{(1)}(k|\vec{O\mathbf{x}}|) = j_n(k|\vec{O\mathbf{x}}|) + iy_n(k|\vec{O\mathbf{x}}|),$$

and j_n and y_n are expressed in Taylor (Laurent) series as

$$j_n(kz) = (2kz)^n \sum_{p=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^p (n+p)!}{p!(2n+2p+1)!} (kz)^{2p}, \quad (\text{F.2})$$

$$y_n(kz) = -\frac{1}{2^n (kz)^{n+1}} \sum_{p=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(2n-2p+1)}{p!\Gamma(n-p+1)} (kz)^{2p}. \quad (\text{F.3})$$

We next compare the coefficient of k in the left-hand side of (F.1) with that in the right-hand side of (F.1) to obtain a series expansion of $|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|$.

- the coefficient of k in the left-hand side of (F.1)

The left-hand side of (F.1) is expanded into a power series of wave number as

$$\frac{e^{ik|\mathbf{x}-\mathbf{y}|}}{ik|\mathbf{x}-\mathbf{y}|} = \frac{1}{ik|\mathbf{x}-\mathbf{y}|} + 1 + \frac{ik}{2}|\mathbf{x}-\mathbf{y}| + \dots \quad (\text{F.4})$$

and therefore the coefficient of k in the left-hand side of (F.1) is

$$\frac{i|\mathbf{x}-\mathbf{y}|}{2}. \quad (\text{F.5})$$

- the coefficient of k in the right-hand side of (F.1)

To begin with, we note that the coefficient of k in $j_n(k|\vec{O\mathbf{y}}|)j_n(k|\vec{O\mathbf{x}}|)$ is zero. The coefficient of k in $j_n(k|\vec{O\mathbf{y}}|)y_n(k|\vec{O\mathbf{x}}|)$ is

$$-\frac{|\vec{O\mathbf{y}}|^n}{|\vec{O\mathbf{x}}|^{n+1}} \left(\frac{(-1)^p (n+p)!}{p!(2n+2p+1)!} |\vec{O\mathbf{y}}|^{2p} \Big|_{p=0} - \frac{\Gamma(2n-2p+1)}{p!\Gamma(n-p+1)} |\vec{O\mathbf{x}}|^{2p} \Big|_{p=1} \right) +$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{(-1)^p(n+p)!}{p!(2n+2p+1)!} |\overrightarrow{Oy}|^{2p} \Big|_{p=1} \left(\frac{\Gamma(2n-2p+1)}{p!\Gamma(n-p+1)} |\overrightarrow{Ox}|^{2p} \Big|_{p=0} \right) \overline{R_{n,m}(\widehat{Oy})} S_{n,m}(\widehat{Ox}) \\
&= \frac{1}{2(2n+1)} \left(\frac{1}{2n+3} \frac{|\overrightarrow{Oy}|^{n+2}}{|\overrightarrow{Ox}|^{n+1}} - \frac{1}{2n-1} \frac{|\overrightarrow{Oy}|^n}{|\overrightarrow{Ox}|^{n-1}} \right) \overline{R_{n,m}(\widehat{Oy})} S_{n,m}(\widehat{Ox}).
\end{aligned}$$

Hence the coefficient of k in the right-hand side of (F.1) is

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \frac{i}{2} \left(\frac{1}{2n+3} \frac{|\overrightarrow{Oy}|^{n+2}}{|\overrightarrow{Ox}|^{n+1}} - \frac{1}{2n-1} \frac{|\overrightarrow{Oy}|^n}{|\overrightarrow{Ox}|^{n-1}} \right) \overline{R_{n,m}(\widehat{Oy})} S_{n,m}(\widehat{Ox}) \\
&= \frac{i}{2} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \left(\frac{S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{Ox}) \overline{U_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{Oy})}}{2n+3} - \frac{T_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{Ox}) \overline{R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{Oy})}}{2n-1} \right). \tag{F.6}
\end{aligned}$$

Comparing (F.5) with (F.6), we obtain a series expansion of $|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|$ given as

$$|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}| = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \left(\frac{S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{Ox}) \overline{U_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{Oy})}}{2n+3} - \frac{T_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{Ox}) \overline{R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{Oy})}}{2n-1} \right) \tag{F.7}$$

$$= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \left(\frac{\overline{S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{Ox})} U_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{Oy})}{2n+3} - \frac{\overline{T_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{Ox})} R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{Oy})}{2n-1} \right), \tag{F.8}$$

where $U_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{Oy})$ and $T_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{Ox})$ are functions defined as

$$U_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{Oy}) = |\overrightarrow{Oy}|^2 R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{Oy}), \quad T_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{Ox}) = |\overrightarrow{Ox}|^2 S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{Ox}). \tag{F.9}$$

Hayami and Sauter [41] obtained the same series expansion of $|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|$ in another way.

Appendix G

Series expansion of the fundamental solution of three-dimensional elastostatics

We introduce a new coordinate system which has following base vectors:

$$\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{i}_1 + i \mathbf{i}_2, \quad \bar{\mathbf{v}} = \mathbf{i}_1 - i \mathbf{i}_2, \quad \mathbf{i}_z = \mathbf{i}_3,$$

where $\mathbf{i}_1, \mathbf{i}_2, \mathbf{i}_3$ are base vectors in the Cartesian coordinates. In the new system, we have

$$\mathbf{x} = x_n \mathbf{i}_n = \frac{\bar{\xi}}{2} \mathbf{v} + \frac{\xi}{2} \bar{\mathbf{v}} + z \mathbf{i}_z, \quad \mathbf{y} = y_n \mathbf{i}_n = \frac{\bar{\xi}_0}{2} \mathbf{v} + \frac{\xi_0}{2} \bar{\mathbf{v}} + z_0 \mathbf{i}_z,$$

where $\xi = x_1 + ix_2$, $z = x_3$, $\xi_0 = y_1 + iy_2$, $z_0 = y_3$. The derivatives with respect to these variables satisfy

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} - i \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} \right), \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{\xi}} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} + i \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} \right), \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial z} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_3},$$

with which ∇_x is written as

$$\nabla_x = \mathbf{i}_n \frac{\partial}{\partial x_n} = \mathbf{v} \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} + \bar{\mathbf{v}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{\xi}} + \mathbf{i}_z \frac{\partial}{\partial z}. \quad (\text{G.1})$$

The functions $T_{n,m}(\vec{Ox})$ and $S_{n,m}(\vec{Ox})$ (See (F.9)) satisfy relations given by

$$\begin{aligned} T_{n,m}(\vec{Ox}) &= (2n-1)\xi S_{n-1,m-1}(\vec{Ox}) + (n-m)(n-m-1)S_{n-2,m}(\vec{Ox}), \\ T_{n,m}(\vec{Ox}) &= -(2n-1)\bar{\xi} S_{n-1,m+1}(\vec{Ox}) + (n+m)(n+m-1)S_{n-2,m}(\vec{Ox}), \\ T_{n,m}(\vec{Ox}) &= (2n-1)z S_{n-1,m}(\vec{Ox}) - (n+m-1)(n-m-1)S_{n-2,m}(\vec{Ox}), \\ T_{n,m}(\vec{Ox}) &= (\xi\bar{\xi} + z^2)S_{n,m}(\vec{Ox}), \end{aligned}$$

and the functions $U_{n,m}(\vec{Oy})$ and $R_{n,m}(\vec{Oy})$ (See (F.9)) satisfy relations given by

$$\begin{aligned} U_{n,m}(\vec{Oy}) &= -(2n+3)\xi_0 R_{n+1,m-1}(\vec{Oy}) + (n+m+2)(n+m+1)R_{n+2,m}(\vec{Oy}), \\ U_{n,m}(\vec{Oy}) &= (2n+3)\bar{\xi}_0 R_{n+1,m+1}(\vec{Oy}) + (n-m+1)(n-m+2)R_{n+2,m}(\vec{Oy}), \\ U_{n,m}(\vec{Oy}) &= (2n+3)z_0 R_{n+1,m}(\vec{Oy}) - (n+m+2)(n-m+2)R_{n+2,m}(\vec{Oy}). \end{aligned}$$

Using above relations, (D.1), (D.2), (D.3), (D.7), (D.8) and (D.11), we differentiate (F.8) using (G.1) to obtain the derivatives of $|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|$ as

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_x |\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}| &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \left(\mathbf{v} \frac{\bar{\xi} - \bar{\xi}_0}{2} + \bar{\mathbf{v}} \frac{\xi - \xi_0}{2} + \mathbf{i}_z (z - z_0) \right) \overline{S_{n,m}(\vec{Ox})} R_{n,m}(\vec{Oy}) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) \overline{S_{n,m}(\vec{Ox})} R_{n,m}(\vec{Oy}). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{G.2})$$

Another way to obtain this result is to use an expansion of $|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|^{-1}$ given by [88]

$$\frac{1}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \overline{S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})} R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) \quad |\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}| < |\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}|. \quad (\text{G.3})$$

With (G.3) we can derive (G.2) as follows:

$$\nabla_{\mathbf{x}} |\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}| = \frac{\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) \overline{S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})} R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}).$$

From (G.2) we obtain the second order derivatives of $|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|$ as

$$\begin{aligned} & \nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \otimes \nabla_{\mathbf{x}} |\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}| \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n -\nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \overline{S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})} \otimes \left(\frac{\bar{\xi}_0}{2} \mathbf{v} + \frac{\xi_0}{2} \bar{\mathbf{v}} + z_0 \mathbf{i}_z \right) R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) \\ & \quad + \nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \overline{S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})} \otimes \left(\frac{\bar{\xi}}{2} \mathbf{v} + \frac{\xi}{2} \bar{\mathbf{v}} + z \mathbf{i}_z \right) R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) \\ & \quad + \overline{S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})} R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) (\mathbf{v} \otimes \frac{\bar{\mathbf{v}}}{2} + \bar{\mathbf{v}} \otimes \frac{\mathbf{v}}{2} + \mathbf{i}_z \otimes \mathbf{i}_z) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n -\nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \overline{S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})} \otimes \mathbf{y} R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) + \nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \overline{S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})} \otimes \mathbf{x} R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) + \overline{S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})} R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) \mathbf{1}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{G.4})$$

where $\mathbf{1}$ is the second order unit tensor. The fundamental solution of the equation of elastostatics is expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) &= \frac{1}{8\pi\mu} \left(\delta_{ij} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} - \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \right) |\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}| \\ &= \frac{1}{8\pi\mu} \left(\delta_{ij} \frac{2}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} - \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} |\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}| \right). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{G.5})$$

Using (G.3), (G.4) and (G.5), we obtain a series expansion of $\Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})$ given by

$$\Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) = \frac{1}{8\pi\mu} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \left(\overline{F_{ij,n,m}^S(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})} R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) + \overline{G_{i,n,m}^S(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})} (\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}})_j R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) \right), \quad |\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}| < |\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}|, \quad (\text{G.6})$$

where $F_{ij,n,m}^S$ and $G_{i,n,m}^S$ are functions defined as

$$\begin{aligned} F_{ij,n,m}^S(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) &= \frac{\lambda + 3\mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \delta_{ij} S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) - \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} (\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})_j \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}), \\ G_{i,n,m}^S(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) &= \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} S_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}). \end{aligned}$$

Also, we can derive (G.6) in another way. We first rewrite then fundamental solution (G.5) as

$$\Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) = \frac{1}{8\pi\mu} \left(\delta_{ij} \frac{2}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} - \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})_j - (\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}})_j}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} \right). \quad (\text{G.7})$$

Substituting (G.3) into (G.7), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) &= \frac{1}{8\pi\mu} \left(\delta_{ij} \frac{2}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} - \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})_j - (\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}})_j}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{8\pi\mu} \left(\delta_{ij} \frac{2}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} - \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})_j}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} + \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}})_j}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{1}{8\pi\mu} \left(\frac{\lambda + 3\mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \frac{\delta_{ij}}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} - \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} (\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})_j \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{1}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} + \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}})_j}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|} \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{8\pi\mu} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \left(\frac{\lambda + 3\mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \delta_{ij} \overline{S_{n,m}}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} (\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})_j \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \overline{S_{n,m}}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) - \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \overline{S_{n,m}}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) (\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}})_j R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{8\pi\mu} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \left(\overline{F_{ij,n,m}^S}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) + \overline{G_{i,n,m}^S}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) (\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}})_j R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) \right).
\end{aligned}$$

Appendix H

M2M, M2L, L2L in three-dimensional elastostatics

H.1 M2M translation formula

The multipole moment centred O' is given by (See (3.53) and (3.54))

$$M_{j,n,m}^1(O') = \int_{S_y} C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O'\mathbf{y}}) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) n_c(\mathbf{y}) dS_y, \quad (\text{H.1})$$

$$M_{n,m}^2(O') = \int_{S_y} C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} ((\overrightarrow{O'\mathbf{y}})_j R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O'\mathbf{y}})) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) n_c(\mathbf{y}) dS_y. \quad (\text{H.2})$$

Substituting (E.2) into (H.1) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} M_{j,n,m}^1(O') &= \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{O'\mathcal{O}}) \int_{S_y} C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} R_{n-n',m-m'}(\overrightarrow{O'\mathbf{y}}) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) n_c(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &= \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{O'\mathcal{O}}) M_{j,n-n',m-m'}^1(O), \\ M_{n,m}^2(O') &= \int_{S_y} C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} ((\overrightarrow{O'\mathbf{y}})_j R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{O'\mathbf{y}})) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) n_c(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &= \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{O'\mathcal{O}}) \int_{S_y} C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} ((\overrightarrow{O'\mathbf{y}})_j R_{n-n',m-m'}(\overrightarrow{O'\mathbf{y}})) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) n_c(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &= \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{O'\mathcal{O}}) \int_{S_y} C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} ((\overrightarrow{O'\mathcal{O}})_j R_{n-n',m-m'}(\overrightarrow{O'\mathbf{y}})) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) n_c(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &\quad + \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{O'\mathcal{O}}) \int_{S_y} C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} ((\overrightarrow{O'\mathbf{y}})_j R_{n-n',m-m'}(\overrightarrow{O'\mathbf{y}})) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) n_c(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &= (\overrightarrow{O'\mathcal{O}})_j \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{O'\mathcal{O}}) \int_{S_y} C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} R_{n-n',m-m'}(\overrightarrow{O'\mathbf{y}}) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) n_c(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &\quad + \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{O'\mathcal{O}}) M_{n-n',m-m'}^2(O) \\ &= (\overrightarrow{O'\mathcal{O}})_j \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{O'\mathcal{O}}) M_{j,n-n',m-m'}^1(O) + \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{O'\mathcal{O}}) M_{n-n',m-m'}^2(O) \\ &= \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{O'\mathcal{O}}) \left(M_{n-n',m-m'}^2(O) - (\overrightarrow{O'\mathcal{O}})_j M_{j,n-n',m-m'}^1(O) \right). \end{aligned}$$

H.2 M2L translation formula

Substituting (E.3) into (3.52) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \overline{F_{ij,n,m}^S}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) M_{j,n,m}^1(O) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \overline{G_{i,n,m}^S}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) M_{n,m}^2(O) \right) \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(\frac{\lambda+3\mu}{\lambda+2\mu} \delta_{ij} \overline{S_{n,m}}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) - \frac{\lambda+\mu}{\lambda+2\mu} (\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})_j \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \overline{S_{n,m}}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) \right) M_{j,n,m}^1(O) \\
&\quad + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\lambda+\mu}{\lambda+2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \overline{S_{n,m}}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) M_{n,m}^2(O) \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} (-1)^{n'} \overline{S_{n+n',m+m'}}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0}) \\
&\quad \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(\frac{\lambda+3\mu}{\lambda+2\mu} \delta_{ij} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) - \frac{\lambda+\mu}{\lambda+2\mu} (\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}})_j \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) \right) M_{j,n,m}^1(O) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\lambda+\mu}{\lambda+2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) M_{n,m}^2(O) \right) \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} (-1)^{n'} \overline{S_{n+n',m+m'}}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0}) \\
&\quad \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(\frac{\lambda+3\mu}{\lambda+2\mu} \delta_{ij} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) - \frac{\lambda+\mu}{\lambda+2\mu} (\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0} + \overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}})_j \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) \right) M_{j,n,m}^1(O) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\lambda+\mu}{\lambda+2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) M_{n,m}^2(O) \right) \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} (-1)^{n'} \overline{S_{n+n',m+m'}}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0}) \\
&\quad \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(\frac{\lambda+3\mu}{\lambda+2\mu} \delta_{ij} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) - \frac{\lambda+\mu}{\lambda+2\mu} (\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}})_j \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) \right) M_{j,n,m}^1(O) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\lambda+\mu}{\lambda+2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} R_{n',m'}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) (M_{n,m}^2(O) - (\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0})_j M_{j,n,m}^1(O)) \right) \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} (-1)^{n'} \overline{S_{n+n',m+m'}}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0}) \\
&\quad \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} F_{ij,n',m'}^R(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}})_j M_{j,n,m}^1(O) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} G_{i,n',m'}^R(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) (M_{n,m}^2(O) - (\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0})_j M_{j,n,m}^1(O)) \right) \\
&= \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} F_{ij,n',m'}^R(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n (-1)^{n'} \overline{S_{n+n',m+m'}}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0}) M_{j,n,m}^1(O) \\
&\quad + \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} G_{i,n',m'}^R(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n (-1)^{n'} \overline{S_{n+n',m+m'}}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0}) (M_{n,m}^2(O) - (\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0})_j M_{j,n,m}^1(O)) \\
&= \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} F_{ij,n',m'}^R(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) L_{j,n',m'}^1(\mathbf{x}_0) + \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} G_{i,n',m'}^R(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) L_{n',m'}^2(\mathbf{x}_0),
\end{aligned}$$

where $L_{j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0)$ and $L_{n,m}^2(\mathbf{x}_0)$ are the coefficients of the local expansion centred at \mathbf{x}_0 , given by

$$\begin{aligned}
L_{j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0) &= \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} (-1)^{n'} \overline{S_{n+n',m+m'}}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0}) M_{j,n',m'}^1(O), \\
L_{n,m}^2(\mathbf{x}_0) &= \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} (-1)^{n'} \overline{S_{n+n',m+m'}}(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0}) (M_{n',m'}^2(O) - (\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0})_j M_{j,n',m'}^1(O)).
\end{aligned}$$

H.3 L2L translation formula

Substituting (E.4) into (3.59) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} F_{ij,n,m}^R(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}}) L_{j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} G_{i,n,m}^R(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}}) L_{n,m}^2(\mathbf{x}_0) \right) \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(\frac{\lambda + 3\mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \delta_{ij} R_{n,m}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}}) - \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} (\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}})_j \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} R_{n,m}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}}) \right) L_{j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0) \\
&\quad + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} R_{n,m}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}}) L_{n,m}^2(\mathbf{x}_0) \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n-n',m-m'}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}_1}) \\
&\quad \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(\frac{\lambda + 3\mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \delta_{ij} R_{n',m'}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{x}}) - \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} (\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}})_j \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} R_{n',m'}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{x}}) \right) L_{j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} R_{n',m'}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{x}}) L_{n,m}^2(\mathbf{x}_0) \right) \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n-n',m-m'}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}_1}) \\
&\quad \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(\frac{\lambda + 3\mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \delta_{ij} R_{n',m'}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{x}}) - \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} (\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}_1} + \overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{x}})_j \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} R_{n',m'}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{x}}) \right) L_{j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} R_{n',m'}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{x}}) L_{n,m}^2(\mathbf{x}_0) \right) \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n-n',m-m'}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}_1}) \\
&\quad \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(\frac{\lambda + 3\mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \delta_{ij} R_{n',m'}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{x}}) - \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} (\overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{x}})_j \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} R_{n',m'}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{x}}) \right) L_{j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} R_{n',m'}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{x}}) (L_{n,m}^2(\mathbf{x}_0) - (\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}_1})_j L_{j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0)) \right) \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \sum_{n'=0}^n \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n-n',m-m'}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}_1}) \\
&\quad \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} F_{ij,n',m'}^R(\overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{x}}) L_{j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} G_{i,n',m'}^R(\overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{x}}) (L_{n,m}^2(\mathbf{x}_0) - (\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}_1})_j L_{j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0)) \right) \\
&= \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} F_{ij,n',m'}^R(\overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{x}}) \sum_{n=n'}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n R_{n-n',m-m'}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}_1}) L_{j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0) \\
&\quad + \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} G_{i,n',m'}^R(\overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{x}}) \sum_{n=n'}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n R_{n-n',m-m'}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}_1}) (L_{n,m}^2(\mathbf{x}_0) - (\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}_1})_j L_{j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0)) \\
&= \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} F_{ij,n',m'}^R(\overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{x}}) L_{j,n',m'}^1(\mathbf{x}_1) + \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} G_{i,n',m'}^R(\overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{x}}) L_{n',m'}^2(\mathbf{x}_1),
\end{aligned}$$

where $L_{j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_1)$ and $L_{n,m}^2(\mathbf{x}_1)$ are the coefficients of the local expansion centred at \mathbf{x}_1 , given by

$$\begin{aligned}
L_{j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_1) &= \sum_{n'=n}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n'-n,m'-m}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}_1}) L_{j,n',m'}^1(\mathbf{x}_0), \\
L_{n,m}^2(\mathbf{x}_1) &= \sum_{n'=n}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} R_{n'-n,m'-m}(\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}_1}) (L_{n',m'}^2(\mathbf{x}_0) - (\overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}_1})_j L_{j,n',m'}^1(\mathbf{x}_0)).
\end{aligned}$$

Appendix I

M2M, M2L, L2L in three-dimensional Helmholtz's equation

I.1 M2M translation formula

The multipole moment centred O' is given by (See (3.128))

$$M_n^m(k, O') = \int_{S_y} \frac{\partial}{\partial n_y} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_n^m(k, \overrightarrow{O'\mathbf{y}}) \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y. \quad (\text{I.1})$$

Substituting (3.123) into (I.1), we obtain the following M2M translation formula:

$$\begin{aligned} M_n^m(k, O') &= \int_{S_y} \frac{\partial}{\partial n_y} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_n^m(k, \overrightarrow{O'\mathbf{y}}) \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &= \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \sum_{\substack{l=|n-n'| \\ n'+n-l:\text{even}}}^{n+n'} (2n'+1)(-1)^{m'} W_{n,n',m,m',l} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_l^{-m-m'}(k, \overrightarrow{O'\mathcal{O}}) \int_{S_y} \frac{\partial}{\partial n_y} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_{n'}^{-m'}(k, \overrightarrow{O\mathbf{y}}) \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &= \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \sum_{\substack{l=|n-n'| \\ n'+n-l:\text{even}}}^{n+n'} (2n'+1)(-1)^{m'} W_{n,n',m,m',l} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_l^{-m-m'}(k, \overrightarrow{O'\mathcal{O}}) M_{n'}^{-m'}(k, O). \end{aligned}$$

I.2 M2L translation formula

Substituting (3.124) into (3.127), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} &\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n (2n+1) \frac{\partial}{\partial n_x} \mathcal{O}_n^m(k, \overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}}) M_n^m(k, O) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \sum_{\substack{l=|n-n'| \\ n'+n-l:\text{even}}}^{n+n'} (2n+1)(2n'+1)(-1)^{m+n'} W_{n,n',m,m',l} \\ &\quad \times \frac{\partial}{\partial n_x} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_{n'}^{-m'}(k, \overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}\mathbf{x}_0}) \mathcal{O}_l^{m+m'}(k, \overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0}) M_n^m(k, O) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \sum_{\substack{l=|n-n'| \\ n'+n-l:\text{even}}}^{n+n'} (2n+1)(2n'+1)(-1)^{m+n'} W_{n,n',m,m',l} \\ &\quad \times (-1)^{m'+n'} \frac{\partial}{\partial n_x} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_{n'}^{m'}(k, \overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) (-1)^{m+m'} \tilde{\mathcal{O}}_l^{m+m'}(k, \overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0}) M_n^m(k, O) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} (2n'+1) \frac{\partial}{\partial n_x} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_{n'}^{m'}(k, \overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}}) \\
&\quad \times \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \sum_{\substack{l=|n-n'| \\ n'+n-l:\text{even}}}^{n+n'} (2n+1) W_{n,n',m,m',l} \tilde{\mathcal{O}}_l^{m+m'}(k, \overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0}) M_n^m(k, O) \\
&= \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} (2n'+1) \frac{\partial}{\partial n_x} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_{n'}^{m'}(k, \overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}}) L_n^{m'}(k, \mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n (2n+1) \frac{\partial}{\partial n_x} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_n^m(k, \overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}}) L_n^m(k, \mathbf{x}_0),
\end{aligned}$$

where $L_n^m(k, \mathbf{x}_0)$ is the coefficient of the local expansion at \mathbf{x}_0 given by

$$L_n^m(k, \mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \sum_{\substack{l=|n-n'| \\ n'+n-l:\text{even}}}^{n+n'} (2n'+1) W_{n',n,m',m,l} \tilde{\mathcal{O}}_l^{-m-m'}(k, \overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0}) M_{n'}^{m'}(k, O). \quad (\text{I.2})$$

In the derivation of (I.2) we have used the following identities:

$$Y_n^m(\widehat{O\mathbf{x}}) = (-1)^n Y_n^m(\widehat{\mathbf{x}O}), \quad Y_n^{-m}(\widehat{O\mathbf{x}}) = (-1)^m \overline{Y}_n^m(\widehat{O\mathbf{x}}).$$

I.3 L2L translation formula

From (3.123), we have

$$\overline{\mathcal{I}}_n^m(k, \overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}}) = \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \sum_{\substack{l=|n-n'| \\ n'+n-l:\text{even}}}^{n+n'} (2n'+1) (-1)^{m'} W_{n,n',m,m',l} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_{n'}^{m'}(k, \overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{x}}) \mathcal{I}_l^{-m-m'}(k, \overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}_1}). \quad (\text{I.3})$$

Substituting (I.3) into (3.130), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
&\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n (2n+1) \frac{\partial}{\partial n_x} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_n^m(k, \overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}}) L_n^m(k, \mathbf{x}_0) \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \sum_{\substack{l=|n-n'| \\ n'+n-l:\text{even}}}^{n+n'} (2n'+1) (2n+1) (-1)^{m'} W_{n,n',m,m',l} \\
&\quad \times \frac{\partial}{\partial n_x} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_{n'}^{m'}(k, \overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{x}}) \mathcal{I}_l^{-m-m'}(k, \overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}_1}) L_n^m(k, \mathbf{x}_0) \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \sum_{\substack{l=|n-n'| \\ n'+n-l:\text{even}}}^{n+n'} (2n'+1) (2n+1) (-1)^{m'} W_{n,n',m,-m',l} \\
&\quad \times \frac{\partial}{\partial n_x} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_{n'}^{m'}(k, \overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{x}}) \mathcal{I}_l^{-m+m'}(k, \overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}_1}) L_n^m(k, \mathbf{x}_0) \\
&= \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} (2n'+1) \frac{\partial}{\partial n_x} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_{n'}^{m'}(k, \overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{x}}) \\
&\quad \times \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \sum_{\substack{l=|n-n'| \\ n'+n-l:\text{even}}}^{n+n'} (2n+1) (-1)^{m'} W_{n,n',m,-m',l} \mathcal{I}_l^{-m+m'}(k, \overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}_1}) L_n^m(k, \mathbf{x}_0) \\
&= \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} (2n'+1) \frac{\partial}{\partial n_x} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_{n'}^{m'}(k, \overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{x}}) L_n^{m'}(k, \mathbf{x}_1) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n (2n+1) \frac{\partial}{\partial n_x} \overline{\mathcal{I}}_n^m(k, \overline{\mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{x}}) L_n^m(k, \mathbf{x}_1),
\end{aligned}$$

where $L_n^m(k, \mathbf{x}_1)$ is the coefficient of the local expansion at \mathbf{x}_1 given by

$$L_n^m(k, \mathbf{x}_1) = \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m'=-n'}^{n'} \sum_{\substack{l=|n-n'| \\ n'+n-l:\text{even}}}^{n+n'} (2n'+1) (-1)^{m'} W_{n',n,m',-m,l} \mathcal{I}_l^{m-m'}(k, \overline{\mathbf{x}_0 \mathbf{x}_1}) L_{n'}^{m'}(k, \mathbf{x}_0).$$

Appendix J

M2X, X2X, X2L in three-dimensional Laplace's equation

In this appendix we describe the derivation of M2X, X2X and X2L translation formulae in three-dimensional Laplace's equation and estimate the computational costs for these translations. Notice that Greengard and Rokhlin [36] estimate the cost under the following conditions:

$$S_{\text{exp}} = \sum_{k=1}^s M(k) \approx p^2, \quad s \approx p$$

J.1 M2X translation formula

Using (3.22), (4.2), (B.1), (B.2) and the following identity:

$$\partial_{\pm} e^{i(\lambda_k/d)((\vec{O}\mathbf{x})_1 \cos \alpha_j + (\vec{O}\mathbf{x})_2 \sin \alpha_j)} = i(\lambda_k/d) e^{\pm i\alpha_j} e^{i(\lambda_k/d)((\vec{O}\mathbf{x})_1 \cos \alpha_j + (\vec{O}\mathbf{x})_2 \sin \alpha_j)},$$

we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \overline{S_{n,m}}(\vec{O}\mathbf{x}_1) M_{n,m}(O) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{m=0}^n \overline{S_{n,m}}(\vec{O}\mathbf{x}) M_{n,m}(O) + \sum_{m=1}^n \overline{S_{n,-m}}(\vec{O}\mathbf{x}) M_{n,-m}(O) \right) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{m=0}^n (-1)^n \partial_-^m \partial_{x_3}^{n-m} \left(\frac{1}{|\vec{O}\mathbf{x}|} \right) M_{n,m}(O) + \sum_{m=1}^n (-1)^{n+m} \partial_+^m \partial_{x_3}^{n-m} \left(\frac{1}{|\vec{O}\mathbf{x}|} \right) M_{n,-m}(O) \right) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=0}^n \sum_{k=1}^s \sum_{j=1}^{M(k)} \frac{\omega_k}{M(k)d} (-i)^m (\lambda_k/d)^n e^{-im\alpha_j(k)} M_{n,m}(O) \\ & \quad \times e^{-(\lambda_k/d)((\vec{O}\mathbf{x})_3 - i(\vec{O}\mathbf{x})_1 \cos \alpha_j(k) - i(\vec{O}\mathbf{x})_2 \sin \alpha_j(k))} \\ &+ \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^s \sum_{j=1}^{M(k)} \frac{\omega_k}{M(k)d} (i)^m (\lambda_k/d)^n e^{im\alpha_j(k)} M_{n,-m}(O) \\ & \quad \times e^{-(\lambda_k/d)((\vec{O}\mathbf{x})_3 - i(\vec{O}\mathbf{x})_1 \cos \alpha_j(k) - i(\vec{O}\mathbf{x})_2 \sin \alpha_j(k))} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^s \sum_{j=1}^{M(k)} \frac{\omega_k}{M(k)d} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n (-i)^m (\lambda_k/d)^n e^{-im\alpha_j} M_{n,m}(O) \\ & \quad \times e^{-(\lambda_k/d)((\vec{O}\mathbf{x})_3 - i(\vec{O}\mathbf{x})_1 \cos \alpha_j(k) - i(\vec{O}\mathbf{x})_2 \sin \alpha_j(k))} \end{aligned}$$

$$= \sum_{k=1}^s \sum_{j=1}^{M(k)} X(k, j; O) e^{-(\lambda_k/d)((\vec{Ox})_3 - i(\vec{Ox})_1 \cos \alpha_j(k) - i(\vec{Ox})_2 \sin \alpha_j(k))}$$

where $X(k, j; O)$ is the coefficient of the exponential expansion centred at O defined as

$$X(k, j; O) = \frac{\omega_k}{M(k)d} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n (-i)^m (\lambda_k/d)^n e^{-im\alpha_j(k)} M_{n,m}(O). \quad (\text{J.1})$$

Exchanging an order of the double sum in (J.1) (See Fig.J.1) we rewrite (J.1) as

$$X(k, j; O) = \frac{\omega_k}{M(k)d} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} (-i)^m e^{-im\alpha_j(k)} \sum_{n=|m|}^{\infty} (\lambda_k/d)^n M_{n,m}(O). \quad (\text{J.2})$$

Next we estimate the cost for M2X translation. Noting (J.2) and truncating the infinite series (3.22)

Figure J.1: Exchange of indices

with p terms, the cost can be roughly estimated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Cost} &= \sum_{k=1}^s \sum_{m=-p}^p \sum_{n=|m|}^p C_0 + \sum_{k=1}^s \sum_{j=1}^{M(k)} \sum_{m=-p}^p C_1 + C_2 \\ &\approx O(C_0 s p^2) + O(C_1 p S \text{exp}) \approx O(p^3) + O(p^3) = O(p^3), \end{aligned}$$

where C_0 and C_1 are the computational cost related to $(\lambda_k/d)^n M_{n,m}(O)$ and $(-i)^m e^{-im\alpha_j(k)}$ in (J.2), respectively and C_2 is the negligible cost.

J.2 X2X translation formula

Shifting the centre of the exponential expansion from O to \mathbf{x}_0 we have the following identity

$$\begin{aligned} &\sum_{k=1}^s \sum_{j=1}^{M(k)} X(k, j; O) e^{-(\lambda_k/d)((\vec{Ox})_3 - i(\vec{Ox})_1 \cos \alpha_j(k) - i(\vec{Ox})_2 \sin \alpha_j(k))} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^s \sum_{j=1}^{M(k)} X(k, j; \mathbf{x}_0) e^{-(\lambda_k/d)((\vec{x}_0 \mathbf{x})_3 - i(\vec{x}_0 \mathbf{x})_1 \cos \alpha_j(k) - i(\vec{x}_0 \mathbf{x})_2 \sin \alpha_j(k))}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{J.3})$$

where $X(k, j; \mathbf{x}_0)$ is the exponential expansion centred at \mathbf{x}_0 defined as

$$X(k, j; \mathbf{x}_0) = X(k, j; O) e^{-(\lambda_k/d)((\vec{Ox}_0)_3 - i(\vec{Ox}_0)_1 \cos \alpha_j(k) - i(\vec{Ox}_0)_2 \sin \alpha_j(k))}.$$

The computational cost for X2X translation is obviously $O(S \text{exp}) \approx O(p^2)$.

J.3 X2L translation formula

Substituting the following formula into the right-hand side of (J.3):

$$\begin{aligned} & e^{-(\lambda_k/d)((\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}})_3 - i(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}})_1 \cos \alpha_j(k) - i(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}})_2 \sin \alpha_j(k))} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\lambda_k/d)^n}{n!} ((\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}})_3 - i(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}})_1 \cos \alpha_j(k) - i(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}})_2 \sin \alpha_j(k))^n, \end{aligned}$$

and using the following identity (See (4.9)):

$$\frac{((\overrightarrow{\mathbf{Ox}})_3 - i(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{Ox}})_1 \cos \alpha_j(k) - i(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{Ox}})_2 \sin \alpha_j(k))^n}{n!} = \sum_{m=-n}^n (-i)^m e^{-im\alpha_j(k)} R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{Ox}}),$$

we rewrite the right-hand side of (J.3) as

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=1}^s \sum_{j=1}^{M(k)} X(k, j; \mathbf{x}_0) e^{-(\lambda_k/d)((\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}})_3 - i(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}})_1 \cos \alpha_j(k) - i(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}})_2 \sin \alpha_j(k))} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^s \sum_{j=1}^{M(k)} X(k, j; \mathbf{x}_0) \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\lambda_k/d)^n}{n!} ((\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}})_3 - i(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}})_1 \cos \alpha_j(k) - i(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}})_2 \sin \alpha_j(k))^n \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^s \sum_{j=1}^{M(k)} X(k, j; \mathbf{x}_0) \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-\lambda_k/d)^n \sum_{m=-n}^n (-i)^m e^{-im\alpha_j(k)} R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) \sum_{k=1}^s \sum_{j=1}^{M(k)} X(k, j; \mathbf{x}_0) (-\lambda_k/d)^n (-i)^m e^{-im\alpha_j(k)} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n R_{n,m}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) L_{n,m}(\mathbf{x}_0) \end{aligned}$$

where $L_{n,m}(\mathbf{x}_0)$ is the coefficient of the local expansion expressed in terms of $X(k, j; \mathbf{x}_0)$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} L_{n,m}(\mathbf{x}_0) &= \sum_{k=1}^s \sum_{j=1}^{M(k)} (-\lambda_k/d)^n (-i)^m e^{-im\alpha_j(k)} X(k, j; \mathbf{x}_0) \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^s (-\lambda_k/d)^n \sum_{j=1}^{M(k)} (-i)^m e^{-im\alpha_j(k)} X(k, j; \mathbf{x}_0) \end{aligned} \tag{J.4}$$

The cost for X2L translation can be roughly estimated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Cost} &= \sum_{m=-p}^p \sum_{k=1}^s \sum_{j=1}^{M(k)} C_0 + \sum_{n=0}^p \sum_{m=-n}^n \sum_{k=1}^s C_1 + C_2 \\ &\approx O(C_0 p s \text{exp}) + O(C_1 p^2 s) \approx O(p^3) + O(p^3) = O(p^3), \end{aligned}$$

where C_0 and C_1 are the computational cost related to $(-i)^m e^{-im\alpha_j(k)} X(k, j; \mathbf{x}_0)$ and $(-\lambda_k/d)^n$ in (J.4), respectively and C_2 is the negligible cost.

Appendix K

M2X, X2X, X2L in three-dimensional elastostatics

K.1 M2X translation formula

Using (4.2), we can transform the right-hand side of (3.52)

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \overline{F_{ij,n,m}^S}(\vec{Ox}) M_{j,n,m}^1(O) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \overline{G_{i,n,m}^S}(\vec{Ox}) M_{n,m}^2(O) \right) \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n \frac{\lambda + 3\mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \delta_{ij} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \overline{S_{n,m}}(\vec{Ox}) M_{j,n,m}^1(O) - \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} (\vec{Ox})_j \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \overline{S_{n,m}}(\vec{Ox}) M_{j,n,m}^1(O) \\
&+ \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \overline{S_{n,m}}(\vec{Ox}) M_{n,m}^2(O) \\
&= \sum_{p=1}^{s(\varepsilon)} \sum_{q=1}^{M(p)} \left(X_j^1(p, q; O) \mathcal{F}_{kij}(\vec{Ox}) + X^2(p, q; O) \mathcal{G}_{ki}(\vec{Ox}) \right) \\
&\quad \times e^{-(\lambda_p/d)(\vec{Ox})_3 + i(\lambda_p/d)((\vec{Ox})_1 \cos \alpha_q(p) + (\vec{Ox})_2 \sin \alpha_q(p))},
\end{aligned}$$

where we have used the result obtained in J.1 and $X_j^1(p, q; O)$ and $X^2(p, q; O)$ are the coefficients of the exponential expansion at O , defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
X_j^1(p, q; O) &= \frac{\omega_p}{M(p)d} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} (-i)^m e^{-im\alpha_q(p)} \sum_{n=|m|}^{\infty} (\lambda_p/d)^n M_{j,n,m}^1(O), \\
X^2(p, q; O) &= \frac{\omega_p}{M(p)d} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} (-i)^m e^{-im\alpha_q(p)} \sum_{n=|m|}^{\infty} (\lambda_p/d)^n M_{n,m}^2(O),
\end{aligned}$$

and \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} are operators defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{F}_{kij}(\vec{Ox}) &= \frac{\lambda + 3\mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \delta_{ij} - \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} (\vec{Ox})_j \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}, \\
\mathcal{G}_{ki}(\vec{Ox}) &= \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}.
\end{aligned}$$

K.2 X2X translation formula

Shifting the centre of the exponential expansion from O to \mathbf{x}_0 we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{p=1}^{s(\varepsilon)} \sum_{q=1}^{M(p)} \left(X_j^1(p, q; O) \mathcal{F}_{kij}(\vec{Ox}) + X^2(p, q; O) \mathcal{G}_{ki}(\vec{Ox}) \right) e^{-(\lambda_p/d)(\vec{Ox})_3 + i(\lambda_p/d)((\vec{Ox})_1 \cos \alpha_q(p) + (\vec{Ox})_2 \sin \alpha_q(p))} \\
&= \sum_{p=1}^{s(\varepsilon)} \sum_{q=1}^{M(p)} \left(X_j^1(p, q; O) \mathcal{F}_{kij}(\vec{x_0x}) - (\vec{Ox}_0)_j X_j^1(p, q; O) \frac{\lambda + \mu}{\lambda + 2\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} + X^2(p, q; O) \mathcal{G}_{ki}(\vec{Ox}) \right)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \times e^{-(\lambda_p/d)(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0})_3+i(\lambda_p/d)((\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0})_1 \cos \alpha_q(p)+(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0})_2 \sin \alpha_q(p))} \\
& \times e^{-(\lambda_p/d)(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}})_3+i(\lambda_p/d)((\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}})_1 \cos \alpha_q(p)+(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}})_2 \sin \alpha_q(p))} \\
& = \sum_{p=1}^{s(\varepsilon)} \sum_{q=1}^{M(p)} \left(X_j^1(p, q; \mathbf{x}_0) \mathcal{F}_{kij}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) + X^2(p, q; \mathbf{x}_0) \mathcal{G}_{ki}(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}}) \right) \\
& \times e^{-(\lambda_p/d)(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}})_3+i(\lambda_p/d)((\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}})_1 \cos \alpha_q(p)+(\overrightarrow{\mathbf{x}_0\mathbf{x}})_2 \sin \alpha_q(p))},
\end{aligned}$$

where $X_j^1(p, q; \mathbf{x}_0)$ and $X^2(p, q; \mathbf{x}_0)$ are the coefficients of the exponential expansion at \mathbf{x}_0 defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
X_j^1(p, q; \mathbf{x}_0) &= X_j^1(p, q; O) e^{-(\lambda_p/d)((\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0})_3-i(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0})_1 \cos \alpha_q(p)-i(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0})_2 \sin \alpha_q(p))}, \\
X^2(p, q; \mathbf{x}_0) &= (X^2(p, q; O) - (\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0})_k X_k^1(p, q; O)) e^{-(\lambda_p/d)((\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0})_3-i(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0})_1 \cos \alpha_q(p)-i(\overrightarrow{O\mathbf{x}_0})_2 \sin \alpha_q(p))}.
\end{aligned}$$

K.3 X2L translation formula

Using the result obtained in J.3 we can obtain the X2L translation formulae given by

$$L_{j,n,m}^1(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{p=1}^{s(\varepsilon)} \sum_{q=1}^{M(p)} X_j^1(p, q; \mathbf{x}_0) (-i)^m (-\lambda_p/d)^n e^{-im\alpha_q(p)}, \quad (\text{K.1})$$

$$L_{n,m}^2(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{p=1}^{s(\varepsilon)} \sum_{q=1}^{M(p)} X^2(p, q; \mathbf{x}_0) (-i)^m (-\lambda_p/d)^n e^{-im\alpha_q(p)}. \quad (\text{K.2})$$

Appendix L

Regularisation of integral equations

In this section we regularise the hypersingular integral equation using the following formulae

$$\int_S n_i(\mathbf{x}) e_{ijk} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} f_k(\mathbf{x}) dS = \oint_{\partial S} f_k(\mathbf{x}) dx_k \quad (\text{L.1})$$

$$\int_S n_i(\mathbf{x}) e_{ijk} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} g(\mathbf{x}) dS = \oint_{\partial S} g(\mathbf{x}) dx_k \quad (\text{L.2})$$

In these formulae the right-hand screw convention is applied to the direction of the integration along ∂S .

L.1 Regularisation of BIE in three-dimensional Laplace's equation

We regularise the hypersingular integral equation (3.15) using (L.2).

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{\partial u^\infty(\mathbf{x})}{\partial n_x} &= \rlap{-}\int_S \frac{\partial^2 G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial n_x \partial n_y} \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y, \quad (\mathbf{x} \in S) \\ &= n_j(\mathbf{x}) \rlap{-}\int_S n_i(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial^2 G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial x_j \partial y_i} \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &= n_j(\mathbf{x}) \rlap{-}\int_S n_i(\mathbf{y}) \delta_{jq} \delta_{ip} \frac{\partial^2 G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial x_q \partial y_p} \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &= n_j(\mathbf{x}) \rlap{-}\int_S n_i(\mathbf{y}) (e_{liq} e_{lpj} + \delta_{ij} \delta_{pq}) \frac{\partial^2 G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial x_q \partial y_p} \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\ &= n_j(\mathbf{x}) \rlap{-}\int_S n_i(\mathbf{y}) e_{liq} e_{lpj} \frac{\partial^2 G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial x_p \partial y_q} \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \left(\because \Delta G = 0, \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} = -\frac{\partial}{\partial y_i} \right) \\ &= n_j(\mathbf{x}) e_{lpj} \rlap{-}\int_S n_i(\mathbf{y}) e_{liq} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial y_q} \left(\frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial x_p} \phi(\mathbf{y}) \right) - \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial x_p} \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_q} \right) dS_y \\ &= n_j(\mathbf{x}) e_{lpj} \oint_{\partial S} \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial x_p} \underbrace{\phi(\mathbf{y}) dy_l}_0 \quad (\because \text{Stokes' theorem}) \\ &\quad - n_j(\mathbf{x}) e_{lpj} \rlap{-}\int_S n_i(\mathbf{y}) e_{liq} \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial x_p} \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_q} dS_y \\ &= -n_j(\mathbf{x}) e_{jpl} \rlap{-}\int_S n_i(\mathbf{y}) e_{iql} \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial y_p} \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_q} dS_y. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{L.3})$$

L.2 Regularisation of BIE in three-dimensional elastostatics

We regularise the hypersingular integral equation (3.46) using (L.1).

$$\begin{aligned} t_a^\infty(\mathbf{x}) &= -\rlap{-}\int_S n_b(\mathbf{x}) C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) C_{cdjl} n_c(\mathbf{y}) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) dS_y, \quad (\mathbf{x} \in S) \\ &= -\delta_{kq} \delta_{cs} \rlap{-}\int_S n_b(\mathbf{x}) C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_q} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) C_{cdjl} n_s(\mathbf{y}) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= -(e_{rqs}e_{rkc} + \delta_{qc}\delta_{ks}) \oint_S n_b(\mathbf{x})C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_q} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})C_{cdjl}n_s(\mathbf{y})\phi_d(\mathbf{y})dS_y \\
&= -e_{rqs}e_{rkc} \oint_S n_b(\mathbf{x})C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_q} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})C_{cdjl}n_s(\mathbf{y})\phi_d(\mathbf{y})dS_y \\
&\quad -\delta_{qc}\delta_{ks} \oint_S n_b(\mathbf{x})C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_q} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})C_{cdjl}n_s(\mathbf{y})\phi_d(\mathbf{y})dS_y \\
&= -e_{rqs}e_{rkc} \oint_S n_b(\mathbf{x})C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_q} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})C_{cdjl}n_s(\mathbf{y})\phi_d(\mathbf{y})dS_y \\
&\quad + \underbrace{\oint_S n_b(\mathbf{x})C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_c} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})C_{cdjl}n_k(\mathbf{y})\phi_d(\mathbf{y})dS_y}_0 \\
&= \oint_S e_{rqs}e_{rkc}n_b(\mathbf{x})C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_q} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})C_{cdjl}n_s(\mathbf{y})\phi_d(\mathbf{y})dS_y \\
&= \oint_S e_{rqs} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_q} \underbrace{\left(e_{rkc}n_b(\mathbf{x})C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})C_{cdjl}\phi_d(\mathbf{y}) \right)}_{A_r^a} n_s(\mathbf{y})dS_y \\
&\quad - \oint_S e_{rqs}e_{rkc}n_b(\mathbf{x})C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial \phi_d(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_q} n_s(\mathbf{y})dS_y \\
&= - \oint_{\partial S} \underbrace{A_r^a}_0 dy_r \quad (\because \text{Stokes' theorem}) \\
&\quad - \oint_S e_{rqs}e_{rkc}n_b(\mathbf{x})C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial \phi_d(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_q} n_s(\mathbf{y})dS_y \\
&= \oint_S n_b(\mathbf{x})C_{abik}e_{rkc}C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})e_{rqs} \frac{\partial \phi_d(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_q} n_s(\mathbf{y})dS_y.
\end{aligned}$$

L.3 Regularisation of VBIE in three-dimensional elastostatics

We regularise the hypersingular integral equation (3.100) using (L.2).

$$\begin{aligned}
&\int_S \psi_a(\mathbf{x})t_a^\infty(\mathbf{x})dS_x \\
&= - \int_S \psi_a(\mathbf{x})n_b(\mathbf{x}) \oint_S C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})C_{cdjl}n_c(\mathbf{y})\phi_d(\mathbf{y})dS_y dS_x, \quad (\mathbf{x} \in S) \\
&= - \int_S \psi_a(\mathbf{x})n_b(\mathbf{x}) \oint_S e_{aip}e_{bjq}e_{ckr}e_{dls} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Phi_{pqrs}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})n_c(\mathbf{y})\phi_d(\mathbf{y})dS_y dS_x \\
&= - \int_S \psi_a(\mathbf{x})n_b(\mathbf{x}) \oint_S e_{ckr} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_k} \underbrace{\left(e_{aip}e_{bjq}e_{dls} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Phi_{pqrs}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})\phi_d(\mathbf{y}) \right)}_{A_r^{ab}} n_c(\mathbf{y})dS_y dS_x \\
&\quad - \int_S \psi_a(\mathbf{x})n_b(\mathbf{x}) \oint_S e_{aip}e_{bjq}e_{ckr}e_{dls} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Phi_{pqrs}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})n_c(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial \phi_d(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_k} dS_y dS_x \\
&= \int_S \psi_a(\mathbf{x})n_b(\mathbf{x}) \oint_{\partial S} \underbrace{A_r^{ab}}_0 dy_r dS_x \quad (\because \text{Stokes' theorem}) \\
&\quad - \int_S \psi_a(\mathbf{x})n_b(\mathbf{x}) \oint_S e_{aip}e_{bjq}e_{ckr}e_{dls} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Phi_{pqrs}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})n_c(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial \phi_d(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_k} dS_y dS_x \\
&= - \int_S \psi_a(\mathbf{x})n_b(\mathbf{x}) \oint_S e_{aip}e_{bjq}e_{ckr}e_{dls} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Phi_{pqrs}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})n_c(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial \phi_d(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_k} dS_y dS_x \\
&= - \int_S e_{bjq} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \underbrace{\left(\psi_a(\mathbf{x}) \oint_S e_{aip}e_{ckr}e_{dls} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Phi_{pqrs}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})n_c(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial \phi_d(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_k} dS_y \right)}_{A_q} n_b(\mathbf{x})dS_x
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& - \int_S e_{bjq} \frac{\partial \psi_a(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_j} \left(\int_S e_{aip} e_{ckr} e_{dls} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Phi_{pqrs}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) n_c(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial \phi_d(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_k} dS_y \right) n_b(\mathbf{x}) dS_x \\
= & - \oint_{\partial S} \underbrace{A_q}_0 dx_q \quad (\text{Stokes' theorem}) \\
& - \int_S n_b(\mathbf{x}) e_{bjq} \frac{\partial \psi_a(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_j} \int_S e_{aip} e_{dls} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Phi_{pqrs}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) e_{ckr} n_c(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial \phi_d(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_k} dS_y dS_x \\
= & - \int_S n_b(\mathbf{x}) e_{bjq} \frac{\partial \psi_a(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_j} \int_S e_{aip} e_{dls} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Phi_{pqrs}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) e_{ckr} n_c(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial \phi_d(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_k} dS_y dS_x
\end{aligned}$$

L.4 Regularisation of BIE in three-dimensional Helmholtz's equation

We regularise the hypersingular integral equation (3.118) using (L.1).

$$\begin{aligned}
-\frac{\partial u^I(\mathbf{x})}{\partial n_x} &= \oint_S \frac{\partial^2 G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial n_x \partial n_y} \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y, \quad (\mathbf{x} \in S) \\
&= n_j(\mathbf{x}) \oint_S n_i(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial^2 G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial x_j \partial y_i} \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\
&= n_j(\mathbf{x}) \oint_S n_i(\mathbf{y}) \delta_{jq} \delta_{ip} \frac{\partial^2 G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial x_q \partial y_p} \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\
&= n_j(\mathbf{x}) \oint_S n_i(\mathbf{y}) (e_{liq} e_{lpj} + \delta_{ij} \delta_{pq}) \frac{\partial^2 G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial x_q \partial y_p} \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\
&= n_j(\mathbf{x}) \oint_S n_i(\mathbf{y}) e_{liq} e_{lpj} \frac{\partial^2 G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial x_p \partial y_q} \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\
&\quad + k^2 \int_S n_i(\mathbf{x}) n_i(\mathbf{y}) G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \quad \left(\because (\Delta + k^2)G = 0, \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} = -\frac{\partial}{\partial y_i} \right) \\
&= n_j(\mathbf{x}) e_{lpj} \oint_S n_i(\mathbf{y}) e_{liq} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial y_q} \left(\frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial x_p} \phi(\mathbf{y}) \right) - \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial x_p} \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_q} \right) dS_y \\
&\quad + k^2 \int_S n_i(\mathbf{x}) n_i(\mathbf{y}) G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\
&= n_j(\mathbf{x}) e_{lpj} \oint_{\partial S} \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial x_p} \underbrace{\phi(\mathbf{y})}_{0} dy_l \quad (\text{Stokes' theorem}) \\
&\quad - n_j(\mathbf{x}) e_{lpj} \int_S n_i(\mathbf{y}) e_{liq} \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial x_p} \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_q} dS_y \\
&\quad + k^2 \int_S n_i(\mathbf{x}) n_i(\mathbf{y}) G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y \\
&= -n_j(\mathbf{x}) e_{jpl} \int_S n_i(\mathbf{y}) e_{iql} \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})}{\partial y_p} \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_q} dS_y \\
&\quad + k^2 \int_S n_i(\mathbf{x}) n_i(\mathbf{y}) G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) \phi(\mathbf{y}) dS_y.
\end{aligned}$$

L.5 Regularisation of BIE in three-dimensional elastodynamics

We regularise the hypersingular integral equation (3.140) using (L.2).

$$\begin{aligned}
t_a^\infty(\mathbf{x}) &= - \oint_S n_b(\mathbf{x}) C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) C_{cdjl} n_c(\mathbf{y}) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) dS_y, \quad (\mathbf{x} \in S) \\
&= -\delta_{kq} \delta_{cs} \int_S n_b(\mathbf{x}) C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_q} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) C_{cdjl} n_s(\mathbf{y}) \phi_d(\mathbf{y}) dS_y
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= -(e_{rqs}e_{rkc} + \delta_{qc}\delta_{ks}) \oint_S n_b(\mathbf{x})C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_q} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})C_{cdjl}n_s(\mathbf{y})\phi_d(\mathbf{y})dS_y \\
&= -e_{rqs}e_{rkc} \oint_S n_b(\mathbf{x})C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_q} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})C_{cdjl}n_s(\mathbf{y})\phi_d(\mathbf{y})dS_y \\
&\quad -\delta_{qc}\delta_{ks} \oint_S n_b(\mathbf{x})C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_q} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})C_{cdjl}n_s(\mathbf{y})\phi_d(\mathbf{y})dS_y \\
&= -e_{rqs}e_{rkc} \oint_S n_b(\mathbf{x})C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_q} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})C_{cdjl}n_s(\mathbf{y})\phi_d(\mathbf{y})dS_y \\
&\quad + \oint_S n_b(\mathbf{x})C_{abik} \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial y_c} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})C_{cdjl}}_{-\rho\omega^2\Gamma_{id}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})} n_k(\mathbf{y})\phi_d(\mathbf{y})dS_y \\
&= \oint_S e_{rqs}e_{rkc}n_b(\mathbf{x})C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_q} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})C_{cdjl}n_s(\mathbf{y})\phi_d(\mathbf{y})dS_y \\
&\quad -\rho\omega^2 \int_S n_b(\mathbf{x})C_{abik}\Gamma_{id}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})n_k(\mathbf{y})\phi_d(\mathbf{y})dS_y \\
&= \oint_S e_{rqs} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_q} \underbrace{\left(e_{rkc}n_b(\mathbf{x})C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})C_{cdjl}\phi_d(\mathbf{y}) \right)}_{A_r^a} n_s(\mathbf{y})dS_y \\
&\quad - \oint_S e_{rqs}e_{rkc}n_b(\mathbf{x})C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial\phi_d(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_q} n_s(\mathbf{y})dS_y \\
&\quad -\rho\omega^2 \int_S n_b(\mathbf{x})C_{abik}\Gamma_{id}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})n_k(\mathbf{y})\phi_d(\mathbf{y})dS_y \\
&= - \oint_{\partial S} \underbrace{A_r^a}_0 dy_r \quad (\because \text{Stokes' theorem}) \\
&\quad - \oint_S e_{rqs}e_{rkc}n_b(\mathbf{x})C_{abik} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial\phi_d(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_q} n_s(\mathbf{y})dS_y \\
&\quad -\rho\omega^2 \int_S n_b(\mathbf{x})C_{abik}\Gamma_{id}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})n_k(\mathbf{y})\phi_d(\mathbf{y})dS_y \\
&= \oint_S n_b(\mathbf{x})C_{abik}e_{rck}C_{cdjl} \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \Gamma_{ij}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})e_{rqs} \frac{\partial\phi_d(\mathbf{y})}{\partial y_q} n_s(\mathbf{y})dS_y \\
&\quad -\rho\omega^2 \int_S n_b(\mathbf{x})C_{abik}\Gamma_{id}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})n_k(\mathbf{y})\phi_d(\mathbf{y})dS_y.
\end{aligned}$$

Bibliography

- [1] K. Abe and K. Koro. BEM analysis with piecewise constant non-orthogonal wavelets. In *Proc. of the 16th Japan National Symposium on Boundary Element Methods*, volume 16, pages 51–56, 1999. (in Japanese).
- [2] M. Abramowitz and I.A. Stegun. *Handbook of Mathematical Functions*. Dover, New York, 1965.
- [3] A.W. Appel. An efficient program for many-body simulation. *SIAM J. Sci. Stat. Comp.*, 6:85–103, 1985.
- [4] J. Barnes and P. Hut. A hierarchical $O(N \log N)$ force calculation algorithm. *Nature*, 324:446–449, 1986.
- [5] G. Beylkin, R. Coifman, and V. Rokhlin. Fast wavelet transforms and numerical algorithms i. *Comm. Pure Appl. Math.*, 44:141–183, 1991.
- [6] L.C. Biedenharn and J.D. Louck. *Angular momentum in quantum physics: theory and application*. Addison Wesley, London, 1981.
- [7] J. Board and K. Schulten. The fast multipole algorithm. *Comp. Sci. Eng.*, 2(1):76–79, 2000.
- [8] M. Challacombe, C. White, and M. Head-Gordon. Periodic boundary conditions and the fast multipole method. *J. Chem. Phys.*, 107(23):10131–10140, 1997.
- [9] W.-H. Chen and C.-C. Huang. Three-dimensional thermal analysis of an infinite solid containing an elliptical surface crack. *Int. J. Fracture*, 54:225–234, 1992.
- [10] Y.H. Chen, W.C. Chew, and S. Zeroug. Fast multipole method as an efficient solver for 2D elastic wave surface integral equations. *Comp. Mech.*, 20:495–506, 1997.
- [11] H. Cheng, L. Greengard, and V. Rokhlin. A fast adaptive multipole algorithm in three dimensions. *J. Comp. Phys.*, pages 468–498, 1999.
- [12] R. Coifman, V. Rokhlin, and S. Wandzura. *IEEE Antennas and Propagation Magazine*, 35(3):7–12, 1993.
- [13] B. Dembart and E. Yip. The accuracy of fast multipole methods for Maxwell’s equations. *IEEE Comp. Sci. Eng.*, 5(3):48–56, 1998.
- [14] H.-Q. Ding, N. Karasawa, and W.A. Goddard III. Atomic level simulations on a million particles: The cell multipole method for Coulomb and London nonbond interactions. *J. Chem. Phys.*, 97(6):4309–4315, 1992.
- [15] W.D. Elliott and J.A. Board Jr. Fast multipole algorithm for the Lennard-Jones potential. Technical Report 94-005, Duke University, 1994.
- [16] W.D. Elliott and J.A. Board Jr. Fast Fourier transform accelerated fast multipole algorithm. *SIAM J. Sci. Comput.*, 17(2):398–415, 1996.
- [17] M.A. Epton and B. Dembart. Multipole translation theory for the three-dimensional Laplace and Helmholtz equations. *SIAM J. Sci. Comput.*, 16(4):865–897, 1995.
- [18] Y. Fu, K.J. Klimkowski, G.J. Rodin, E. Berger, J.C. Browne, J.K. Singer, R.A. van de Geijin, and K.S. Vemaganti. A fast solution method for three-dimensional many-particle problems of linear elasticity. *Int. J. Numer. Meth. Engng.*, 43:1215–1229, 1998.

- [19] Y. Fu, J.R. Overfelt, and G.J. Rodin. Fast summation methods and integral equations. In M. Bonnet, A.M. Saendig, and W. Wendland, editors, *Mathematical Aspects of Boundary Element Methods*, pages 128–139. CRC Press, 1999.
- [20] Y. Fu and G.J. Rodin. Fast solution method for three-dimensional Stokesian many-particle problems. *Commun. Numer. Meth. Engng.*, 16:145–149, 2000.
- [21] H. Fujiwara. The fast multipole method for integral equations of seismic scattering problems. *Geophys. Int. J.*, pages 773–782, 1998.
- [22] H. Fujiwara. The fast multipole method for solving integral equations of three-dimensional topography and basin problems. *Geophys. Int. J.*, pages 198–210, 2000.
- [23] T. Fukui and J. Hattori. Fast multipole boundary element method. In *Proc. Conf. Computational Engineering and Science*, volume 1, pages 319–322, 1996. (in Japanese).
- [24] T. Fukui and K. Inoue. Fast multipole boundary element method in 2D elastodynamics. *J. Appl. Mech. JSCE*, 1:373–380, 1998. (in Japanese).
- [25] T. Fukui and J. Katsumoto. Fast multipole algorithm for two dimensional Helmholtz equation and its application to boundary element method. In *Proc. 14th Japan Nat. Symp. BEM*, volume 14, pages 81–86, 1997. (in Japanese).
- [26] T. Fukui and J. Katsumoto. Fast multipole boundary element method accelerated by FFT in two dimensional scattering problems. In *Proc. 15th Japan Nat. Symp. BEM*, volume 15, pages 93–98, 1998. (in Japanese).
- [27] T. Fukui and T. Kutsumi. Fast multipole boundary element method in three dimensional elastostatic problems. In *Proc. 15th Japan Nat. Symp. BEM*, volume 15, pages 99–104, 1998. (in Japanese).
- [28] T. Fukui and T. Mochida. Fast multipole boundary element analysis in plane elastostatics. In *Proc. Conf. Computational Engineering and Science*, volume 2, pages 321–324, 1997. (in Japanese).
- [29] N. Geng, A. Sullivan, and L. Carin. Fast multipole method for scattering from 3-D PEC targets situated in a half-space environment. *Microwave Opt. Technol. Lett.*, 21(6), 1999.
- [30] J.E. Gómez and H. Power. A multipole direct and indirect bem for 2D cavity flow at low reynolds number. *Eng. Anal. Boundary Elements*, 19:17–31, 1997.
- [31] J.E. Gómez and H. Power. A parallel multipolar indirect boundary element method for the Neumann interior Stokes flow problem. *Int. J. Numer. Meth. Engng.*, 48:523–543, 2000.
- [32] A.E. Green and W. Zerna. *Theoretical Elasticity*. Oxford University Press, London, 1968.
- [33] L. Greengard. *The rapid evaluation of potential fields in particle systems*. MIT Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts, 1988.
- [34] L. Greengard, J. Huang, V. Rokhlin, and S. Wandzura. Accelerating fast multipole methods for the Helmholtz equation at low frequencies. *IEEE Comp. Sci. Eng.*, 5(3):32–38, 1998.
- [35] L. Greengard and V. Rokhlin. A fast algorithm for particle simulations. *J. Computat. Phys.*, 73:325–348, 1987.
- [36] L. Greengard and V. Rokhlin. A new version of the fast multipole method for the Laplace equation in three dimensions. *Acta Numerica*, pages 229–269, 1997.
- [37] M.F. Gyure and M.A. Stalzer. A prescription for the multilevel Helmholtz FMM. *IEEE Comp. Sci. Eng.*, 5(3):39–47, 1998.
- [38] W. Hackbusch and Z.P. Nowak. On the fast matrix multiplication in the boundary element method by panel clustering. *Numerische Mathematik*, 54:463–491, 1989.
- [39] K. Hayami and S.A. Sauter. A formulation of panel clustering method for the three-dimensional elastostatics problem. In *Proc. of the 13th Japan National Symposium on Boundary Element Methods*, volume 13, pages 125–130, 1996.

- [40] K. Hayami and S.A. Sauter. Application of panel clustering method to the three-dimensional 3-d elastostatic problems. In M. Marchettia, C.A. Brebbia, and M.H. Aliabadi, editors, *Boundary Elements XIX*, pages 625–634. Computational Mechanics Publications, 1997.
- [41] K. Hayami and S.A. Sauter. Panel clustering for 3-d elastostatics using spherical harmonics. In A. Kassab et al., editors, *Boundary Elements XX*, pages 289–298. Computational Mechanics Publications, 1998.
- [42] J. Helsing. Fast and accurate numerical solution to an elastostatic problem involving ten thousand randomly oriented cracks. *Int. J. Fracture*, 100:321–327, 2000.
- [43] E.W. Hobson. *The theory of spherical and ellipsoidal harmonics*. Cambridge University Press, 1931.
- [44] T. Hrycak and V. Rokhlin. An improved fast multipole algorithm for potential fields. *SIAM J. Sci. Comput.*, 19(6):1804–1826, 1998.
- [45] B. Hu, W.C. Chew, E. Michielssen, and J. Zhao. Fast inhomogeneous plane wave algorithm for the fast analysis of two-dimensional scattering problems. *Radio Science*, 34(4):759–772, 1999.
- [46] B. Hu, W.C. Chew, E. Michielssen, and J. Zhao. Fast inhomogeneous plane wave algorithm for electromagnetic solutions in layered medium structures: Two-dimensional case. *Radio Science*, 35(1):31–43, 2000.
- [47] T. Iritani, K. Yoshida, N. Nishimura, and S. Kobayashi. A new formulation of FMBIEM in elastodynamics. In *Proc. Conf. Computational Engineering and Science*, volume 5, pages 301–304, 2000. (in Japanese).
- [48] J.F. Leathrum Jr. and J.A. Board Jr. The parallel fast multipole algorithm in three dimensions. Technical Report 92-001, Duke University, 1992.
- [49] T. Kaneko, K. Amaya, and S. Aoki. Effective optimization of corrosion protection design by fast multipole boundary element method. In *Proc. of the 13th Computational Mechanics Conference*, volume 00-17, pages 91–92, 2000. (in Japanese).
- [50] S. Koc and W.C. Chew. Calculation of acoustical scattering from a cluster of scatterers. *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, 103(2):721–734, 1998.
- [51] V.D. Kupradze, T.G. Gegelia, M.O. Bachelishvili, and T.V. Burchuladze. *Three-dimensional problems of the mathematical theory of elasticity and thermoelasticity*. North-Holland, 1979.
- [52] C. Lage and C. Schwab. Wavelet Galerkin algorithms for boundary integral equations. *SIAM J. Sci. Comput.*, 20(6):2195–2222, 1999.
- [53] A. Leitner. Diffraction of sound by a circular disk. *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, 21(4):331–334, 1949.
- [54] C.-C. Lu and W.C. Chew. A multilevel algorithm for solving a boundary integral equation of wave scattering. *Microwave Opt. Technol. Lett.*, 7(10), 1994.
- [55] C.C. Lu and W.C. Chew. Fast algorithm for solving hybrid integral equations. *IEE Proc. H*, 140(6):455–460, 1993.
- [56] A.K. Mal. Interaction of elastic waves with a penny-shaped crack. *Int. J. Engng. Sci.*, 8:381–388, 1970.
- [57] A.A. Mammoli and M.S. Ingber. Stokes flow around cylinders in a bounded two-dimensional domain using multipole-accelerated boundary element. *Int. J. Numer. Meth. Engng.*, 44:897–917, 1999.
- [58] A.A. Mammoli and M.S. Ingber. Parallel multipole BEM simulation of two-dimensional suspension flows. *Eng. Anal. Boundary Elements*, 24:65–73, 2000.
- [59] A. MESSIAH. *Quantum mechanics*. John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1968.
- [60] M. Miyakoshi, N. Nishimura, and S. Kobayashi. Fast multipole Galerkin integral equation method for crack problems. In *Proc. BTEC-98*, pages 39–42, 1998. (in Japanese).
- [61] P.M. Morse and H. Feshbach. *Methods of theoretical physics*. McGraw-Hill, New York, 1953.

- [62] T. Nishida and K. Hayami. Application of the fast multipole method to the 3D BEM analysis of electron guns. In M. Marchettia, C.A. Brebbia, and M.H. Aliabadi, editors, *Boundary Elements XIX*, pages 613–622. Computational Mechanics Publications, 1997.
- [63] N. Nishimura and S. Kobayashi. A regularized boundary integral equation method for elastodynamic crack problems. *Comp. Mech.*, 4:319–328, 1989.
- [64] N. Nishimura, M. Miyakoshi, and S. Kobayashi. Application of new multipole boundary integral equation method to crack problems. In *Proc. BTEC-99*, pages 75–78, 1999. (in Japanese).
- [65] N. Nishimura, K. Yoshida, and S. Kobayashi. A fast multipole boundary integral equation method for crack problems in 3D. *Eng. Anal. Boundary Elements*, 23:97–105, 1999.
- [66] J.M. Pérez-Jordá and W. Yang. A concise redefinition of the solid spherical harmonics and its use in fast multipole methods. *J. Chem. Phys.*, 104(20):8003–8006, 1996.
- [67] T. von Petersdoff, C. Schwab, and R. Schneider. Multi wavelets for second-kind integral equations. *SIAM J. Num. Anal.*, 34:2213–2227, 1997.
- [68] A. Rathsfeld. A wavelet algorithm for the boundary element solution of a geodetic boundary value problem. *Comm. Meth. Appl. Math. Eng.*, 157:267–287, 1998.
- [69] V. Rokhlin. Rapid solution of integral equations of classical potential theory. *J. Comp. Phys.*, 60:187–207, 1985.
- [70] V. Rokhlin. Rapid solution of integral equations of scattering theory in two dimensions. *J. Comp. Phys.*, 86:414–439, 1990.
- [71] V. Rokhlin. Diagonal forms of translation operators for the Helmholtz equation in three dimensions. *Appl. Comp. Harmonic Anal.*, 1:82–93, 1993.
- [72] V. Rokhlin. Sparse diagonal forms for translation operators for the Helmholtz equation in two dimensions. *Appl. Comp. Harmonic Anal.*, 5:36–67, 1998.
- [73] S.A. Sauter. Variable order panel clustering(extended version). Preprint 52, Max-Planck-Institut für Mathematik in den Naturwissenschaften Leipzig, 1999.
- [74] K. Schulten and R.G. Gordon. Exact recursive evaluation of 3j- and 6j-coefficients for quantum-mechanical coupling of angular momenta. *J. Math. Phys.*, 16(10):1961–1970, 1975.
- [75] A. Sommerfeld. *Partial differential equations in physics*. Academic Press, 1949.
- [76] J. Song, C.-C. Lu, and W.C. Chew. Multilevel fast multipole algorithm for electromagnetic scattering by large complex objects. *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propagation*, 45(10), 1997.
- [77] J.M. Song and W.C. Chew. Fast multipole method solution using parametric geometry. *Microwave Opt. Technol. Lett.*, 7(16):760–765, 1994.
- [78] T. Takahashi, N. Nishimura, and S. Kobayashi. Fast multipole BEM simulation of overcoring in an improved conical-end borehole strain method. In *Proc. of the 13th Japan National Symposium on Boundary Element Methods*, volume 13, pages 125–130, 1996. (in Japanese).
- [79] T. Takahashi, N. Nishimura, and S. Kobayashi. A multipole integral equation method for stationary stokes flow problems in 3D. In *Proc. BTEC*, volume 10, pages 1–4, 2000. (in Japanese).
- [80] P.R. Wallace. *Mathematical analysis of physical problems*. Dover, New York, 1984.
- [81] C.A. White and M. Head-Gordon. Derivation and efficient implementation of the fast multipole method. *J. Chem. Phys.*, 101(8):6593–6605, 1994.
- [82] C.A. White and M. Head-Gordon. Rotating around the quartic angular momentum barrier in fast multipole method calculations. *J. Chem. Phys.*, 105(12):5061–5067, 1996.
- [83] N. Yarvin and V. Rokhlin. Generalized Gaussian quadratures and singular value decomposition of integral operators. *SIAM J. Sci. Comput.*, 20(2):699–718, 1998.

- [84] K. Yoshida, N. Nishimura, and S. Kobayashi. Analysis of three dimensional elastostatic crack problems with fast multipole boundary integral equation method. *J. Appl. Mech. JSCE*, 1:365–372, 1998. (in Japanese).
- [85] K. Yoshida, N. Nishimura, and S. Kobayashi. Analysis of three dimensional scattering of elastic waves by a crack with fast multipole boundary integral equation method. *J. Appl. Mech. JSCE*, 3:143–150, 2000. (in Japanese).
- [86] K. Yoshida, N. Nishimura, and S. Kobayashi. Analysis of three dimensional scattering of scalar waves by cracks with fast multipole boundary integral equation method. *Trans. JSME (A)*, 67:16–22, 2001. (in Japanese).
- [87] K. Yoshida, N. Nishimura, and S. Kobayashi. Application of fast multipole Galerkin boundary integral equation method to elastostatic crack problems in 3D. *Int. J. Numer. Meth. Engng.*, 50:525–547, 2001.
- [88] K. Yoshida, N. Nishimura, and S. Kobayashi. Application of new fast multipole boundary integral equation method to crack problems in 3D. *Eng. Anal. Boundary Elements*, 25:239–247, 2001.
- [89] K. Yoshida, N. Nishimura, and S. Kobayashi. Application of new fast multipole boundary integral equation method to elastostatic crack problems in three dimensions. *J. Structure Eng. JSCE*, 47A:169–179, 2001.
- [90] H. Yoshikawa, N. Nishimura, and S. Kobayashi. Fast solution method for three dimensional crack problems using wavelet BIEM. In *Proc. of the 16th Japan National Symposium on Boundary Element Methods*, volume 16, pages 63–68, 1999. (in Japanese).